

November 2021

TO BE: Lessons from international innovation practices

Appendix to main report with case studies

Erik Arnold, Alexandra Patriksson, Amanda Bengtsson Jallow, Reda Nausedaite, Kalle Nielsen, Jonatan Ryd, Beate Rygg Johnsen, Anders Braarud Hanssen, Peter Varnai, Göran Melin

November 2021

TO BE: Lessons from international innovation practices

Appendix to main report with case studies

Erik Arnold, Alexandra Patriksson, Amanda Bengtsson Jallow, Reda Nausedaite, Kalle Nielsen, Jonatan Ryd, Beate Rygg Johnsen, Anders Braarud Hanssen, Peter Varnai, Göran Melin

Table of Contents

1	adMare Bioinnovations	1
1.1	Background	1
1.2	Context	1
1.3	Domains of relevance for this case	3
1.3.1	Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital	3
1.3.2	Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems	4
1.3.3	Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use	5
1.3.4	Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations	5
1.3.5	Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems	6
1.4	Conclusions	8
2	BioInnovation Institute (BII)	10
2.1	Background and context	10
2.2	Domains of relevance for this case	10
2.2.1	Domain 2 – Funding from research to commercialisation	10
2.2.2	Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems	12
	Venture Lab	14
	Creation House	15
	The role of BII vs the role of the TTO	16
3	Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre (IBioIC)	18
3.1	Introduction	18
3.2	Background	18
3.3	Domains of relevance for this case	21
3.3.1	Domain 1 – Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence	21
3.3.2	Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital	22
3.3.3	Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems	25
3.3.4	Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use	26
3.3.5	Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations	27
3.3.6	Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems	28
3.4	Conclusions	29
4	The Institute of Marine Research (Havforskningsinstituttet)	32
4.1.1	Domain 1 – Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence	32
4.2	Domains of relevance for this case	34
4.2.1	Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems	34
4.2.2	Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use	34
4.2.3	Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations	36

4.2.4	Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems	36
4.2.5	Domain 7 – RRI	37
4.3	Conclusions	38
5	KU Leuven Research & Development (LRD)	39
5.1	Background and context	39
5.2	Domains of relevance for this case	40
5.2.1	Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital	40
5.2.2	Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems	44
5.2.3	Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations	46
5.2.4	Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems	47
5.3	Conclusions	50
6	UK Centre for Mammalian Synthetic Biology (Edinburgh)	52
6.1	Introduction	52
6.2	Background	52
6.2.1	UK policy background	52
6.2.2	The Mammalian Centre	52
6.3	Domains of relevance for this case	53
6.3.1	Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital	53
6.3.2	Domain 7 – RRI	54
6.4	Conclusions	56
6.5	List of references	56
6.5.1	Interviews	56
6.5.2	Policy background:	56
6.5.3	SysSynth-Mammalian	57
7	Nofima	58
7.1	Background and context	58
7.1.1	Domain 1 – Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence	58
7.2	Domains of relevance for this case	59
7.2.1	Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems	59
7.2.2	Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use	59
7.2.3	Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations	61
7.2.4	Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems	62
7.2.5	Domain 7 – RRI	65
7.3	Conclusions	66
8	Sustainable Aquaculture Innovation Centre (SAIC)	67
8.1	Introduction	67
8.2	Background	67

8.3	Domains of relevance for this case	70
8.3.1	Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital	70
8.3.2	Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems	73
8.3.3	Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use	75
8.3.4	Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the universities	76
8.3.5	Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems	78
8.3.6	Domain – 7 RRI	78
8.4	Conclusions	79
9	SynbiCITE	82
9.1	Background	82
9.2	Context	82
9.3	Domains of relevance for this case	84
9.3.1	Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital	84
9.3.2	Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems	85
9.3.3	Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use	87
9.3.4	Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations	88
9.3.5	Domain 7 – RRI	88
9.4	Conclusions	89
10	SYNBIOCHEM	92
10.1	Introduction	92
10.2	Background and context	92
10.2.1	UK investment in Synthetic Biology (Synbio)	92
10.2.2	RRI and Synthetic Biology in the UK	92
10.2.3	The SYNBIOCHEM Centre	93
10.3	Domains of relevance for this case	94
10.3.1	Domain 7 – RRI	94
10.4	Lessons	98
10.5	Conclusions	98
10.6	List of references	99
10.6.1	Interviews	99
10.6.2	Policy background:	99
10.6.3	SYNBIOCHEM	99
11	Umeå Biotech Incubator	101
11.1	Background and context	101
11.2	Domains of relevance for this case	101
11.2.1	Domain 1 – Digital life capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence	101
11.2.2	Domain 2 – Funding from research to commercialisation	102

11.2.3 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems _____	103
11.2.4 Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use _____	104
11.2.5 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations _____	105
11.2.6 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems _____	106
12 Flemish Institute for Biotechnology VIB (Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie) _____	112
12.1 Background and context _____	112
12.2 Domains of relevance for this case _____	113
12.2.1 Domain 1 – Digital life capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence _____	113
12.2.2 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital _____	115
12.2.3 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems _____	117
12.2.4 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems _____	120
12.3 Conclusions _____	124
13 Wageningen University and Research _____	126
13.1 Background and context _____	126
13.2 Domains of relevance for this case _____	129
13.2.1 Domain 1 – Digital life capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence _____	129
13.2.2 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital _____	131
13.2.3 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems _____	132
13.2.4 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems _____	135
13.3 Conclusions _____	140

1 adMare Bioinnovations

1.1 Background

adMare BioInnovations is a pan-Canadian organisation funded by public and private actors focused on building the national life sciences industry. They serve as a one-stop destination for new commercial opportunities in drug development, with resources including scientific and business expertise, R&D infrastructure, and the necessary capital to transform a health-related technology into a growing company. Their vision is to be a 'catalyst for Canadian life sciences leading the world' with a mission to:

- Translate leading academic research into new companies of scale
- Help existing Canadian companies scale-up
- Train the next generation of highly qualified personnel to drive the growth of companies into strong anchors

adMare has brought together different aspects of the commercialisation process under one roof, and provides important insight for Digital Life Norway in multiple areas. Although adMare is mostly focused on life sciences related to human health and drug development, they collaborate with actors in other fields such as digitalisation and radiopharmaceuticals.

The domains of relevance in this case study are *Domain 2: Funding from research to venture capital*, *Domain 3: Operating within innovation ecosystems*, *Domain 4: Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use*, and *Domain 5: Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations*.

For domain 2, more specifically related to capital investment, beyond adMare's own capital to invest, in 2020 they merged with Accel-RX, a life sciences seed investment specialist. This enhances adMare's expertise and resources in seed-stage investment. adMare's preferred investment approach is through equity investment that promises returns to adMare. In domain 3, the case study showcases adMare's national perspective and their approach to strengthen the innovation ecosystem. Domain 4 gives insight into how adMare connects knowledge producers and users through their foresight process. Finally, domain 5 explores how the adMare Academy contributes to talent creation to sustain the life sciences R&D ecosystem in Canada.

For this case study, we have interviewed Barry Gee, Senior Director of Communications and External Relations who also quality assured the case.

1.2 Context

adMare BioInnovations is a pan-Canadian not-for-profit organisation focused on building the national industrial base for life sciences. The enterprise was formed in 2019 through the merger of the Centre for Drug Research and Development (CDRD) which was Canada's national life sciences venture based in Vancouver and the NEOMED Institute, a not-for-profit R&D organisation building an innovation ecosystem in Montréal. In early 2020 Accel-RX, a Canadian health-science seed investor, joined adMare.

CDRD was established to improve the commercialisation rate of the Canadian research base. The Centre was founded in 2007 with funding from the federal and provincial (British Columbia) government, and has been working to accelerate Canadian research, partnering with research organisations to develop and commercialise their discoveries. The focus of the Centre was threefold: spinning out companies of scale; helping existing companies scale up; and

training life sciences personnel, both on the science and business side.¹ CDRD evaluated more than 1,400 technologies for their commercial and therapeutic potential. Of those, 269 were incubated within CDRD and 58 were successfully advanced towards commercialisation, generating 72 patents.²

The NEOMED Institute was created in 2012 when AstraZeneca closed their pharmaceutical research centre in Montreal. AstraZeneca then donated their R&D site, equipment, and four therapeutic discovery programmes to a group of academics who then turned the R&D site into an incubator focusing on commercialising research. The institute was funded from the federal government through the programme Centres of Excellence for Commercialization of Research (CECR) and from pharmaceutical companies including AstraZeneca, Pfizer Canada, GlaxoSmithKline as well as the government of Quebec.³

To further utilise Canada's resources and create a more dynamic and efficient environment for commercialising research and create world-leading companies, the federal government urged CDRD and NEOMED to consider an alternative model. Thus, adMare was created through the merger of CDRD and NEOMED Institute bringing together the respective organisations' expertise under one roof and then scale this up to a more cohesive national focus. adMare is led by a single management team and a single Board of Directors – each derived from both CDRD and NEOMED – reflecting the organisation's stakeholders across academia, industry, the investment community, and government.⁴

Recently, Accel-Rx, a Canadian life science seed capital investor, was also brought in under the adMare organisation. This has added expertise and capability in seed-stage investment and entrepreneur development to adMare which will further strengthen adMare's position as a single-stop destination. Together they can stimulate co-investment by private investors to provide capital for early-stage life sciences companies and help enable them to successfully create sustainable value in Canada.⁵

Together these three organisations bring together drug development capabilities, business expertise, scientific expertise, training of talent, and seed capital under one roof to drive health-related technology to a company of scale. adMare supports translating discovery research into new life sciences companies; scaling up existing companies; and providing training relevant to both these stages. There are also physical incubation facilities.⁶ The mission of adMare is to:

- Translate leading academic research into new companies of scale
- Help existing Canadian companies scale-up
- Train the next generation of highly qualified personnel to drive the growth of companies into strong anchors

The funding partners are:

- Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada

¹ https://pharma.nridigital.com/pharma_may18/inside_canada_s_centre_for_drug_research_and_development

² https://www.nce-rce.gc.ca/NetworksCentres-CentresReseaux/CECR-CECR/CDRD-CRDM_eng.asp

³ <https://innovationsoftheworld.com/neomed-institute-a-non-profit-research-development-organization/>

⁴ <https://www.admarebio.com/cdrd-neomed-institute-join-forces-to-create-a-new-pan-canadian-enterprise-admare-bioinnovations/>

⁵ <https://www.admarebio.com/admare-accelrx-unite-to-advance-canadian-life-sciences/>

⁶ <https://www.admarebio.com/about/the-admare-way/>

- The Ministère de l'Économie et de l'Innovation
- City of Montreal
- Pfizer Canada Inc.
- ROBIC (a firm specialised in intellectual property)

adMare is a not-for-profit organisation with several different legal entities under its name. The legal structure allows adMare to bring in revenue while maintaining its not-for-profit status, and allowing adMare to reinvest and develop its operations to ultimately become self-sustainable. The organisation employs around 100 people, mainly in Vancouver but also approximately 30 people in Montreal and a handful in Toronto. In the beginning circa 80 percent of the employees were scientists. Today around 60 percent are scientists. The partnership team, IP-team, and investment team have grown, accounting for the rest of the employees.⁷

adMare BioInnovations has since its creation supported a portfolio of over 25 companies which have attracted \$1.4b of investment and have a combined worth of over \$3b. More than 900 jobs have been created in Canada, 260 people have graduated from the adMare academy with 96 percentage being employed by the Canadian life sciences industry and 85 new potential therapies has been developed.⁸ The adMare Innovation Centre, located in Montreal Technoparc, hosts over 20 strategic companies playing a key role in the life sciences value chain. The resident companies offer services in medicinal chemistry, assay development, DMPK, intellectual property, and strategic recruitment consulting.

1.3 Domains of relevance for this case

1.3.1 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital

Capital investment

adMare provides resources to researchers at early stages, which is the typical reason why actors approach adMare – to support further development of their technology toward commercialisation. This is made possible from adMare's two streams of funding, one being public funding which accounts for \$16m per year and the other being revenue from commercial sources which accounts for \$15m per year. adMare has a vision of becoming economically self-sustainable through return on investment from its investment portfolio. The investment portfolio is slowly growing and yielding more and more return on investment but achieving the vision of economic sustainability takes long time and needs significant public sector investment. adMare also receives some support from the private sector, but this has decreased over the years because of a shift in their model to focus more solely on Canadian company creation vs. licensing of technology to multi-nationals.⁹

The funding streams allow adMare to invest in technology that requires additional validation as well as support companies in pre-seed capital investments. The sectors which are of focus for adMare's investments are mainly human health related life sciences, more specifically therapeutics and diagnostics, but emerging areas such as AI and digital health are also under consideration.

The criteria for adMare to invest are:

⁷ Interview

⁸ <https://www.admarebio.com/outcomes-impacts/>

⁹ Interview

- Differentiation and competitive advantage of a technology
- Quality of the team; Willing and engaged PI
- Ability to take the project to the next value inflection point (milestone)
- Scope and strength of IP coverage
- Type of co-investors
- Potential investment returns

According to the interviewee, a willing and engaged PI is one of the top lying criteria for adMare to consider investing in a technology/company. The PI must realise that the investment is not just monetary, but in fact a partnership where adMare brings relevant expertise to the table for the technology/company to grow. Furthermore, the innovation process team is an important building stone since they are the bridge between the academia and industry.¹⁰ The PI also retains control over the project throughout the support, and all original intellectual property remains with the PI and their institution.¹¹

The initial investment from adMare into companies generally ranges between \$500k to \$3m which can be followed by further investment of a similar scale. The investment type is tailored around the company, but the primarily one used is equity. With equity, adMare gets a return on investment allowing it to eventually become self-sustainable when its portfolio of companies has grown. adMare can either be the sole investor, or a co-investor alongside venture capitalists, (and prefers to have interest/involvement of other investors as early as possible).

The investment strategy of the previous CDRD was to build a company around one or two technologies, making the spin-offs quite thin. When adMare was created, the strategy shifted towards gathering several technologies and forming a company around all of them to allow the company to have a more solid ground to build upon.¹²

1.3.2 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

The innovation ecosystem in Canada consists of many different funding programmes and agencies. adMare BioInnovations is by far the biggest seed investor and the most nationally orientated. The other similar organisations are mostly looking at parts of adMare's focus, are regionally focused, or focus on a specific technology or therapeutic area. One such organisation in the life sciences area is Centre for Commercialisation of Regenerative Medicine (CCRM) in Toronto which specialise in regenerative medicine.¹³ Another investment made by the Canadian government is the Super Cluster Programme. The Clusters are areas of intense business activity made up of companies, academia, and not-for-profit organisations that boost innovation and growth in a particular industry. There are currently five Super Clusters in the areas of: Digital Technology, Protein Industries, Advanced Manufacturing, Scale AI, Ocean.¹⁴ According to the interviewee adMare has instead focused on a broad expertise in the commercialisation process and subject matter expertise only in drug development.

¹⁰ Interview

¹¹ <https://www.admarebio.com/partnering-with-academics/the-admare-advantage/>

¹² Interview

¹³ <https://www.ccrm.ca/>

¹⁴ <https://www.ic.gc.ca/eic/site/093.nsf/eng/00016.html>

1.3.3 Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use

adMare's predecessor CDRD was primarily reactive to what researchers were working on, and was less focused on potential commercial/investor demand. The risk with this approach was that many years and large amounts of money could be put into a new technology that ultimately was not wanted by the market.¹⁵ Therefore, when adMare was created, a foresight process was also created. This is a process whereby a team of experts – scientific and business experts – use numerous means to analyse and evaluate areas of potential commercial opportunity. That enables adMare to identify which areas could hold the most strategic value to the organisation and which could form a basis of a multi-asset financeable company of scale in Canada. Further on, adMare carries out a proactive, focused search throughout academia for researchers that might have novel therapeutic approaches that are aligned to the existing or anticipated interests and needs of commercial end users (generally, investors positioned to advance a technology through clinical trials). While implementing this strategic approach, adMare also remains open to the presentation of opportunities directly from academic researchers who are wanting to advance their work.¹⁶ This is further described in Domain 6.

1.3.4 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations

The adMare Academy

adMare has since their creation tried to systematise the process of commercialising research and building companies around technologies. To successfully do this, adMare has identified a market gap in talent that can work in the industry. Either, Canadian researchers and business professionals go to the US, or those coming to Canada are not dedicated to stay there for a longer time.¹⁷ To fill this gap, the adMare Academy was created.

The adMare Academy provides specialised training required to foster the next generation of highly qualified personnel who can meet the demand and drive the growth of Canadian life sciences companies into anchor companies. The academy has four different levels of training – **Executive Institute, BioInnovation Scientist Program, Fellowship Program, Undergraduate Institute**. Each level provides customised training programme to ensure that the life science sector in Canada has the management talent required.¹⁸

From the academy, more commercially minded scientists will be able to enter the industry and develop research into novel therapies and technologies. Since the creation, the academy has graduated 225 post-docs, 96 percent of whom went on to relevant jobs in the industry with approximately 85 percent of them currently work in Canada.

Executive Institute

The Executive Institute is a 10-month custom designed development program where the focus is on training future management talent to think in more complex, systematic, and strategic ways. This education programme focuses on up-and-coming mid-career talent who can attract money to the industry. The Executive Institute is supported with a \$1m contribution from Pfizer Canada and delivered in collaboration with the not-for-profit Centre for Creative

¹⁵ Interview

¹⁶ <https://bioprocessintl.com/business/bioregions/admare-bioinnovations-canada-the-next-global-life-science-leader/>

¹⁷ Interview

¹⁸ <https://www.admarebio.com/admare-academy/the-admare-academy-way/>

Leadership. The program combines researched and proven best practices/principles with targeted industry topics.¹⁹

The BioInnovation Scientist Program

The BioInnovation Scientist Program is the biggest of the four education levels and is focused on supporting scientists acquiring the required skillset to accelerate an efficient and successful translation of scientific discoveries to commercialisation. The programme is designed to complement the academic education and employer talent programmes to improve the skills of researchers to be able to innovate.²⁰

The Fellowship Program

The Fellowship Program is a programme for recently graduated PhD-students who can work alongside the R&D team at adMare. Fellows are invited for a 24-month research intensive fellowship which is designed to offer scientific experience. The fellows will in addition to contribute to numerous therapeutic programmes focusing on data generation, also receive on-the-job training supplemented with customised learning and development initiatives to advance their understanding of drug development lifecycle and personal skills acquisition.²¹

The Undergraduate Institute

The Undergraduate Institute recruits undergraduate students for co-op programmes and gives students hands-on skills development. The programme runs for 4-8 months.

1.3.5 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

Scouting for innovations

As mentioned in Domain 4, adMare carries out a proactive, focused search throughout academia for researchers that might have novel therapeutic approaches that are aligned to the existing or anticipated interests and needs of commercial end users (generally, investors positioned to advance a technology through clinical trials). While implementing this strategic approach, adMare also remains open to the presentation of opportunities directly from academic researchers who are wanting to advance their work.²²

To be able to search through academia, adMare has spent a lot of time and resources in building relationships with the universities and TTO's in Canada. Now adMare has extensive insight into which TTO's and universities are more conducive to collaboration. When adMare tries to commercialise research, they do not just develop a technology and license it through the TTO's. Instead, they build companies around technologies which in turn attract entrepreneurially minded researchers.²³

A key pillar of adMare's mission is to help existing Canadian life sciences companies scale up. The single-stop destination provides companies with the necessary scientific, business, infrastructure, and capital resources to drive health-related technology to a company of scale. adMare partners with Canadian life sciences companies in a flexible shared risk/reward model.

¹⁹ <https://www.admarebio.com/admare-academy/executive-institute/>

²⁰ <https://www.admarebio.com/admare-academy/bioinnovation-scientist-program/>

²¹ <https://www.admarebio.com/admare-academy/fellowship-program/>

²² <https://bioprocessintl.com/business/bioregions/admare-bioinnovations-canada-the-next-global-life-science-leader/>

²³ Interview

By working together and providing expertise, infrastructure, and capital to Canadian companies, adMare helps to advance their pipelines to the next corporate value creation point.²⁴

For each stakeholder group, adMare provides some type of value proposition:

- For academics, the offer is a pathway to advance their research and translate this into a company
- For companies, adMare provides scientific, business, infrastructure, and capital resources to drive health-related technology to a company of scale
- For investors, the offer is new, validated, and de-risked healthcare product opportunities to invest in
- For current and future industry leaders, the adMare academy offers training and a pathway to a successful industry career
- For governments, adMare turns public investment in research into job creation and economic benefit
- For patients, new therapies reaching the market

For the opportunities deemed to hold the most potential in creating/returning value, adMare brings together the very best partners from throughout academia, industry, patient foundations, the investment community, as well as other key opinion leaders. adMare helps build an experienced management team for the company – thus generating a complete and highly-compelling business case to secure the private sector investors, grow the company, and take technologies to patients.²⁵ adMare not only further validate technologies, but also develop them into commercially attractive programmes by generating valuable IP and data and developing and executing on a viable commercial strategy.²⁶

The issue of open science is according to the interviewee an unresolved issue. This is an area of interest for the federal government and adMare, but can conflict with adMare's vision of becoming economically self-sustainable. For adMare to invest into open science and/or science for which there is public interest and/or need, but not a commercial value proposition, they would need more public funds earmarked for this, as it is not consistent with their core mandate.

Helping companies scale up and grow

One challenge in Canada with commercialising research is keeping companies in the country. The neighbour US works as a big vacuum soaking up those companies succeeding in commercialising research. adMare therefore tries to position itself to fill market gaps for a sustained national commercial market. One strategy for adMare has therefore been to build strong spin-off companies which are built around more than one product so they can stay and grow in Canada.²⁷ To do this adMare has two ways of helping existing life sciences companies scale up: to leverage adMare's expertise to help companies solve scientific roadblock to risk capital; to create an ecosystem through their Montreal Innovation Centre where organisations

²⁴ <https://jllabs.jnjinnovation.com/videos/meet-with-admare-bioinnovations>

²⁵ <https://www.admarebio.com/partnering-with-academics/the-admare-way/>

²⁶ <https://bioprocessintl.com/business/bioregions/admare-bioinnovations-canada-the-next-global-life-science-leader/>

²⁷ Interview

can come together, share resources, and use scientific infrastructure which they may not afford on their own.²⁸

For existing life sciences companies, adMare's strategic network offers a key to scaling up and creating anchor firms. For young and promising companies, the resources and support provided by adMare's Innovation Centre are of importance. The innovation centre is a drug discovery hub in Montreal which hosts contract research organisations, biotech companies, and specialised commercialisation support services and infrastructure. The Centre currently hosts 350 entrepreneurs/researchers working at 32 different organisations.²⁹

The access to state-of-the-art facilities is currently providing sophisticated and specialised laboratories and equipment, but also access to an environment that is stimulating and collaborative. An example of the impact: six of the most recent companies welcomed to the Centre expanded from a collective total of only 16 full-time employees, to providing highly-skilled and highly-paid employment to more than 285 people.³⁰

1.4 Conclusions

adMare Bioinnovations is a pan-Canadian 'one-stop shop' supporting start-up, scale-up and entrepreneurship training in the health sciences. The funding partners include both private and public actors. adMare's resources, including scientific and business expertise, infrastructure, and capital enables them to drive health-related technology to a company of scale. Their vision is to be a catalyst for the Canadian life sciences leading the world.

adMare Bioinnovations has since the creation supported over 25 companies which have attracted \$1.15b of investment and have a combined worth of over \$3b. More than 900 jobs have been created in Canada, 260 people have graduated from the adMare academy with 96 percentage being employed by the Canadian life sciences industry and 85 new potential therapies has been developed.

For each stakeholder group, adMare provides some type of value:

- For academics, a pathway to advance their research and start a company
- For companies, adMare provides scientific, business, infrastructure, and capital resources for scale-up
- For investors, validated and de-risked healthcare product investments
- For future industry leaders, training, and a path to a career
- For governments, adMare turns public investment in research into job creation and economic benefit
- For patients, new therapies

The conclusions which can be drawn from the case study which can provide valuable insights for DLN is provided in the bullets below.

- adMare's strategy revolves around identifying needs and demand and coupling these to the process to identifying relevant ideas and people from the research system into start-ups, and then helping with scale-up. These activities are supported by training from the undergraduate to the executive level and the provision of physical infrastructure, advice

²⁸ <https://thefutureeconomy.ca/interviews/gordon-mccauley/>

²⁹ <https://researchinfosource.com/pdf/CIL2019.pdf>

³⁰ <https://www.admarebio.com/admare-innovation-center/>

and networks of other early-stage companies. As a result, it provides both development paths and supportive communities for invention and entrepreneurship.

- Domain 2: adMare reinvests commercial income into new investments with a goal of becoming economically self-sustainable. The organisation is specialised in therapeutics, and diagnostics. adMare focuses on finding more than one new technology which a stable company can be built around in contrast to CDRD's earlier strategy of spinning off a company with one lead technology. One of the most important selection criteria for adMare is a willing and engaging PI who can collaborate with adMare when building a company.
- Domain 3: adMare's state-of-the-art facilities provide specialised laboratories and equipment for drug discovery as well as an environment for researchers to build networks in which adMare staff provide advice and support. For existing life sciences companies, adMare's strategic network offers a key to scaling up and creating anchor firms. For young and promising companies, the resources and support provided by adMare's Innovation Centre are of importance. The facility is currently providing sophisticated and specialised laboratories and equipment, but also access to an environment that is stimulating and collaborative.
- Domain 4: adMare's foresight process enables it to identify which areas could hold the most strategic value to the organisation and which could form a basis of a multi-asset financeable company of scale in Canada. This, coupled with the focused search throughout academia for researchers who might have novel therapeutic approaches that are aligned to the existing or anticipated interests and needs of commercial end users, enables adMare to systematically choose what to invest in. For adMare to invest in open science public funding earmarked for this would be needed.
- Domain 5: The adMare Academy fills a market gap in providing the talent needed in building a sustainable life sciences industry. The Academy educates researchers in entrepreneurship and helps up and coming management talent in acquiring the skills to think in more complex, systematic, and strategic ways.

2 BiInnovation Institute (BII)

2.1 Background and context

The BiInnovation Institute (BII) Foundation is an independent international commercial foundation with a non-profit objective supported by the Novo Nordisk Foundation. The idea of BII came up in Novo Nordisk Foundation (NNF) in 2017, resulting in the establishment of BII as a department at the NNF in 2018. From December 2020 BII is independent from the Novo Nordisk Foundation.

BII is primarily engaged with start-ups and aims to help researchers and other experts having a research-based idea to bring it to the market. The goal is to make the start-ups become investment-ready by bridging the gap between academia and business. BII offers knowledge (Domain 5), network and expertise (Domain 1 and 4), funding (Domain 2) and infrastructure (Domain 6) to promising start-ups, mainly through its two innovation programmes – Venture Lab and Creation House – and through collaboration with relevant service providers, venture capitalists and other experts.

BII names themselves an international hub for research-based innovation and entrepreneurship that help people with a great idea in life science to commercialise research. They cover the areas of therapeutics, health tech and bioindustrials and they claim to “embrace” every phase of the life science innovation process and therefore to be a relevant collaboration partner both for brief ideas and for start-ups/companies with a full business plan.

“BII has had an incredible reception among scientists and entrepreneurs. That is why we are now establishing BII as an independent charitable, commercial foundation, so it can make the most of available opportunities while ensuring its long-term efforts to support excellent research and new ideas along the way,” says Birgitte Nauntofte, CEO of the Novo Nordisk Foundation. “We see great potential to develop new solutions in life science and biotechnology, but good ideas often need support from an early stage of development to be matured and prepared for commercialisation in order to benefit people and societies. That is why BII's task is so important,” she adds.

To date, the Novo Nordisk Foundation has awarded €64m to BII. With continued positive development, The Novo Nordisk Foundation can provide up to €470m to the BII Foundation over 10 years (2021–2030) to support early-stage life science projects and start-ups. BII currently has 30 full-time employees and has ambitions to house more than 500 researchers, innovators and entrepreneurs. BII also aims for more international partnerships in the future.

BII is a relevant case with respect to the health sector and domain 2, 3, and 6.

2.2 Domains of relevance for this case

2.2.1 Domain 2 – Funding from research to commercialisation

BII Faculty programme

The Faculty programme is a new initiative of BII that started in January 2020. The aim of the programme is to support commercializing research in areas where there could be a great potential but where the technical risk is so high that it normally would be very difficult to get funding. The Faculty programme is more long-term strategic than the start-up funding programmes (Domain 6) and look for first-mover trends. It also targets specific fields like women's health where it is difficult to get early financing, or other less funded fields with potential for future growth. The goal is to create new start-ups through cross fertilisation between academic research and BII project/companies.

Participation in the Faculty programme is currently by invitation only on the PI level, and in this first pilot BII has entered a collaboration with four Danish research institutions (DTU, UCPH, Aarhus University and hospitals at the Capital Region of Denmark). The projects that are accepted to the Faculty programme will join BII for up to three years. Each project will be granted up to DKK6m per year. The grant is given to the collaborating research institution.

Once approved for the Faculty programme, the project will have to establish a team including a co-PI and BII will connect project, business development and IP anchors to it. BII requires the co-PI and team to spend most of their time in BII facilities and lab space to work alongside projects and start-ups in the BII programmes. The reason is that BII expects to see benefits from interdisciplinary collaborations and cross-fertilisations of methods and tools between the projects in all BII programmes. By getting the people and projects into the BII sphere it is easier for BII after some time to assess if there is potential in an idea, or if they should drop it. BII also gives advice on IP strategy through the Faculty programme and funds the generation of solid IP portfolio for the project to enable launching future spin-out companies.

BII tries to be strategic and work actively to identify good people and good ideas for the Faculty programme. BII has defined strategic areas of interest that are both scientifically novel and are predicted to have good future market potential. They scout not only in Denmark but also abroad using both systematic mining of scientific and patent databases and through contacting researchers in the extensive BII contact network. They even sometimes identify areas where they would love to see a company built, and use that as a starting point to find someone who would have the right research profile to develop the necessary technology. This strategic perspective also means that there are fields where they do not enter at all. They typically stay away from "red ocean" opportunities where the market is already crowded and competition for investment is high. Traditional clinic medical devices are one such example where the Faculty programme is not actively used.

One risk they see with the Faculty programme and the strategic approach they have chosen, is that they may tend to fund people who already have lots of funding instead of people with the most disruptive ideas. They may also make mistakes and go for the wrong stuff occasionally because they try to be targeted. However, they are willing to take some scientific and technical risks, sometimes even big ones.

Because the Faculty programme is so new nothing can yet be said about outcome or impact of the programme.

BII convertible loans

BII offers so called founder-friendly convertible loans. The loans are connected to their two start-up support programmes Venture Lab and Creation House (for more details, see Domain 6) and are only offered to start-ups entering either of these programmes.

Basically, the loans are for free the first two years, and the company is not obliged to make any repayments during this period. After the two years, the company should ideally have matured and be able to raise some serious financing. Then the loan must be paid back. The companies should not live on the loan forever. For successful companies, where there are big investments coming in, the loan can be converted to equity, wholly or partly. Usually, the equity stake is quite small since BII is fully funded from Novo Nordisk Foundation and does not aim to be profitable. If the company cannot repay anything at all, the loan is converted to a grant and the company is liquidated. In those cases, there is no business anyway, which is part of the risk that BII is taking.

The philosophy behind the financial model that BII has developed is that funding successful start-ups is “a numbers game”; if you fund ten early-stage start-ups, one or maybe two will succeed in the long terms. Similarly, funding 100 start-ups can give twenty success stories. Therefore, BII does not give a lot of money to one company, but rather starts by giving relatively small amounts to many. That allows other follow-on investors to pick the ones that are showing signs of going in the right direction and provide them with continued funding.

Other funding agencies – private and public

Denmark has a well-functioning research and commercialisation funding system. One big reason is the Novo Nordisk Foundation. Their investments in life science research and innovation have helped to build a successful life science ecosystem. Together with other players such as the Innovation Foundation Denmark (the largest government founding body in this area), the Lundbeck Foundation and Novo Holdings, their Danish system now has critical mass, many funding opportunities and not only single or individual efforts/investments and many projects funded. This forms an ecosystem that allows university-based life science innovation to be commercialised effectively by European standards. Part of the investment returns made by Novo Holdings will go back to Novo Nordisk Foundation which funds BII. It is also quite easy to start a company in Denmark. With fixed capital DKK40.000 everyone can get started, and the paperwork is minimal. The entrepreneurial culture in Denmark could be considered very good and Denmark is generally regarded as one of the easiest countries in the world to run a business in.³¹

The Novo ecosystem consisting of Novo Nordisk A/S, Novozymes A/S, Novo Holdings A/S, Novo Nordisk Foundation and BII forms a very strong base for the life science commercialisation ecosystem in Denmark and beyond (as NNF, NH and BII also fund opportunities outside of Denmark). BII uses the other organisations in the Novo ecosystem for their own due diligence and to exchange scientific and business know-how. However, BII makes its funding decisions completely independent of the other organisations in the Novo ecosystem. BII-funded companies can also seek investments from any source and are not limited to Novo Holdings as an investor.

However, the Danish funding system has not always been like this. Initially, there were some early start-up funding, much like the small money of NOK50,000–100,000 that DLN can offer. If the projects were able to get IP, then more funding was available. Now the chain of funding opportunities is relatively complete and there are multiple incubator programmes and opportunities. However, BII wants to develop a one-stop-shop accelerator that can help start-ups all the way until they are mature enough to attract VC funding without having to exclusively rely on small grants from different sources. In addition to funding, BII provides all other necessary drivers of start-up success: mentoring by BII anchors, a network of advisors and investors and infrastructure to launch and scale start-ups (See Domain 6).

2.2.2 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

The ideal support system

BII has asked themselves, is it possible to build a support / tech transfer system that is able to reach the vast majority of all researchers to avoid great ideas being lost? Can every researcher with a good idea start a company? Their own answer to that is, “Why not?” And from that, they

³¹ [Ease of doing business index – Wikipedia](#)

have built a comprehensive support system, or an accelerator as they prefer to call it themselves, to make it possible.

To start with, the idea was to have a 6-months programme with DKK400,000 in funding. The money was not enough to do a Proof of Concept so the aim was instead to write a business plan. However, quite soon BII found that once the business plan was written, generally by an academic researcher who came straight out of university, it was shelved. Nothing further happened, so BII had to rethink their model.

In health tech the strategy is to add more time and money. Due to the long development times, ideas often need to 'jump' from accelerator to accelerator, trying to find new support and new funding for each phase in their development cycle. This is unfortunate and can often be confusing as they are being given different advice at different places, and the projects often 'get bored' over time. Based on that understanding, BII wants to build a complete accelerator where ideas can be brought in at one end and out of the other end; and then there would be a self-sustainable company. With more time and money and just the one accelerator, the start-ups could be building a business faster.

Therefore, BII has now designed two different programmes – Venture Lab and Creation House – which together has the capacity to support the whole chain from idea to company, with external funding. Both programmes offers both funding and expertise and are further described below.

BII evaluation and screening process

BII has a well-defined and developed evaluation process for the recruitment of projects/companies for the two start-up incubation and funding programmes, Venture Lab and Creation House. The evaluation is done through four steps based on materials submitted by the applicants (a pitch slide deck and a written proposal for the work to be performed with BII funding).

Step 1 – pre-screen. Applications are scored and ranking by BII business development staff. Scoring is done per field (therapeutics, health tech, bioindustrials). An internal team at BII selects the applications to take further for due diligence. Approximately three times more applications are taken to due diligence than are selected for funding at the end.

Step 2 – due diligence. Data relevant for an investor, such as the market size, IP-strategy, regulatory strategy, B2B attractiveness etc. is compiled by help of external experts, both individual Key Opinion Leaders and market/IP/regulatory advice providers, and presented to an advisory board who give comments. BII in general spend DKK 100.000 per project in due diligence through external consultancy fees and in-house work. BII selects approximately two times more projects to pitch based on due diligence than what will be eventually funded.

Step 3 – Programme advisory group (PAG) pitch. BII has three programme advisory groups (therapeutics, health tech, bioindustrials) consisting of international VC fund representatives (Sofinnova, Novo Seeds/Holdings, NEA, Abingworth, Amadeus Capital, Bioventures MedTech Fund, Rock Health, Wellington Partners, The March Fund and SR One) as well as selected technical experts (e.g. chemistry, software development). The applications are scored by the PAG members independently and the applicants pitch to the advisory group and BII BD staff and leadership followed by Q&A and discussion.

Step 4 – BII recommendation for funding. BII synthesises the input from its due diligence and PAG discussion to rank order applicants and recommend the ones that should be funded.

Step 4 – Final BII Board of Directors approval. BII Board of Directors approves all funding decisions at BII and typically will follow BII's recommendations, although BII BoD will also discuss the applications to be funded briefly.

As an example of the selection funnel in the first 2021 Venture Lab call there were more than 60 applications and out of these 16 were selected for due diligence and further 13 to pitch. Eventually up to seven applications will be funded from this call.

Venture Lab

The BII Venture Lab is an accelerator programme for the earliest stages of an innovation process. The purpose with Venture Lab is to help inventors with cutting edge transformative ideas and strong commercial aspirations, to develop their ideas into validated concepts. The goal is to accelerate the scientific maturity of the innovation to attract further funding, probably seed funding, and to develop a solid business plan and entrepreneurial skills for the team. The programme is meant to be a place for business case exploration, rapid testing of a product or market hypothesis, and completion of the critical experiment or product development step to allow fundraising. The next step, after finishing the Venture Lab, could be the Creation House programme or raising a seed investment from other investors.

Programme recruitment is done through biannual calls, aiming to fund 5–10 start-ups/projects per call. To be eligible for the programme the applicant must have established a Danish company either upon application or at least before entering the programme. The company must be built on an idea based on scientific evidence and it must be the founding team itself that applies. The team must have a clear understanding of its value proposition, its uniqueness and how it differentiates from potential competitors.

The projects/ideas must be somewhat mature before they can enter the programme, but it is not a requirement to have generated or filed IP. What they must have are specific thoughts about possible IP to be considered in the development plan, and some idea of a market to approach. An early business plan should be laid out. Thus, the idea can be at an early stage, but there must be some data or intelligence about the market potential.

The Venture Lab programme runs over 12 months. Each company gets a dedicated BII business anchor, who follow the progress, supports and guides the company through the programme and connect with external parties (Key Opinion Leaders, consultants, experts), in addition to a dedicated leadership coach who runs workshops on competence and recruitment, a scientific advisor with expertise in the key area which helps identify and generate critical experiments, and a CEO. The inventor and the team meet with the experts on a monthly basis. The company is also given a convertible loan of DKK4m (which can be repaid or converted into equity) and access to lab facilities.

The Venture Lab programme starts with a kick-off bootcamp with the purpose to get all the companies on the same page and to let them learn to know each other. The kick-off is then followed by monthly crunches, where the participants focus on a specific area to accelerate the growth of the company. The crunches contain teaching of the basics of business development for people without start-up experience, e.g. researchers from academia, and provides them with tools, case studies and an inspiring international network (people from other companies) for learning. The programme ends up in a Demo Day where each company pitches their companies in public to an audience including investors, corporate innovation experts and other people active in the start-up ecosystem. Through the programme the participants are given the opportunities to collaborate with the other programme participants, world-class coaches, experienced entrepreneurs, subject matter experts and the BII staff.

Creation House

The BII Creation House is a programme for start-ups with a strong commercial aspiration aiming to attract venture capital. The purpose of the programme is to fast-track the business to a stage where they have a lead candidate or prototype that can attract funding (e.g., series A capital) to support further development and/or growth.

The programme recruitment is done through biannual calls and funds 5–7 companies per call. To be eligible for the programme, the start-up must be a registered Danish company. Start-ups outside of Denmark can apply, but in order to receive funding (see Domain 2, convertible loan) they need to establish a Danish company that has full access to the company IP and at least one person employed in Denmark. There must be proof of concept for the idea and the value proposition should be validated. The team should also have a clear staffing plan including a candidate profile of an industry experienced chairperson for the board. Initially, a temporary board is set up consisting of the BII-anchor, the chair, the founder and the CEO. Academic researchers are seldom good CEOs and therefore BII can help finding someone for that role. They can hire a consultant or someone from the financial sector with commercial understanding. Bringing in a competent CEO preferably with prior fundraising experience is essential for raising money.

Companies do not have to go through the Venture Lab first but can apply directly to the Creation House programme if they are mature enough. The programme runs over 18 months. Each company gets a dedicated BII anchor who monitors company progress, supports the team, and helps to develop and evolve the milestone plans. The company gets a convertible loan of DKK10m (see Domain 2 for details) and access to BII office/lab facilities at a subsidised price.

The Creation House programme starts with a Venture Capital bootcamp where the participants learn how to approach VCs and what the VCs want to see and hear. The bootcamp is followed by monthly workshops where some of the topics from the bootcamp are addressed more in detail. Some workshops are left open to address specific needs of the companies that are discovered during the programme. The programme also contains VC Network pitches where the companies are given the opportunity to test their pitch and storytelling with real investors. BII works closely with the company all through the programme, but the aim is to make the company more and more independent from the BII anchor over time.

Pitching as an important tool

Pitching an idea to an investor is an art form, but it is not magic. BII has put much effort on pitching and for the companies it is both mandatory and voluntary, and rehearsed many times. If the pitching fails, it is difficult to attract private investors even if the team and idea are good. Researchers in particular have to be trained in how to sell their research to investors.

Described outcomes and results

Since BII and its programmes are still pretty new, it is difficult to say generally how successful the programmes are. So far two BII-funded companies have raised series A financing (€20m and €51m) with six companies have raised seed financing (over €1m). However, there are already lessons learned that BII are willing to share:

- Start-up team: Require direct fundraising experience on team either in the form of an experienced CEO or a Board Chair with fundraising experience. BII helps with recruitment of senior management to companies and uses external recruiters for this if needed

- Technology: Identify the 'killer experiment' needed to convince investors that the technology is working and execute effectively on this experiment. Engaging with investors early can be a useful way to discover what experiments are needed to make a convincing case
- Market: Develop a professional level understanding of differentiation between the product you are developing and what is under development by others or already on the market. BII recommends using external consultants for market research and strategic guidance
- Communication: Start-ups need to tell a convincing story to an investor audience. BII engages all start-ups in active pitch training as well as frequent pitching to its VC network

The role of BII vs the role of the TTO

In Denmark, as in most other countries, university/hospital researchers need to go through the TTOs whenever they have an idea they believe has commercial potential. But the role of the TTO is mainly to secure that IP is protected, with limited efforts to further commercialise innovation. Some universities have taken action to start innovation incubators in-house, but it is too expensive to build a solid support function in terms of both business development support and infrastructure. BII was therefore constructed to make something out of university/hospital-based innovations; to make it possible for any researcher to innovate and take good research to market.

BII does not rely on TTOs for finding promising start-ups or projects for its programmes. A majority of the start-ups have come to BII either through word of mouth or through active outreach to entrepreneurs by BII rather than by referral from TTOs. Nonetheless, projects that originate from a university/hospital setting must go through the TTO at some point because the university/hospital owns the IP associated with inventions made by its staff. Normally the TTOs are contacted early during the selection process to BII programs either by the entrepreneurs themselves or in some cases by BII. TTOs play a key role in making sure that inventions developed at universities and hospitals are protected by high quality intellectual property.

The goal is to create companies

BII only deals with start-up formation and does not focus on licensing of innovation to corporates. For the TTOs on the other hand, the licensing option is usually the more common way of commercialisation of innovation as they mainly deal with patents. According to BII, the TTOs are not usually thinking about intellectual property strategy from a start-up perspective, and it is up to the researcher to decide which way he or she wants to go and if a researcher shows a business model to the TTO that makes sense, they will agree to a different model.

IP and ownership

The companies participating in any of the two BII programmes have to license any required background IP from the university or company where it originates. Licensing is done on market terms and BII does not engage in negotiations or contracts about licensing. Licensing models and conditions depend significantly both on the university partner and the type/value of the invention.

Supporting international start-ups

Denmark has an active life science research environment, but in order to find the best science to commercialise BII needs to start looking for cases abroad as well. The BII programmes are therefore not only open for Danish ideas and companies. Foreigners can also apply if they have high quality science and good people to form the basis for an early-stage life science company. What is important for BII is to bring people together to form a critical mass where

ideas can be born and shared and different companies can also help each other in their journeys. It does not matter where these people are located; it can be in Finland or Germany or Sweden, because they contribute to the competence development in Denmark through their collaboration. The Nordic countries are each too small to compete on their own in the life science space where big hubs like Boston and San Francisco Bay Area dominate the start-up ecosystem. When going to the US with a business idea, they do anyway believe that the Nordics are one and the same. BII would like to expand the Danish ecosystem to a Nordic or even European level. The Baltics are also of great interest for BII; there are many good ideas, and labour is cheaper allowing for different commercialisation models. BII is also interested in opportunities in elsewhere in Europe including southern Europe, but geographical distances can become an issue with more remote opportunities.

To make it possible for international projects or companies to enter the BII programmes a model has been set up where they establish a Danish company that has the rights to the intellectual property that is needed for product development. In addition, BII requires that at least one senior person from the company is present at the BII most of the time during the incubation programme. BII is also investigating models for the future where there is no need to establish a company in Denmark, but for those models it will be necessary to have other ways than physical co-location to build a thriving and dynamic life science innovation community.

3 Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre (IBiolC)

3.1 Introduction

This case study is about the Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre (IBiolC) – an innovation centre within the Scottish Innovation Centre Programme (ICP), funded and supported by the Scottish Funding Council (SFC), Scottish Enterprise (SE) and Highlands and Islands Enterprise (HIE). The centre, which is hosted by the University of Strathclyde, works as a hub and supporting organisation for the wider industrial biotechnology (IB) sector (industry, academia as well as relevant stakeholders).

The case covers the following domains (topics) of relevance for DLN: domain 1) Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence; domain 2) Funding from research to venture capital; domain 3) Operating within innovation ecosystems; domain 4) Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use; domain 5) Innovation culture and practices in the universities; domain 6) University innovation support and commercialisation systems.

In short, IBiolC is an example of an R&I organisation that: promotes industry and academia collaborations, by funding research projects (domains 2 and 4); acts as a hub for IB issues within the wider RD&I context (domain 3), sustains skills development and provision (domains 4 and 5); promotes an innovation culture amongst researchers (domains 4, 5 and 6); provides research facilities and tools to support commercialisation and handle Intellectual property (IP) rights in collaborative projects (domain 6); introduces IB into new sectors and triggers collective actions in areas of relevance for the whole sector, such as digitalisation (domain 1).

3.2 Background

The networking and support organisation IBiolC connects industry, academia, and relevant parts of the state to bring biotechnology processes and products to the global market.

Areas of focus for IBiolC are sustainable feedstocks, biocatalysis/biotransformation, cell factory construction and process physiology, downstream processing, and integrated bioprocessing. The centre has a cross-sector focus and represents many parts of IB, such as bioenergy, marine, agriculture, construction, health, animal health. At the outset, however, the centre was most closely aligned to the chemical sector.³²

IBiolC's vision is to *establish an innovation and growth engine yielding substantial economic impact and delivering increased and sustainable wealth creation, prosperity, and employment in Scotland*.³³ To promote the vision, the centre provides expert support, creates an environment for networking, establishes academic and industrial collaboration, and mentor organisations in developing ideas from the first concept through to industry adoption.

The centre's key activities and initiatives are:

³² SFC, 2020, 'Innovation Centre programme', http://www.sfc.ac.uk/web/FILES/councilpapers_30012020/SFC20_06_Innovation_Centre_Programme.pdf [accessed 2021-03-18].

³³ EKOS Limited, 2016, 'Business Engagement and Economic Impact Evaluation of the Innovation Centres Programme', Final Report to the Scottish Funding Council 9th September 2016, http://www.sfc.ac.uk/web/FILES/InnovationCentres/Innovation_Centres_Programme_-_Final_Report_to_SFC_-_9_September_2016.pdf [accessed 2021-03-18].

- **Provision of funding.** IBiolC funds projects on Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) 3–7 (in some cases up to 8) to accelerate and de-risk the development of commercially viable, sustainable solutions for high value (speciality and commodity) manufacturing in chemistry-using and life science sectors. The centre is designed to fill a gap in research funding, and activities, between basic research (TRLs 1–3) and company R&D projects (TRLs 8–9)
- **Coordination of the network and support to members.** To bring value to its members, the centre's team facilitates networking activities; workshops, and conferences, provides membership care; technical networks and advice, R&I project support and help to navigate the R&I landscape. An important aspect of this is to gather people who work in the sector and act as the voice of IB. For this reason, the centre also provides outreach and public affairs activities
- **Skills provision and talent development programmes.** To ensure that the industry has the necessary skilled workforce to innovate in Scotland, IBiolC provides formal training programmes and courses at PhD, MSc and Higher National Diploma (HND) level
- **Scale-up facilities.** IBiolC grants its members priority access to two Scale-Up centres; the Rapid Bioprocess Prototyping Centre at the University of Strathclyde and the Flexible Downstream Bioprocessing Centre at Heriot-Watt University. Through IBiolC's on-site Scale-Up Team, members can also get access to expertise and technical support

IBiolC's operations underline Scotland's commitment to environmentally sustainable growth and development in the sense that it was set up to fulfil the aims of **the Scottish National Plan for Industrial Biotechnology** (the National Plan): *to grow the IB sector in Scotland to over £900 million in turnover, with over 200 companies operating in the sector by 2025*³⁴. For this reason, the centre is aligned with national targets for the IB sector and is required to make a real and measurable contribution to Scotland's IB growth ambitions. The targets include generation of more than £400m of IB sales Scotland-wide; creation of 1,500 new jobs in the sector; securing inward investment projects worth more than £140m; creation of more than 25 start-up businesses. IBiolC measures itself against the targets on an annual basis.

Initially, SFC invested £11.8m in the centre for the first period of operation (2014–2018), for the second period of operation (2018–2023) the centre received another £11.1m. In addition, the centre collects member fees from its members. Current membership levels are defined by size, those being Micro, SME and Large.

In terms of policy, IBiolC is one of seven Scottish innovation centres funded by the SFC and supported by SE and HIE within the Scottish ICP. The ICP was launched in 2012 to support transformational collaboration between Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and businesses. The programme aims to enhance innovation and entrepreneurship across Scotland's key economic sectors, create jobs and grow the Scottish economy. Aligned with the overarching aim, the programme's main objectives are:

- To offer **collaborative knowledge exchange and research** activities to help solve industry defined problems and co-create innovative opportunities for growth
- To **enhance two-way knowledge exchange** between universities, industry and others towards realising tangible benefits for businesses while also stimulating and challenging the Scottish research base

³⁴ Scottish Enterprise, 2019, National Plan for Industrial Biotechnology: Driving Progress to 2025, <https://www.lifesciencesscotland.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/National-Plan-for-IB-2019-PDF.pdf> [accessed 2021-03-18], Innovation Centres, 'IBiolC (Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre)', <https://www.innovationcentres.scot/innovation-centres/ibioc/> [accessed 2021-03-18].

- To **provide an environment that supports the development** of the next generation of business innovators, academics and entrepreneurs in Scotland and a culture change towards greater and more effective university/industry collaboration
- To **simplify the innovation landscape** in Scotland through creating conduits to the university knowledge and expertise for all businesses in Scotland and being complementary to and exploit existing initiatives such as Interface

The programme's initial phase ran between 2013–2018 and has been reviewed, on programme level as well as centre level, on several occasions. For instance, an Impact assessment, performed in 2016,³⁵ concluded that IBiolC was already demonstrating impacts in terms of products and processes delivered to market; jobs creation; and revenues to companies from new products or services.

By the end of phase one, the centre had facilitated 48 Industry-led projects in Scottish universities, established HND, MSc and PhD courses and levered the core grant into £100.8m in sector growth and 170 new jobs. To that, the centre's network included 114 industry members, 18 HEIs, and 4 Scottish Further Education Colleges (FECs).³⁶

For the second phase, IBiolC is continuing to develop its activities. Although, the centre's focus has slightly shifted towards commercialisation activities. Mirroring this shift, funded projects in phase two range from TRLs 3–8 instead of TRLs 3–5 (which was the case for phase one).

IBiolC's five key themes for the second phase are:

1. Providing strategic leadership
2. Accelerating commercialisation
3. Developing new value chains
4. Investing in value chains using biotechnology
5. Skilling the necessary workforce

Aligned with the key themes for phase two, IBiolC has established additional activities which include leveraging IB awareness to drive adoption and implementation; increasing access to facilities to de-risk scale-up and demonstration; making access to direct funding easier; expanding the community into new value chains; promoting the advancement of policies to support commercialisation of IB.

Currently, the centre has 127 member organisations. A majority of the organisations are businesses, ranging from medical biotechnology companies working on protein production to companies developing green solutions in biomanufacturing, that utilise agriculture, marine and forestry derived feedstocks in sustainable manufacturing processes. Around 80 per cent of the members are SMEs or micro-companies. In addition to that, the centre has 18 HEIs, and 4 FECs as part of the member network. It also has a strategic relationship with the N8 Universities which are the eight most research intensive HEI's across the North of England.

IBiolC's team has 24 members (including the Scale-Up Team which sits with the Scale-up facilities) dedicated to assisting members with projects and applications; helping them to innovate; guiding them to other funding bodies; coordinating collaborations and networks; attracting new members; and engaging with the wider public (through a public affairs person).

³⁵ SFC, 2020, 'Innovation Centre programme',

³⁶ IBiolC, 2018, Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre: Phase II Summary, <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5f7e28835ee59e18a639d16c/t/5fa56df89c6d8029944288e9/1604677122612/IBiolC+Phase+II+Brochure.pdf> [accessed 2021-03-18].

IBiolC's Governing Board with 15 members, from academia and industry, sets the strategic direction of the centre, reports appropriately to the funders, and ensures that all activities contribute to the overall vision. The Governing Board is also responsible for the compliance, financial oversight, and risk management.

Below the Governing Board, IBiolC has a Commercial Advisory Board (CAB) and a Scientific Advisory Board (SAB). The CAB consists of 17 members, both industry representatives as well as academics experienced in working with businesses. The board meets quarterly to provide guidance to the centre and strategise with IBiolC's team. This, to ensure that the centre maximises the commercial impact and fosters its industrial reputation. The SAB consisting of 20 members, from academia and business, oversees the scientific content of the centre's funding calls and provides technical guidance to ensure that the centre advances in its five key thematic areas. Both the SAB and the CAB are involved in the centre's application assessment process (see section 3.3.2).

The centre is a legal entity within the University of Strathclyde; though, it is run as if it was a private company and is from the outside perceived as a free-standing entity. Investments from the funders pass through the university, the centre is subject to the university's policies and the IBiolC staff are all employed by the university, while initiatives and activities are launched and governed by the centre. This way of organising is beneficial in terms of, for instance, graduating students, but it is not when it comes to communicating to external parties that the centre provides other functions and services than a regular university department or institute.

3.3 Domains of relevance for this case

3.3.1 Domain 1 – Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence

Interdisciplinarity is embedded in the field of IB, the centre has, over the years, therefore taken a cross-sectoral approach to IB. IBiolC has several activities to support and encourage members to engage in cross-sectoral research. For instance, matchmaking, outreach and network building activities (see sections 3.3.2 and 3.3.4); technical networks (see section 3.3.6), and collaboration project funding (see section 3.3.2).

The centre also tries to work as a trigger for cross-sectoral collaborations and to enhance activities in certain areas with low activity through 'strategic projects'³⁷. Such projects fit the centre's strategic agenda and are initiated by IBiolC if there is a need for a coordinated action that will benefit a majority of the stakeholders. The projects are ultimately linked to how the centre contributes to the goals of the National Plan.

IBiolC has, for example, initiated a strategic project to try to grow the bioeconomy sector, penetrate other sectors, and advance engagement with biotechnology solutions:

- **The Bioeconomy Cluster Builder project³⁸** – a joint project between IBiolC, the Knowledge Transfer Network (KTN), and SE to introduce biotechnology solutions to new markets that will in turn grow the bioeconomy sector in Scotland. The Bioeconomy Cluster Builder project has been designed to help companies outside of the current bioeconomy community to understand and engage with biotechnology applications and things like bio-based products that will improve sustainability credentials whilst also increasing efficiency and improved product performance.

³⁷ IBiolC, 'Strategic Projects', <https://www.ibioic.com/network-news/#strategic-projects> [accessed 2021-03-18].

³⁸ IBiolC, 'Growing the Bioeconomy: the Bioeconomy Cluster Builder project', <https://www.ibioic.com/innovation-support/#growing-the-bioeconomy-the-bioeconomy-cluster-builder-project> [accessed 2021-03-18].

Moreover, digitalisation, changing working methods, data science and AI are all important areas for the IB sector, and have potential within both manufacturing and research. However, a broad transition has not yet commenced within the IB sector, since many companies do not have the competencies or know-how to start digitalising or use data science. For these reasons, IBiolC is part of a couple of strategic projects with an IT/digitalisation focus:

- **ICT-Biochain** – a project with a consortium of eight partners from across Europe working to increase the efficiency of biomass supply chains using ICT. The main objectives of the project are to establish multi-actor digital innovation hubs for biomass supply chains; improve the efficiency of biomass supply chains within the Model Demonstrator Regions by producing a feedstock-specific database of best practices, and new opportunities for digitisation; establish a user-friendly online platform to allow for wider exploitation of ICT, the Internet of Things and Industry 4.0 tools for improving supply chain efficiency.
- **The European Marine Biological Resource Centre Biobank** – a pan-European research project. The project's main goals are to facilitate sustainable access to marine biodiversity, its associated data and extractable products for local and international academia and industry users, and to incentivise biodiversity conservation in coastal ecosystems by promoting compliance with Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) regulations derived from the Nagoya Protocol. Within this project, E-tools will be developed to harmonise database structure and client-server architecture throughout all involved biobanks, improving overall operational standards.

There are no clear targets on digitalisation in the current National Plan. However, since digital practices are important and there is a need for them within the sector, the next version of the National Plan³⁹, will almost certainly set up digitalisation targets for the forthcoming years.

3.3.2 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital

As previously mentioned, IBiolC funds projects from TRL 3 to 7, or 8, and uses project calls to support collaborations between the industry and academia as well as to help researchers translate university research into commercial success. IBiolC only funds collaboration projects between industry and academia, and such projects are expected to address a defined market need/commercial opportunity through the innovative application of biotechnology. Projects should also be aligned with the National Plan.

Funding available includes:

To enter one of IBiolC's own funding calls (Innovation Funding call, Feasibility Funding, Scale-Up Accelerator call), all applicants must meet the following criteria:

- The project must demonstrate a clear market need or commercial opportunity through the innovative use or application of biotechnology
- The project must demonstrate an economic, societal and/or reputational benefit to Scotland
- Companies must become members of IBiolC prior to the project's start date and remain members for the entire duration of the project

Projects are selected based on their technical and commercial merits – through a clear and transparent assessment process – by the SAB and CAB respectively. For IBiolC, it is important to

³⁹ An updated version of the National Plan is expected during 2022.

have a clear and transparent assessment process and scoring system to be able to build trust with both current and potential members.

The criteria by which IBioIC funded projects are assessed are set up in Table 1.

Table 1 IBioIC's project assessment criteria.

Technical Merits	Commercial Merits
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Technical Ambition and Viability. Projects should have a degree of ambition as well as being feasible.2. Technical Approach. The scientific approach must be appropriate, risks must be identified and mitigated, and project partners must be appropriate for the proposed work. (25 p)3. Non-commercial scientific benefit to the project. Projects should show an additional benefit such as reputational and should deliver impact to IB within Scotland. (25 p)4. How innovative is the project? Projects should prove that there is a strong possibility of patentable intellectual property ("IP") being generated. (25 p)5. Project Timelines and Resources. Projects should be industry-led, but with good collaboration with academia and knowledge exchange. Timelines must be realistic with appropriate milestones and deliverables. (25 p)	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Breadth of applicability. Projects should address an identifiable commercial or scientific barrier with a view to marketing a solution (15 p)2. Path to Market. Projects should consider the path from current TRL to commercialization (15 p)3. Benefit versus cost. Applications should demonstrate a commercial benefit on top of the cost of the project (15 p)4. Time to market and market appraisal. Application should make an appraisal of the potential market share, competition and timeline to market (15 p)5. Economic impact on project partners. Applicants should demonstrate that the project could generate additional growth through market, employment or IP opportunities (10 p)6. Governance, Management Processes and Risk appraisal. Applications should demonstrate an industry-led approach and consideration of potential risks (15 p)7. Funding profile. The financial information provided should be adequate and realistic for the proposed project (5 p)8. Track record of success. Applicants should highlight project-specific expertise and previous successes (10 p)

Source: IBioIC, documentation for calls for Innovation Funding and Feasibility Funding.

To date, IBioIC has funded 60 projects between business and academia. An important aspect is that the provision of money/resources drive collaboration because the lack of funding, access to research facilities or partners are usually barriers for academics and SMEs to participate in R&I projects. Therefore, to join the pieces of the R&I ecosystem together, the centre provides project funding (including funding of studentships, see section 3.3.5), research facilities (see section 3.3.6) as well as matchmaking to its members.

Innovation Funding Call⁴⁰

Under this call, IBioIC funds industry-led R&I projects which enables industry members to partner up with at least one Scottish HEI. Projects are expected to address and solve defined commercial problems through the innovative application of biotechnology. To support costs incurred by academic partners, projects can be awarded up to £100,000 – although it needs to be matched by cash/ in-kind contributions from industry. Applicants must also meet the criteria stated above to be considered for funding under this call.

⁴⁰ IBioIC, 2020a, 'Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre: Call for Projects Innovation Fund 2021'.

Feasibility Funding Call⁴¹

IBiolC funds feasibility projects which provide industry members with the opportunity to tap into the expertise of Scotland's research base to assist with biotech-focused PoC studies to support a future funding application for a larger scale research work programme. Projects are expected to be small and short term (less than one year) and should focus on innovative applications to IB. Up to £20k is available to support costs incurred by academic partners. Large companies must match the project funding with an equal amount in cash, to be paid to the academic partners, or by in-kind contributions. SMEs must match the project funding with an equal amount of in-kind contributions. The IBiolC project support team may assist potential applicants with idea development and identifying a suitable academic partner.

Besides the criteria mentioned above, project applications must have the potential to lead onto larger scale work, for example, onto a SMART award, Innovate UK's Knowledge Transfer Partnerships, Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council's (BBSRC) Industrial Partnership Awards, or LINK.

Scale-Up Accelerator Project Call for SMEs⁴²

IBiolC supports projects to evolve from basic research to scale-up via this open call for projects. It allows SMEs to develop, optimise and scale-up their bioprocesses in partnership with the centre's Scale-Up Team, utilising specialist equipment within the centre's Bioprocessing Scale-Up Centres at Heriot-Watt University and the University of Strathclyde (see section 3.3.6).

To enter, SMEs should complete the Scale-Up Accelerator Expression of Interest (EoI) and submit it to the Scale-Up Team. Submitted applications undergo assessments for funding eligibility, and projects will be selected on their technical and commercial merits, as mentioned above. Successful applicants are informed within two weeks of EoI submission and will subsequently be invited to develop their work programme with a member of the IBiolC's Scale-Up Team. The Scale-Up Team can also help applicants to identify collaborators and support the bid writing process for external funding. Besides the criteria highlighted in Table 1 IBiolC's project assessment criteria., to be considered for funding under this call the project must be led by an SME.

Algae-UK/ IBiolC joint PoC Funding Call⁴³

Algae-UK and IBiolC are offering funds to support several small, PoC and 'scouting' project, between academic and industrial based partners with the view that they will deliver significant future outcomes. They fund projects up to £50k, with duration no longer than 12 months. Firstly, Algae-UK reviews and assesses all applications based on their technical benefits. Subsequently, IBiolC conducts a commercial review of successful applications.

The aim of the call is to provide support for projects that help to address the technical challenges in delivering IB applications of algae in food and novel food ingredients.

Projects eligible for support must be relevant to the IB sector; be clearly aligned to assist with the ongoing technical challenges; and have clear plans to engage or collaborate further with other partners relevant to the value chain that the project will impact.

⁴¹ IBiolC, 2020b, Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre: IBiolC Feasibility Programme March 2021 Call for Projects'.

⁴² IBiolC, 2020c, 'Scale-Up Accelerator 2020 Call for Projects'.

⁴³ Algae-UK, 2020, 'Algae-UK PoC Call with IBiolC: industrial biotechnology applications of algae in food and novel food ingredients'.

Spin-out funding

To support academics even further, through the provision of **spin-out funding**, IBioIC has teamed up with Scottish Edge – a funding competition aimed at identifying and supporting Scotland's innovative, high growth potential entrepreneurial talent. Researchers may be awarded loans for business projects aimed at setting up spinouts. The centre puts £100,000 into the EDGE pot, for an IBioIC EDGE award.

In addition, IBioIC mentors researchers or early-stage entrepreneurs, providing day-to-day strategic advice on how to find funding, write applications and similar activities.⁴⁴

3.3.3 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

IBioIC illustrates how Scotland uses the triple helix model of innovation to coordinate and optimise the innovation ecosystem for IB through the ICP. The Scottish R&I ecosystem for IB is rather complex and difficult to navigate, with organisations active across different sectors and policy issues not aligned under a single stakeholder group or authority. Funding bodies for innovation are, for instance, both decentralised to Scotland as well as present at the national level.

Scotland's life science research sector is considered to be one of the strongest in the world and there were interactions between universities and the industry before the centre was established. However, such interactions were based on institutional relationships or personal relationships and not evenly spread throughout the research sector. As a result of this, some universities benefitted more from investments and project funding than others, and smaller companies had difficulties penetrating the universities to find the right expertise, i.e., to collaborate with universities. There was a need for a forum for the industry and academia to come together to collaborate, and to deal with common issues, as such, the Scottish Government launched IBioIC to coordinate the interactions and to spread out R&I activities more evenly across the country.

The National Plan underlines the centre's position as an important focal point in the innovation ecosystem. The centre is, therefore, well-positioned to act as a single portal between industry and the emerging science behind IB, since it acts as a hub for all activity surrounding IB by providing a forum, or network, for organisations to come together from different sectors to support net-zero targets; decreased environmental impact, sustainability; or circular economy, by using IB.

Besides facilitating closer relationships amongst its members, in several ways (see sections 3.3.2, 3.3.4 and 3.3.6), the IBioIC team links members with other funding bodies and support organisation in the innovation ecosystem, to ensure that projects and collaboration activities beyond the centre's scope takes place. Such organisations include SE, BBSRC, Innovate UK and the Royal Society of Edinburgh.

Also, to ensure that the ecosystem is fit for purpose, IBioIC has established essential research facilities at the request of its stakeholders (see section 3.3.6) and is regularly identifying areas in need of coordinated action through strategic projects, such as the Bioeconomy Cluster Builder project or the ICT-Biochain project (see section 3.3.1).

Occasionally, the centre influences decisions and advises agencies or the Government. This is ultimately to support the members by ensuring that decisions concerning the sector are

⁴⁴ Scottish Edge, 2020, 'Scottish EDGE increases Biotechnology winner support with £77.5K injection from IBioIC', <https://www.scottishedge.com/news-database/edge16-ibioic> [accessed 2021-03-18].

evidence-based. To generate evidence-based policy advice on various matters, IBiolC typically uses its members and the projects they pursue. In order to spread the knowledge and ensure that relevant information reaches stakeholders as well as the public, the centre has communication activities and a dedicated public affairs person who deals with public engagement.

IBiolC has, furthermore, established a good relationship with its funders based on what the centre has managed to deliver over the years, and the fact that it takes a national responsibility regarding what it delivers. A recent example of this is that during the Covid -19 pandemic, the centre pivoted some of its activities to help Scotland's diagnostic testing capacity. The centre looked at the country's supply chain as well as the training and recruitment of people to run the diagnostics tests. In total, IBiolC funded three Covid -19 related projects and has in addition been added as a partner to one of three training centres for the manufacture of cell and gene therapies.

3.3.4 Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use

The innovation centre is established to work as a natural link between academia and industry parties, as mentioned before. Actors from both categories are represented in the centre's governing bodies, networks as well as in the R&I project (see sections 3.2, 3.3.2 and 3.3.3).

The centre was also instrumental in terms of making the practice of academia and industry collaboration more general. It has, for instance, had projects with all 18 universities across Scotland and has a large proportion of SMEs present in the member network. (see sections 3.2 and 3.3.3).

IBiolC's key to establishing, as well as sustaining, the position as a natural link between the sectors has been the value it brings to its members. Value such as several funding opportunities, innovation support initiatives and networking opportunities. The business engagement team, which sits with the centre, is also an essential function in this regard. The team, consisting of senior managers, are responsible for membership care and communication with members, to keep them content and to support them with what they need (from marketing to technical advice). Outward-facing communication is also an important aspect of this and showcasing examples of R&I collaboration projects that have worked well helps IBiolC to entice companies and academics to engage in collaborations with one another.

Another significant aspect is the centre's CAB and SAB, with members from both sectors. Since they advise IBiolC on strategic matters, assess project applications from a scientific/technical perspective and a commercial perspective, and helps the project in the earliest project stages (see section 3.3.2).

Ultimately, the centre builds confidence and a good reputation through the way it handles its members and the fact that the centre is a high performing organisation. The centre's high profile around Scotland helps both in terms of attracting new members as well as keeping current members engaged.

There are also institutional relationships established between the centre and a couple of universities/colleges as part of the centre's task to support the sustainable growth of the bioeconomy through Industry-led skills development. In this manner, the centre forges producer-user links in knowledge production and use at an early stage in the researchers' careers (see section 3.3.5).

To that, IBioC runs a number of technical expertise and advice networks⁴⁵ on various topics with industry expertise from a range of industries from food and pharma to materials. The networks are set up to share technology within the IBioC network, and members are encouraged to communicate with each other. The networks are organised so that members from one segment regularly come together to discuss specific topics, and from time to time they also invite members or technical experts from networks with other topics to join. The topics have come and gone; currently, fermentation is a vibrant topic. At the last network meeting, on fermentation, around 45 professionals, both from business and academia, attended. This way of organising has been successful for IBioC since it has contributed to cross-fertilisation in the different technology areas the centre support.

3.3.5 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations

IBioC has several measures dedicated to foster an 'innovation mindset' within academia.

As previously mentioned, good examples of successful collaboration projects help to entice researchers to engage with the centre, so by showcasing these the centre helps to incline researchers to participate in innovation activities. Once researchers are involved in the centre's activities, they are, in addition, provided with support and tools to carry out R&I projects (see sections 3.3.2, 3.3.4, 3.3.6).

Another part of this is the skills provision programmes IBioC offers as part of its mission to inspire the future generation to work in IB – in alignment with the National STEM Strategy⁴⁶ (and the National Plan).

- In collaboration with IBioC, Glasgow Clyde College and Forth Valley College are set to deliver the Higher National Diploma (HND) in IB.⁴⁷ The HND in IB is intended for those wishing to find employment in the IB industry or to progress to further (degree level) study. It is a wide-ranging course that develops relevant knowledge and skills in the theoretical and practical aspects of IB, and learners will be exposed to each of the main branches of IB: chemistry, biology and process engineering. As well as classroom and lab-based learning, students will have the opportunity to visit key biotechnology industries in the local region. Career opportunities are Science Laboratory Technician; Research Scientist; Process Operator and Production Scientist.
- The centre provides **Industrial Masters**⁴⁸ by the University of Strathclyde, where teaching takes place at Strathclyde's campus in Glasgow as well as at Abertay University; Glasgow Caledonian University; Heriot-Watt University; Innogen Institute; Scottish Association for Marine Science; University of Edinburgh; University of Glasgow; University of the Highlands and Islands.

The course has been designed in direct response to industry needs and is at the forefront of developments in biotechnology and engineering. The course content is informed by industry and reviewed annually to ensure it is up-to-date and optimally aligned to the rapidly growing IB sector. As part of the course, the students undertake a 10-week placement where they participate in industry-led research projects. To provide students

⁴⁵ IBioC, 'Technical Expertise and Advice' <https://www.ibioic.com/innovation-support/#technical-expertise-and-advice> [accessed 2021-03-18].

⁴⁶ Scottish Government, 2020, 'STEM – Strategy for Education and Training in Scotland Second Annual Report'.

⁴⁷ IBioC, 'Skills: HND', <https://www.ibioic.com/skills/#hnd> [accessed 2021-03-18].

⁴⁸ IBioC, 'Skills', <https://www.ibioic.com/skills> [accessed 2021-03-18].

with the skills required to work in the biotechnology industry is the programme's end-goal. Most of the students continue to work in the industry after the dissertation.

- Industrial PhD programme including a BBSRC-funded **Collaborative Training Partnership (CTP)**.⁴⁹ IBioIC has a portfolio of 105 PhD projects across all member universities that are funded by industry and managed by the centre. Through this programme, IBioIC provides PhD students with wider industry competencies. The end goal is to make students 'Industry Ready' and to support the sustainable growth of the bioeconomy through Industry-led skills development.

The training programme is a combination of compulsory and optional structured training, complemented by ongoing personal development initiatives. To complement the taught training programme, every IBioIC PhD student undertakes a 3–12-month placement in the industry. In order to ensure that students have the diverse range of skills required for a successful career in IB, the training programme focuses on three key elements i) essential project skills, ii) essential industry skills, and iii) personal growth, outlined in Table 2

Outline of skills provided by the CTP.

Table 2 Outline of skills provided by the CTP.

<i>Essential projects skills</i>	<i>Essential industry skills</i>	<i>Skills for personal growth</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific training for the individual project delivered by the host university • Where project skills gaps are identified, IBioIC will utilise its networks to identify a suitable provider or, if sufficient demand, develop a bespoke course 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical skills. Training focuses on practical technical skills required by industry but not traditionally taught in academia. Previous training includes good manufacturing practice, and design of experiments • Commercial skills. This training is tailored specifically to the IB industry and focuses on commercial skills such as patent interrogation and process costing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking activities – IBioIC facilitate interaction between future employers, our members, and the students throughout the training programme • 'Skills for the future', timeless, higher-order skills that create adaptive learners and promote success in whatever context the future brings • International exchanges – the IBioIC team actively seek out exchange opportunities for the PhD students • Expert training in public engagement

Source: IBioIC's CTP website.

3.3.6 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

Besides the funding opportunities and support (see section 3.3.2) the centre provides, IBioIC has established two Scale-up centres in order to improve university innovation support and commercialisation systems.

Within the Scale-up centres, IBioIC offer members priority access to a wide range of fermentation technologies and services from small scale culture to pilot-scale production, process optimisation, downstream processing, and data analysis. Project costs are partly covered by the centre. Members may also gain access to expertise and technical support from IBioIC's on-site team – consisting of six Scale-Up Team members to help progress their R&I projects from basic research to scale-up. The centre's team helps to identify collaborators and support the bid writing process for external funding to realise members scale-up ambitions. To

⁴⁹ IBioIC, 'Collaborative Training Partnership', <https://www.ibioicctp.com/> [accessed 2021-03-18].

that, the centres are part of BioPilotsUK – a collaboration of four open-access centres to develop and strengthen UK-based value-chains – which IBIoIC's members can benefit from in terms of R&D facilities, technical assistance, and collaboration opportunities.⁵⁰

The Scale-up Centres were established on behalf of IBIoIC's industry members, since they asked for more support in terms of low-cost scale-up facilities to utilise before they could afford to go forward with the project to a commercial party.

Further, to convince companies to collaborate and not compete, IBIoIC has established a clear confidentiality policy. Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) must be signed by members when joining the member network. Concerning collaboration projects, parties must always agree on the terms and conditions of the contract, including IP, before commencing. At times, IBIoIC also helps with legal support through the University of Strathclyde's legal services. IBIoIC never takes on projects that are competing with other projects within the centre.

IBIoIC has, furthermore learned that in order to deal with companies that have similar or competing technologies it is important that the centre takes on the role as an agnostic third party to support them with their R&I projects. As a result of this, smaller companies have the confidence to send in some of their scientists to work alongside other scientists as part of the knowledge transfer process.

3.4 Conclusions

IBIoIC's overall success factors

- The National Plan for IB guides IBIoIC's actions and sets up targets for the centre to measure itself against annually
- The centre's Governing Board has the CAB and the SAB to assist on strategic matters as well as R&I project assessments
- IBIoIC has, over the years, taken a cross-sectoral approach to IB, which has led to more opportunities for cross-fertilisation and the development of the Scottish IB sector
- The overall responsiveness of the centre to both the member's needs as well as the IB sector has contributed to the centre's position as a hub for IB issues within the R&I ecosystem for IB

Lessons and conclusions per domain

Domain 1

- IBIoIC uses strategic projects to trigger cross-sectoral collaborations and to address certain areas in need additional efforts coordinated by the centre
 - To try to grow the bioeconomy sector, IBIoIC has initiated the Bioeconomy Cluster Builder project
 - To trigger digitalisation, IBIoIC is part of two strategic projects, the ICT-Biochain project and the European Marine Biological Resource Centre Biobank project

Domain 2

- The composition of IBIoIC's funding instruments is set up to provide its members funding in different project stages, from the first concept through to industry adoption – Feasibility funding; Innovation Funding; Scale-up Accelerator funding

⁵⁰ IBIoIC, 'Bioprocessing Scale-Up Centres' <https://www.ibioic-scaleup.com/> [accessed 2021-03-18].

- To ensure that the funding portfolio is fit for purpose, IBiolC has also teamed up with other funding bodies such as Algae-UK and the Scottish EDGE, so that researchers and early-stage entrepreneurs are supported properly throughout their innovation journey
- Projects are selected based on their technical and commercial merits by the SAB and CAB respectively to ensure the projects' scientific as well as business potential
- The centre's project assessment process and scoring system are clear and transparent. On this behalf, IBiolC has managed to build trust with both current and potential members
- To enhance the project's success rate, the IBiolC team supports project applicants as well as project leaders with various project-related tasks such as finding partners or additional funding, bid writing, work programme writing and technical assistance
- An important take away according to IBiolC is that the provision of funding or other resources drive collaboration and joins the pieces of the R&I ecosystem together. It does so by lowering barriers for participation, and thereby increasing incentives to collaborate

Domain 3

- The Scottish R&I ecosystem for IB is complex and difficult to navigate within, with organisations active across different sectors and policy issues not aligned under a single stakeholder group or authority. Funding bodies for innovation are both decentralised to Scotland as well as present at the national level. IBiolC is, nevertheless, an interesting example of how the Scottish government uses the triple helix model of innovation to coordinate and optimise the innovation ecosystem for IB through the ICP
- To make the ecosystem for IB more fit for purpose, IBiolC has established two Scale-up centres to improve university innovation support and commercialisation systems, at the request of its stakeholders. To that, the centre uses its members to generate and provide evidence-based policy advice and information, on various matters, to the government and the wider public. Actions like these are essentially the reason for IBiolC's maintained position as a hub for IB issues
- IBiolC has built a trusting relationship with its funders based on the national responsibility it assumes as well as what it has managed to deliver over the years

Domain 4

- IBiolC's key to establishing, and sustaining, the position as a natural link between the industry and academia has been the value it brings to its members through activities, networking opportunities, and support provided by the IBiolC's team of senior managers. The centre builds trust and a good reputation through the way it handles its members. The high profile IBiolC has around Scotland helps to attract new members and keep current members
- To forge producer-user links in knowledge production and use at an early stage in the researchers' careers, the centre has established institutional relationships with a couple of universities/colleges. This is part of the centre's task to support the sustainable growth of the bioeconomy through Industry-led skills development programmes
- To encourage members to share technology, IBiolC runs several technical expertise and advice networks on various topics (from food and pharma to materials). It is a way for the centre to organise cross-sectoral activities and stimulate cross-fertilisation

Domain 5

- IBiolC has learned that good examples of successful collaboration projects help to entice researchers to engage in future collaborations. So by showcasing good examples, the centre helps to incline researchers to participate in its innovation activities. To that, once researchers are involved in activities, they are provided tools and support to innovate

- To promote an 'innovation mindset' amongst academics, the centre also offers skills provision programmes as part of its mission to inspire the future generation to work in IB
 - The HND in IB, the Industrial masters, the Industrial PhD programmes, including the BBSRC-funded CTP, all provides students with industry competencies, tools and abilities to collaborate or work within the IB sector

Domain 6

- To convince companies to collaborate and not compete, IBIoIC has established a clear confidentiality policy. An NDA must be signed by members when joining the network; parties must always agree on the terms and conditions of the contract, including IP, before starting collaboration projects; IBIoIC never takes on projects that are competing with other projects within the centre
- IBIoIC has learned that to support companies that have similar or competing technologies it is important that the centre takes on the role as an agnostic third party. This approach has been successful in the sense that smaller companies now have the confidence to send out their scientists to work alongside other scientists as part of the knowledge transfer process

4 The Institute of Marine Research (Havforskningsinstituttet)

Norway is the country with the highest number of researchers within the marine sector per capita in the world. The only countries spending more money in absolute terms on marine research than Norway are USA, Australia and Japan. Therefore, when looking for relevant cases to study within the marine sector, the Norwegian research institutes are well positioned.

The Institute of Marine Research (IMR) is one of the biggest marine research institutes in Europe, with about 1,000 employees with scientific expertise in areas ranging from oceanography to ecology and human nutrition. Their main activities are research, scientific advice, and monitoring. Through their research and advisory functions, the IMR seeks to help society to continue exploiting the valuable assets in the sea in a sustainable way. The institute is an unbiased knowledge provider, and their scientific research is made available through publications both in Norway and internationally.

The main tasks of IMR are:

- To give research-based advice to the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries, the Directorate of Fisheries, Norwegian Food Safety Authority and other relevant authorities in questions concerning governance and exploitation of marine biological resources.
- To make data and research available for the public administration, other research institutions, the marine sector and society.
- To deliver relevant research that contributes to knowledge-based development of the marine sector.

In January 2018, the IMR was merged with NIFES, the National Institute of Nutrition and Seafood Research, to become a leading supplier of knowledge for sustainable management of the resources in our marine ecosystems. Following that merger, IMR now covers the whole value chain for marine food production, from the sea to the table.

The IMR is affiliated to the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries which also provides around half of their funding, amounting to NOK1,059m in 2019. NOK564m came from the Research Council of Norway, the EU and other bodies that fund research. A minimal part of the yearly revenues come from industry and private companies. The total revenues of the institute were NOK1,627m in 2019.

Today the IMR has a total of 1,076 employees: 673 at their head office in Bergen, 76 in Tromsø, 43 at the Flødevigen research station, 44 at the Austevoll research station, and 40 at the Matre research station. In addition, the Research Vessel Department has ownership responsibility for the 7 research vessels, which are its most important tools for collecting marine data, and employs 200 sailors. 36 fishing vessels in the reference fleet also provide fishing data on a regular basis. The IMR also has several laboratories that analyse the samples taken by its monitoring and research programmes (Domain 6).

The IMR is a relevant case with respect to the bio-marine sector and domain 1, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7.

4.1.1 Domain 1 – Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence

IMR research and research groups

The Institute of Marine Research studies everything from seafood production chains to the most subtle details of marine ecosystems. They also invest a lot of resources in aquaculture research and developing new technology.

The IMR has 22 thematic research groups consisting of both scientists and technical staff, usually working from several of the different geographical locations of the institute. The kind of expertise and personnel that is employed within each research group depends on the group's main tasks. The research and surveillance activities are organised in projects and carried out in the research groups. Research groups of relevance for DLN are Animal welfare, Seafood hazards, The Norwegian Marine Data Centre, Population genetics, Reproduction and developmental biology, Seafood and nutrition, and Pathogen and disease transfer.

The role data in IMR

The role of IMR as an advisor to relevant authorities and sectors is guiding and governing the research activity within the institute; the advice they give has to be knowledge-based and build on frontier research. For most of the research and advisory activities they do, data is key, and the data collection spans everything from mapping and monitoring to experimental studies and modelling. Data is obtained via research cruises, measurement installations and land-based experimental facilities. Bioinformatics is a major focus area at IMR and a lot of the collected data is used for that purpose. IMR believes that there are big opportunities in genomics data that could be linked to university research. The bioinformaticians also tend to be good at AI and machine learning, saving resources in some of the more manual processes at the institute. Another area of interest within IMR, which is also highly data driven, is the use of cameras and sonar, and interpreting the images for a wide range of possible applications. Historically, IMR has been using trawls a lot, basing their data on fish catches and counting them, but now, with use of technology and data driven methods, the organization can work in a completely different way. IMR has tried to use machine learning on these data and seen that it is quite easy to gain good results. That has been very stimulating and raised interest in the organization to test AI and machine learning methods in even more disciplines. Image recognition and data analysis can revolutionize operations within IMR; instead of trawling for specimens, new image recognition technologies facilitate remote sample registration and identification. A concrete example of such a data driven digital innovation has been developed through one of their SFIs (see Domain 4).

IMR believes there are opportunities to use the data it can collect much more extensively for developing and monitoring regulation and policy. The institute is developing a plan to expand its activities in these areas.

Yet another area where IMR see a huge use for the data they collect is for policy development. There is a big monitoring plan with IMR to generate the kind of data needed for that purpose.

E-infrastructure

The mission and role of IMR does not only require a comprehensive and world-leading research infrastructure in the form of research vessels, research stations and laboratories (see Domain 6). Just as important is the access to advanced IT, or E-infrastructure, and efficient data pathways to fulfil their mission related to data collection, data management and dissemination. It is crucial to IMR to have systems for storage, use and sharing of all their research data, and the storage need has multiplied because of the use of new research methods based on digital solutions and new sensors. Therefor there is a constant focus on good and secure storage solutions and efficient methods for data transfer from sampling to storage. To be proactive, the institute has chosen to invest in the national high performance computing resource Sigma. IMR procured additional storage capacity in 2019 to cover additional storage needs over the next 4 years until a national solution is in place.

Convergence with other scientific disciplines

IMR has a policy of being strongly focused on natural sciences. However, because of their role as an advisor, not only for the public authorities but also for the marine industry sector, economic studies are of great importance as well. So far, IMR has left that for others to take care of but the trend is the opposite; more and more organizations are integrating social sciences with their fields of research. NOAA in the USA is one example of an organization that has chosen to have social sciences research in house. IMR has chosen to collaborate with others rather than building in house competence in economics.

The merger with NIFES meant that the research focus of IMR was broadened to include also the more downstream parts of the value chain for marine food production, from the sea to the table. The merger has led to some disciplinary integration between IMR's classical interests and seafood and related issues. But there is no deliberate strategy to become more interdisciplinary in IMR – the approach is rather pragmatic; if someone has project funding, they can use researchers and people from across the entire organisation.

4.2 Domains of relevance for this case

4.2.1 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

Collaboration with the universities

The IMR collaborates with several of the Norwegian universities, in particular with the University of Bergen, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, the University of Agder and the University of Western Norway. Collaboration with other research institutions and the sector at large is considered important, not only for development of the best possible research and advice, but also to find and develop good solutions for future.

Most of the collaborations are at project level and tend to focus on joint grant applications to RCN and EU. These collaborations are mostly bottom up and are generated by the researchers themselves. There is also some collaboration around research infrastructure. On the question how these collaborations are initiated and what is needed to start long-lasting collaborations, the answer is, good meeting places and some sort of demonstration of usefulness. Formal agreements like MoUs between organisations can be useful internationally, but the experience of IMR is that they are insufficient to foster collaboration between Norwegian organisations. Instead, what is needed is 'on the ground' contact; people have to walk around and make friends; one really has to work well together on the ground. Natural meeting places in front of the coffee machine are important, especially to bring about interdisciplinary collaboration. And there are examples of this within the institute. Some collaborations have their origin in long-standing personal relationships between individual researchers.

IMR also actively uses 'Researcher 2' positions and PhD students to start collaborative relationships. And incentives are important. According to IMR, researchers are very cynical about publications; having the research published in high impact scientific journals is what counts. And rewarding collaboration in itself is not very useful – it must generate something of value.

4.2.2 Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use

Industry collaboration

IMR collaborates with industry mainly on the basis of research projects and as an advisor. Both approaches requires that IMR has a good understanding of the sector and the challenges of the industry. IMR does not do contract research or targeted innovation but some of the services

they offer, like risk analyses, is in effect a way to identify innovation needs, often across disciplines. Innovations can therefore often be by-products of giving advice.

Norwegian fishing businesses are very pushy and innovative. There are well-functioning business clusters, especially in aquaculture. IMR is a member of some of the clusters and finds them good meeting places to share ideas and discuss common interests. Many of the needs that are identified through these discussions end up as projects.

The reason why IMR does not do contract research is because of their mission and role as consultative body and advisor, and the ownership of the institute. Nor is there any pressure from the ministries on the institute to conduct contract research. Being the preferred advisor of the marine industry is not compatible with doing contract research for them. Therefore, the industry rarely comes to IMR if they have a need they want research collaboration to solve. Instead Nofima is the research institute in Norway where industry usually goes.

Innovation collaborations through centres for research-based innovation (SFIs)

Innovation collaboration with industry happens mostly through RCN funded centres for research-based innovation (SFI in Norwegian), and IMR has good track record in attracting funding for several such centres over years.

IMR can have various roles in these SFIs, both as a research partner and as a user. One example of a successful SFI that has ended up with an innovative product that IMR is now using, is the CRISP project. Through that SFI, which was focusing on developing smarter technologies to meet future challenges for a sustainable and economically viable fishing industry, a completely new photobox was developed which can identify and determine the size of fish in the trawl, making it possible selectively to catch some fish and release others. The photobox was developed by the industry partner Scantrol AS, a Bergen based company, together with IMR, Nofima, the University of Bergen and UiT The Arctic University of Norway. IMR has taken no ownership of the idea or the technology and is now buying the technology from Scantrol at market price. The SFI has resulted in a number of other patents and innovations as well, some of which are about to be implemented in the operations. IMR also has a long-standing cooperation with Kongsberg, for instance on sonar development, currently through another SFI called CRIMAC, centre for research-based innovation in marine acoustic abundance estimation and backscatter classification. SFIs are good instruments, according to IMR. The funding is long term and the partnership model is working very well.

Aqua Nor

One important international meeting place for the aquaculture industry is the Aqua Nor conference which has existed since 1979, and today is the world's largest trade fair for aquaculture technology. Here, all news of importance to the industry is presented. During Aqua Nor, a number of seminars, conferences, presentations, lectures and debates are arranged that help to keep visitors professionally up to date. These events are partly managed by the Nor-Fishing Foundation, partly by exhibitors, institutions and companies.

For some years, Aqua Nor has hosted a meeting place called the "Research Square" aimed for discussions about research and innovation, and to bring together the research, innovation and teaching environments that are exhibitors at the fair, ie the Institute of Marine Research, Nofima, the Veterinary Institute, Akvaplan-niva, NINA (Norwegian Institute for Natural Research), NORCE, SINTEF Ocean / NTNU, UiT, Nord University, NMBU (Norwegian University of Life Sciences, FHF (Fisheries and Aquaculture Research Fund), Innovation Norway and the Research Council of Norway.

Student day

The marine industry needs to attract the best minds to be able to develop further. Therefore, the Nor-Fishing Foundation has established their own Student Day in collaboration with NTNU, Brohode Havbruk 2050 and regional partners. All students get free admission to the fair and there is always a seminar arranged to inspire the students before they visit the exhibition area where students can meet the companies and organisations that want to collaborate or are looking for new employees. In 2017, more than 200 students participated in this event.

4.2.3 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations

Understanding the marine sector is key to IMR, not because of innovation but because of the role the organisation has as an advisor for the sector. The work environment at the Institute of Marine Research is considered good and creative in terms of supporting and promoting industry collaboration, and the institute has a large network of many business actors and organisations, great activity in dissemination and also innovation by using new methods and new ways of working for increased quality and efficiency.

Training and education

Continuous improvement and renewal of the expertise of the institute is important, and the Academy of Marine Research is a strategic initiative to secure that. Through the academy, IMR is offering the employees internal training and institute-specific education needed. The academy is also coordinating other training courses offered by external organisations as well as managing courses at master and BSc level at some of the Norwegian universities. The academy also brokers master's projects. Everyone working at IMR can suggest courses and a separate association is put together to coordinate across the different departments. The courses offered are within IT, biology, fieldwork, technical/administrative, statistics and laboratory work.

Prizes and awards to stimulate innovation

Even though innovation is not at the top of the agenda of IMR, the sector is in great need for innovation and renewal. Every year, various prizes and awards are given to the players in the marine sector to stimulate innovation. One such is the innovation award established in 2003 by the Nor-Fishing Foundation to stimulate equipment suppliers and others to innovate and improve. Over the years, the Innovation Award has contributed to the winners being able to launch their finished products and services. Another award is the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries' Environmental Prize, given to a producer who has launched environmentally friendly products or processes. The award has long traditions and enjoys great prestige among suppliers.

4.2.4 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

Innovation is not on the agenda of IMR but rather a by-product of their work; the mandate is to do research, advisory work and monitoring and the institute is not entitled from the ministries to commercialize the research. Therefore, IMR does not engage in targeted innovation, but they still do innovation for the purpose to improve and renew the in-house need for instrumentation and internal operations. There is always a massive need for new technology and ways to observe, and this is a major driver for innovation at IMR, more so than in many other kinds of environmental research. Research from IMR has resulted in a number of innovations, i.e. new de-lousing methods and methods for avoiding salmon lice, such as "snorkel cages", sampling cannon for use in the fishing fleet, new methods for using echo sounders and sonar for sustainable fishing, optical species determination and sizing system. trawl, and software for identifying different species in broadband sonar images. But the institute

must be careful regarding the monitoring activities. There, continuity and reproducibility are extremely important, as the data analysis is based on time series over many years and the results have to be comparable over time. Minor changes in the technical equipment can sometime be enough to destroy the compatibility. Therefore, they cannot innovate too much in that area.

Research infrastructures and laboratories

IMR has a world-class infrastructure with extensive biological experimental facilities, advanced equipment for monitoring and observation, laboratories and IT infrastructure, in addition to a number of vessels and a database from genetic bioprospecting in Tromsø, Marbank. The infrastructure is a prerequisite for IMR to be able to deliver both monitoring services, advanced research and advice in line with the continuously developing needs and requirements of the marine industry. A specific committee is appointed to work strategically with the development and renewal of the infrastructure.

The activity within the institute is high and the most modern facilities are usually fully utilized by themselves. Generally, IMR allows researchers to come on their cruises and are open for use of the research stations and facilities when there is unused capacity. To what extent this is possible and to what cost depends a bit on the engagement of IMR in that research and will be considered case by case.

Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC)

The Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC) is the e-infrastructure of IMR which offers seamless access to documented and annotated marine data sets from important Norwegian sea areas to the marine research community. NMDC is funded as an infrastructure project by the Research Council of Norway and is composed of a total of 14 partners, among these UiO, UiB and UiT. The development phase of the project was completed in 2017, and the project is now in its third year of operation. Together with several other research infrastructures that also focus on sharing and preserving research data, NMDC has arranged joint user meetings, including the topic "How can national and international research infrastructures help the national research environments?". This is to have a good dialogue with the user communities in order to be able to deliver relevant services.

Tech Transfer and IP

IMR is one of the co-owners of VIS, the TTO of the Bergen region, together with the University of Bergen, Haukeland University Hospital, Siva, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, and NHH Norwegian Business School. VIS takes care of everything related to innovation and commercialisation and provides relevant advice and support. VIS is a very active partner that regularly reminds IMR to look for ideas and innovation opportunities that they can bring further. IP and ownership is regulated case by case and there are some examples of researchers getting IPR in inventions and selling their rights.

4.2.5 Domain 7 – RRI

Open data sharing

In addition to being of great importance to IMR and their own operations, the data being collected is also of great importance to other players within the sector. The institute has an open data policy that emphasises the sharing of data in society's best interests and IMR is supposed to make data and research results known and available to the public administration,

other research institutions, industry, consumers and society in general. As part of this responsibility, the institute has to:

- Ensure good and adapted dissemination of research results.
- Collect, manage and make available national marine data, including seafood data, and ensure that these are disseminated quickly to relevant users.
- Develop and operate a national marine biobank.
- Take advantage of the opportunities that lie in utilising data material from the fishing fleet and the aquaculture industry.
- Optimise and streamline data access.

IMR uses a Creative Commons approach for data sharing, implying that data are open for non-commercial use. There are no restrictions on who can access and use their data but they do not want international companies to download and mirror the data. In the event of a need for larger scale use, they would be asked to contact HFI for a separate agreement.

The ambition is to give access also to raw data available, e.g. sonar, but sometimes there can be technical limitations meaning that not everyone can access all the data they want.

4.3 Conclusions

- To promote convergence, good meeting-places are needed
- Good understanding of the sector is fundamental. It is hard to solve problems for other people if you do not know what they are struggling with. Therefore, make sure you have industry knowledge, which takes time and experience to gain
- In terms of value creation – look for the low-hanging fruit and make tailor made solutions, specifically for them
- Regulation and compliance are rich sources of needs for innovation – when searching for innovation opportunities it could be useful for DLN to include these areas
- Equally, growing data-intensity with the use of sensors, sensor networks, big data and large databases provide new sets of innovation opportunities
- Active participation in ecosystems with other actors – universities, institutes, clusters, companies – provides both information about innovation needs and opportunities and channels
- Opening access to instrumentation, data sources, data bases similarly create channels for identifying and satisfying innovation needs

5 KU Leuven Research & Development (LRD)

5.1 Background and context

The Katholieke Universiteit Leuven was originally founded by papal bull in 1425 in the Duchy of Brabant. It has a complex history as the area in which it was located passed first in France and later into The Netherlands and finally became part of modern Belgium. In 1968 KU Leuven was split up into the Dutch-speaking KU Leuven in Leuven and the French-speaking Universit Catholique de Louvain in the new town of Louvain-la-Neuve. Today KU Leuven is a university with 16 faculties within the Humanities, Science & Technology and Biomedical Sciences. The overall research expenses were 476m in 2018. In 2019, KU Leuven was ranked seventh on the list of the world's most innovative universities in the Reuters annual ranking. Its current core tasks are academic education, scientific research and service to the community including knowledge and technology transfer.

In 2018–2019 KU Leuven had 58,254 students of whom 17.7% international. As of 2020 KU Leuven employs 14,129 people, of whom 1,850 are tenured academic staff, 1,792 postdoctoral staff, 407 teaching staff and 4,453 administrative and other non-academic staff. Leuven University Hospital has 2,000 beds and 8,167 employees.

The university itself is at the centre of a very big ecosystem. Within the legal framework of KU Leuven, there are, besides education activities, two entities that are independent. One is the University Hospital; the other is KU Leuven Research & Development (LRD). LRD, founded in 1972, was one of the first university technology transfer offices in the EU. LRD was created in the 1970s when there was an ambition to make KU Leuven more research-based and to attract more money for research from industry, especially because the amount of government research funding available was very small at that time. Some PhD students were sent abroad to learn from UC Berkeley, Stanford University and MIT. When they returned, they became professors with a knowledge of technology transfer activities from Silicon Valley and the Boston Route 128 area. This helped LRD create the instruments needed to support industry-academia collaborations. Over time, KU Leuven researchers learned to work with industry, and regional companies started increasingly to look outside for technology. Companies in Flanders were incentivised via funding from the new innovation agency (IWT) to approach the university with projects and problems to be solved. LRD learned to understand the basic building blocks of technology transfer, spin-offs, and contract or collaborative research. LRD continues to manage the use of government innovation subsidy instruments and contract research at KU Leuven, in addition to its own innovation instruments.

It took a long time, however, to build up the LRD activity. It started at a very small scale in about 1970. In 1998, the turnover was still only 14m. In the last 20 years or so, companies have increasingly looked extramurally for sources of technology, so this has helped LRD to grow. It is much easier to be successful and offer a good range of services once the organisation has achieved a certain scale.

KU Leuven Research & Development (LRD), the Technology & knowledge transfer office of KU Leuven, is the bridge between the university, industry, and society. It offers support to researchers in their innovation and new technologies to their industry partners. Its mission is "Promoting and supporting knowledge and technology transfer between university and society".

Today, LRD runs as an autonomous centre within KU Leuven, with its own budget & human resources. The operational budget of LRD comes from the 17% overhead paid by projects involving industry collaboration, half of which goes directly to LRD. The income generated from

the project overhead is sufficient for LRD to sustain itself, so it can operate without needing additional funds from KU Leuven. LRD comprises research units and central management which, in addition to overseeing administrative operations for LRD, also includes units that facilitate technology transfer, research commercialisation and intellectual property management (Figure 1).

Across the units under Central Management LRD offers comprehensive services, i.e. expertise, support, resources, funds and a mechanism to work in close collaboration with the industry. Part of this work is to manage intellectual property rights including patentability assessment, IP strategy, filing and follow up patents and partner agreements. In 2018 LRD administered 650 active patent families in portfolio and supported €57m in license-income.

Figure 1 LRD organisation chart

Source: KU Leuven Organisational Chart. Available at: <https://www.kuleuven.be/wieiswie/en/unit/global/50017594>

5.2 Domains of relevance for this case

5.2.1 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital

While the full process of research commercialisation will be discussed under Domain 6, here we present a look at how KU Leuven and the LRD offers financial support for its research.

LRD offers opportunities for both pre-seed capital (CD3) and seed capital (GFF and the KU Leuven Patent Fund). LRD also maintains a network of business angels and investors it has

attracted and with which it has had prior dealings. This network of investors is involved in 2nd round funding (though there is the possibility of GFF extending its funding to 2nd round as well). Figure 2 presents the importance of external capital in funding spin-offs where during the period of 2005-2020 the funding from KU Leuven and GFF into spin-offs was a fraction of the investments made by external parties.

Figure 2 Investments in KU Leuven spin-offs (€) in 2005–2020

Source: KU Leuven (2021). *KU Leuven Research & Development Advancing the Impact of Research Results*. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/doc/lrd-brochure-2021>

However, the role of KU Leuven and LRD funding to successfully launch spin-offs should not be underestimated. The aim is that all funds and support needed for the researcher to valorise research is provided through LRD. The scale and number of projects makes it possible for LRD to be self-sustaining.

The Centre for Drug Design and Discovery (CD3)

The Centre for Drug Design and Discovery (CD3)⁵¹ handles pre-seed funding and brings expert drug discovery capabilities and financial resources to academic research groups and small companies. CD3 capital is co-provided by the LRD and the European Investment Fund (EIF) with 3 funds launched in 2006, 2010 and the latest in 2016 (with a capital of €60m from the LRD and EIF)⁵². In total, CD3 has received €84m.⁵³

CD3 focuses on funding the translation of innovative research into promising drug discovery programmes that are well qualified for further development by pharma or biotech companies.

⁵¹ <https://www.cd3.be/about-cd3> <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/en/news/ku-leuven2019s-centre-for-drug-design-and-discovery-closes-60-million-euro-fund-to-turn-academic-research-into-new-medicines>

⁵² KU Leuven (2016). *KU Leuven's Centre for Drug Design and Discovery closes 60 million euro fund to turn academic research into new medicines*. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/en/news/ku-leuven2019s-centre-for-drug-design-and-discovery-closes-60-million-euro-fund-to-turn-academic-research-into-new-medicines>

⁵³ Centre for Drug Design and Discovery (2021). *Organisation*. Available at: <https://www.cd3.be/about-cd3/organization>

Unlike the GFF (which we discuss further on), CD3 works with potential drug discoveries within and outside of KU Leuven. CD3's general investment principles are

- CD3 focuses primarily on investing in small molecule discoveries; however, there is also the option to receive funding for therapeutic antibody development
- CD3 works with collaborative research projects, start-up biotech companies that are working on: "modulation of biological targets or pathways to prevent or treat human disease with an unmet medical need. Biologically active compounds at any development stage can also be starting points for a drug discovery collaboration"⁵⁴
- CD3 invests in projects, start-ups, etc. that provide an: "innovative biological rationale linking modulation of the specific target or pathway to a beneficial effect on the disease of interest with an acceptable side-effect profile"⁵⁵
- CD3 does not actively look for investment opportunities; rather, researchers, start-ups, biotech companies wishing to receive funding from CD3 can apply with their proposal which then undergoes a multi-stage evaluation process:⁵⁶ the proposed research project is presented for initial evaluation during a (if possible) face-to-face meeting. This meeting primarily focuses on the scientific aspects of the proposal, identifying whether the research meets the investment criteria for CD3. If required, the CD3 signs a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) with the applicants
- Projects that are deemed to be scientifically relevant to D3 then undergo a further preliminary evaluation which now combines scientific and financial analysis of the proposal, with the applicants required to submit any relevant documentation. The preliminary evaluation takes up to four weeks
- Projects that are selected after the preliminary evaluation receive further support from CD3 based on the level of progress. Early-stage projects sign a collaboration agreement with CD3. For advanced projects, CD3 helps prepare a project proposal which is submitted to the Scientific Advisory Board and Investment Committee of CD3
- The Scientific Advisory Board evaluates the scientific aspects of the submitted project proposal. This means that by the final stages the scientific aspect has undergone three review stages to ensure it meets the scientific foci and criteria of the CD3. However, the final decision lies with the Investment Committee which evaluates the business viability of the project

KU Leuven Patent Fund

To support researchers seeking to submit patent application, LRD manages the KU Leuven Patent Fund which available to researchers who lack sufficient funds to submit their applications themselves. (LRD also provides guidelines for researchers about the costs of patenting at different stages to support their decision making). The fund is supported through

⁵⁴ Centre for Drug Design and Discovery (2021). What are we looking for in a project? Available at: <https://www.cd3.be/about-cd3/what-are-we-looking-for-in-a-project>

⁵⁵ Centre for Drug Design and Discovery (2021). What are we looking for in a project? Available at: <https://www.cd3.be/about-cd3/what-are-we-looking-for-in-a-project>

⁵⁶ Centre for Drug Design and Discovery (2021). How to apply with your project? Available at: <https://www.cd3.be/about-cd3/procedure>

contributions each time a funded patent is licensed⁵⁷, in line with LRD's overall approach of maintaining self-sustainability of its operations.

Gemma Frisius Fund (GFF)

Gemma Frisius Fund (GFF) is the seed capital fund designed to stimulate the creation and growth of KU Leuven spin-off companies. The fund is a joint venture between KU Leuven (20%), KBC Bank (40%) and BNP Paribas Fortis Private Equity (40%), and was launched in 1997. GFF entails a combination of knowledge and technology transfer expertise (university) and financial expertise (financial partners). The fund has about €36.5m invested in 58 spin-off companies.⁵⁸ It is an evergreen fund, which means that whenever there is an exit, the money goes back into the fund, for future investment. The general investment principles of the GFF include the following:

- GFF funds spin-offs based on any research, technology, innovation, etc. coming from KU Leuven. As such, GFF does not have a preferred focus for the type of research or technology are funded – the primary concern is the relation to KU Leuven
- GFF focuses primarily on first round funding. Exceptions can be made for second-round funding if this is necessary to ensure the spin-off's growth. In such cases GFF cooperates with other external investors that are also involved in the second round

GFF funding period generally lasts for 7-10 years. As an evergreen fund, GFF investment is made in exchange for shares in the spin-off, making GFF a long-term investor. Hence, GFF generally has representatives on the spin-off's board of directors.

GFF is divided into two operational units: the advisory board and the board of directors. The advisory board is responsible for evaluating the proposed spin-off ideas and supporting researchers in preparing their business plan. In addition, spin-offs that are funded by GFF can benefit from guidance in managing the spin-off growth. The board of directors is responsible for approving the final business plan (drafted with help from advisory board).

The GFF fund has also enabled the LRD to expand its investment opportunities. Some of the GFF profits were invested (as a limited partner) in amounts between €1m and €5m in a dozen other funds. These are all specialised, e.g in biotech, smart manufacturing, sustainable chemistry, and ICT and are both local and regional but mostly international (e.g. NL, DK, SE, DE, FR). LRD's initial investment in a company is made using their own internal seed funds, but when companies move on to subsequent investments, LRD can continue investing with these more specialised funds. When LRD proposes a project to one of these specialised investment funds, the researcher will get a review and feedback on their projects whether the investment is made or not. It is important for LRD's reputation that the projects they suggest to others for investment are solid. This secures LRD's position in this 'financial ecosystem'.

Governmental funding instruments

LRD also manages governmental funding instruments to realise industrial proof-of-concept studies or produce convincing prototypes for the market. KU Leuven Industrial Research Fund, financed by the Flemish government, supports innovative research & development projects with clear industrial or societal applications. Several specialised incubation instruments were

⁵⁷ KU Leuven (2021). KU Leuven Research & Development Advancing the Impact of Research Results. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/doc/lrd-brochure-2021>

⁵⁸ KU Leuven (2020). Gemma Frisius Fund: portfolio. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/en/spinoff/gemma-frisius-fund-portfolio>

created in order to meet the need to finance projects at an early stage of development. Further the LRD's Flemish and Federal Government Funding Department supports researchers in applying for government funding. These applications must be to finance public-private partnerships with an aim to implement research results.⁵⁹

5.2.2 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

When discussing how LRD (and KU Leuven) operates in a wider context, we can separate the discussion into 2 parts – networks and ecosystems. Since the 1990's LRD has been involved in creating networks that focus on particular areas of innovation. By 2021, the LRD was part of five such networks, of which three were horizontal networks (bringing together wider range of different stakeholders and operating under the triple helix principles and with a wider technological focus) and two were vertical networks (bringing together specific stakeholders with a specific technological focus).⁶⁰ The horizontal networks of LRD include:

- Leuven.Inc – a network that supports high-tech entrepreneurship and increasing collaboration, partnerships, relationships between investors, researchers, and businesses. The network also focuses on social impacts and promotes social entrepreneurship⁶¹
- Smart Hub Vlaams-Brabant – a network that focuses on the Flemish Brabant region and establishing it as a high-tech innovator in Europe. The network operates five tech hubs each focusing on a specific area of research – Smart Hub Health, Smart Hub Food, Smart Hub Logistics, Smart Hub Cleantech and Smart Hub Creativity⁶²
- ELAT: the Eindhoven-Leuven-Aachen triangle. Operating as a high-tech ecosystem, the ELAT: Eindhoven -Leuven -Aachen triangle is a cross-border and interregional network built to stimulate the knowledge economy

The vertical networks in which LRD is involved in are:

- LSEC – a network that focuses on IT and electronic security and raising security awareness
- DSP Valley – network that brings together members working with smart electronic systems, working across the entire value chain

As for the ecosystems, LRD is an active member of the Leuven MindGate initiative which seeks to establish the region as a premier high-tech ecosystem. Launched in 2016 as a collaboration between 29 organisations, Leuven MindGate is based on the Triple Helix model, combining the efforts of knowledge institutions, the government and the private sector towards common goals and collaborations.

⁵⁹ KU Leuven (2018). Flemish government funding. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/en/Flemish-government-funding/what-do-we-do>

⁶⁰ KU Leuven (2021). Networks. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/en/hitech/networks>

⁶¹ Leuven.Inc (2019). More About Leuven.Inc and its Foundation. Available at: <https://www.leuveninc.com/about>

⁶² Smart Hub Vlaams-Brabant (2021). 5 Smart Hubs. Available at: <https://www.smarthubvlaamsbrabant.be/international/#projects>

Figure 3 Leuven MindGate triple helix approach

Source: Leuven MindGate (2021). About Leuven MindGate. Available at: <https://www.leuvenmindgate.be/about-leuven-mindgate>

Within the context of Leuven MindGate, LRD enables ecosystem development through establishing and managing different types of research and innovation infrastructures that provide state-of-the-art labs and office space for innovative spin-off companies as well as international research-intensive companies. This infrastructure consists of:

- Incubators. LRD is responsible for managing four incubators: KU Leuven Innovation and Incubation Centre provides shared services and facilities and offers management support (financial and managerial advice) for businesses and focuses on research-oriented businesses with a preference for working with KU Leuven and [IMEC](#) entrepreneurs. [Leuven Bio-Incubator](#) focuses on biotech start-ups with support services divided between business and science needs of entrepreneurs. [Kortrijk Innovation & Incubation Centre](#) works with high-tech start-ups, providing working spaces, business support services and the technological infrastructure to launch and operate high-tech companies. Lastly, [Tienen Biogenerator](#) is focused on supporting food-tech start-ups⁶³
- Science parks. Currently LRD operates two science parks with a third one expected to launch in the future – these science parks are located within the area of Leuven city. The Arenberg Science Park (launched in 2004) is composed of four clusters: two dedicated to biotech research and two other clusters working with ICT and high-tech research. The second science park is Haasrode Science Park which houses KU Leuven spin-offs and international businesses. A third science park – Leuven Noord – is still under development in collaboration with NMBS and the City of Leuven. In addition, LRD is collaborating with city of Genk and the University of Hasselt on one and the city of Tienen on another science park outside of Leuven

⁶³ KU Leuven (2021). Incubators. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/en/hitech/incubators>

- Business centres. LRD operates three business centres: the Leuven Business Centre (an incubator and office space for new businesses), the Ubicentre (office space), and Remy Campus (focus on tech companies, provides office space)

The city of Leuven has been a strong support in this work by enabling LRD to expand its infrastructure. For example, when a company wants to locate to Leuven for its R&D, or when creating a new incubator, the city administration makes sure that permits and local legislation are in place to facilitate the process. The resulting high-tech ecosystem of Leuven, secured by the strong cooperation between universities, industry, the government and the international orientation of the city, has also led KU Leuven to be increasingly involved in European consortium projects and in Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) of the European Institute of Innovation & Technology.

In addition, Leuven has significant investment capital to support the many incubators, science parks, and business centres. In the ecosystem that LRD actively developed, they have built a strong link with VCs operating in the region. These are leveraged, not so much financially, but on their goodwill to help entrepreneurs and scientists becoming entrepreneurs or becoming part of an entrepreneurial venture.

Of importance is also that LRD is an active member of its own professional community, the League of European Research Universities (LERU), ensuring that it does not get isolated. This community shares best-practice and has triggered some joint projects and spin-offs. In addition, membership of the Flanders TTO network entails best-practice sharing and visibility for the tech transfer organisations in the Flemish university landscape.

5.2.3 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations

Creating an innovation culture starting with the students - Kick

KU Leuven recognises that engaging the students in entrepreneurship is needed to secure a viable innovation culture. The intention of involving students went on for many years, but there were few links to the student community. The LRD staff experienced that other institutions like Cambridge had access to students and the interest of students in both research and development, while in Leuven they found this was not the case. This led to the creation of LC Leuven Centre for Innovation Driven Entrepreneurship in 2012/2013. The initiative started by engaging the Deans in order to get access to the faculties, but the Deans could not agree on where to place the centre, because the university incentive system would award credits for the students involved to whichever faculty housed the centre. The Deans of engineering, business and economics and medicine each felt the centre should be in their own faculty. In addition, there was a lot of life science activity going on, outside these faculties.

The dispute had not been resolved by 2014, so the students themselves had started to work on entrepreneurship. In an old warehouse belonging to the father of one of them, the students created 10 companies. Eventually, the Deans were bypassed, a new steering group was formed, and the student body was made the owner of the Leuven Community for Innovation Driven Entrepreneurship (Lcie), later re-named Kick.

Kick is now a faculty-independent and bottom-up community-driven entity. An old incubator was given to the students, and since then, about 70 companies have been created. The Deans have come back on board, but students now tell them what courses to run.

Entrepreneurial training at KUL

There are initiatives to formalise entrepreneurial learning and courses in the university setting, and a new trend in educational policy that emphasises the entrepreneurial skills that students should acquire regardless of their discipline (in parallel with Kick).

Other community initiatives that engage students are *IusStart* (legal advice), *TechStart* (tech advice), *Id-Start* (creative advice), and *PIP* (interdisciplinary project course). A one-year post-graduate programme was launched by the Faculty of Engineering: *Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Engineering*.

LRD facilitates entrepreneurship at the operational level and has become an indispensable unit embedded in a larger entrepreneurial ecosystem that has considerable impact on the entrepreneurial culture of the institution. It is a TTO that constantly adapts to the changing environment and seeks improvements that create a sustainable ecosystem to encompass bottom-up initiatives.

LRD is viewed by the users as a facilitator, a service provider, a tool, and a catalyst. It plays an indispensable role for the professors and researchers who want to participate in technology transfer. LRD provides expertise, support and resources/funds, which are great aid for self-driven entrepreneurs in the university.

“At this moment, one cannot realise the idea without services anymore.”

“The professors do not see LRD only as a compulsory administrative organization where they need to get stamps or signatures from. They see LRD as their own tools; a mechanism that they use as their own to work with the industry. ... LRD is financed by a small portion of the turnover generated by the professors, so the professors feel that LRD are their personal tools.”⁶⁴

Inviting role models to give speeches or have meetings with the students to share their stories and experience is a common practice to promote a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship. The TTO plays a crucial role in encouraging risk-taking behaviour among the academics. By providing a risk-free financial mechanism within the accounting system of LRD, professors can set up virtual companies to experience the market without taking any actual financial or administrative risks. Without a reasonable or attractive financial return, it is hard to keep the entrepreneurial spirit active within the system. There appear to be different points of view about the importance of financial rewards for innovation. Background documentation we read suggests that a high financial return for those employed in KU Leuven and LRD encourages the professors to continue engaging in entrepreneurship activities, but we were also told that such financial motivation is only a very minor driver for innovation.

5.2.4 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

As engaging with industry has always been high on the policy agenda in Flanders, the university has always had a strong focus on getting the industry involved. Over many years, Flemish policy has emphasised the need for higher education, research and industry to grow in parallel so that they create a virtuous circle of development with strong interaction between the research and industrial sectors.

⁶⁴ Wang, L. (2018) “The impact of TTO on institutional entrepreneurial culture formation - A case study of KU Leuven Research & Development”.

Due to this long-standing collaboration culture, KU Leuven has a mature perspective on owning IP based on its research. While many other universities expect to own the IP and a large share in any companies generated, LRD has learnt that there are limits to what you can expect and what companies will accept. Negotiations are done case by case on what is a fair return. This can sometimes involve the University in receiving other benefits than ownership, such as sponsorship or becoming a service centre. This flexibility lets the university build strong and sustainable relationships with individual companies. Currently, about 80-90% of companies that have worked with KU Leuven come back and do so again.

The core tasks of LRD are to manage research collaborations, protect intellectual property, set up spin-off companies, provide incubation and seed funds, and create a high-tech ecosystem. LRD gives administrative, legal and financial support in a wide variety of dossiers, government assignments and contract research with the industry. In earlier chapters, we have discussed the funding available (Domain 2) and entrepreneurial infrastructure (Domain 3), and these opportunities contribute to the technology transfer practices discussed in this chapter. This section presents a look at how LRD is structured to engage with researchers and enable research commercialisation while reducing the burdens related to the business side of research commercialisation.

LRD takes on the role of promoting entrepreneurship by assisting the researchers to create spin-off companies, based on patents, where applicable. LRD helps the researchers develop business plans, validate the market, find investors and infrastructures and manage intellectual property. It offers the researchers legal support and help putting together a competent team and managing further growth of the spin-offs. Their helps transform the researchers' innovative ideas and technologies into new technology-based companies. Researchers are employed in LRD's research divisions, through which they can manage their technology transfer activities autonomously and be supported by an LRD team. Each research division can use the resources it has acquired from research exploitation to finance early-stage development and validation projects.

By setting up virtual companies under the umbrella system of LRD, professors are supported to be entrepreneurial without having to take any financial or administrative risks. LRD creates an environment for those who want to take the risk and go for it. All the projects and activities that are carried out by the researchers are set up and monitored by the virtual companies created within the accounting system of LRD. In this accounting system, professors can set up new virtual companies by creating new divisions under the LRD accounting system and hire by using LRD's HR service.

LRD is structured so that the researchers it supports are on the LRD payroll. Approx. 25–30 % of researchers' wages are paid by LRD. To support the projects, LRD has approximately 100 FTEs, half of whom are back-office (financial admin, HR, legal) staff. The 50 people in the front-office work with IP (15), spin-off (12), legal, regional business development, (industry liaison, association with incubators etc). This front-office also handles contacts with the regional VCs. During 2020, approx. 4,000 new contracts were signed.

LRD makes initial contact with the researchers at times when they see opportunities for collaboration. LRD maintains contacts with the researchers and the laboratories frequently by having an effective governance structure. That is, by using the internal financial mechanism managed by LRD to provide services that the researchers use regularly. Further, the networks in which LRD is embedded and the relationships it develops with businesses and other research organisations mean that LRD is positioned to leverage its contacts and encourage collaborative projects. As a result, since 2005 there has been a near annual increase in new

collaborative research contracts signed with KU Leuven researchers with 2020 accounting for 2,800+ new contracts signed.

Figure 4 New collaborative research contracts signed at KU Leuven

Source: KU Leuven (2021). *KU Leuven Research & Development Advancing the Impact of Research Results*. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/doc/lrd-brochure-2021>

In KU Leuven there is no applied research division. Applied and basic research are mixed and spring out of fundamental research. The dilemma of publishing papers vs secrecy of patentable research is handled through agreements. The industry cannot prevent a researcher from publishing, but publishing delays of up to six months can be negotiated. The PhD researchers are normally not fully engaged in industry projects. PhDs' salaries are not taxed but the government therefore requires a PhD project is independent of commercial interests, so PhD work is typically kept separate from the industry collaborations. On the other hand, any IP belongs to the university where research is funded by government and the university is expected to use this IP in collaborations. If a researcher is in collaboration with a company that pays for the research, then the IP is owned by company, but some collaborations will be built on background IP from the university. In such circumstances, agreements must be made, so that the university get a fair return from the company. There has been some learning through the years on how to structure the agreements. There is a limit to what the university can expect (cannot claim 100% vis-a-vis a company), while the companies need to acknowledge that the university's IP is not free, even though it is funded by the government. The "fair return" could be many things, e.g royalty, sponsoring a PhD, or the university becoming a "service centre" for the company, for example. The "fair return" clause secures that a business agreement is advantageous for both parties, proper distribution of value from IP, and fair compensation to the university where the IP ownership lies with the company. LRD have learned from experience that good deals make companies returning companies.

Researchers may continue to get funds from the government even if they have ownership in an industry collaboration, but then there is a need to consider conflict of interest. As funding always comes through the university, LRD has a role in overseeing that there are no conflicts of interest. In addition, this gives LRD the option to pay researchers on their request if they are successful. LRD may pay this as a direct salary supplement. This form of salary supplement is capped to be a maximum of doubling the salary of the researcher involved. So a research group that is highly efficient and successful might have quite some income from the industry.

But this means that they cannot have a direct contract with that company but have to run it by the tech transfer office. In general, these salary requests typically amount to <1% of the LRD spending, and is generally awarded younger researchers. The main drive of the researchers come from advancing the science.

This approach towards technology transfer has resulted in 140+ spin-offs launched since the 1980s, with significant growth in the number of spin-offs evident in the 2nd half of 1990s – a period which saw the launch of GFF (supporting funding of spin-offs) and LRD's expanding involvement in networks (supporting research). By 2020 the active spin-offs employed 7,200+ people. These spin-offs were made possible by KU Leuven and LRD investing € 2.7m in its spin-off companies with a further €1b raised in external capital.

Figure 5 KU Leuven spin-offs – created and active

Source: KU Leuven (2021). *KU Leuven Research & Development Advancing the Impact of Research Results*. Available at: <https://lrd.kuleuven.be/doc/lrd-brochure-2021>

5.3 Conclusions

In summary, when examining the success factors, the following approaches and conditions stand out as enablers of an infrastructure that can successfully support technology transfer and innovation.

- It takes many years to build a comprehensive structure like LRD. It succeeds because it has scale but especially because it is built into the very structure of the university
- LRD creates favourable conditions for entrepreneurial researchers with a comprehensive infrastructure that includes pre and seed capital, IP rights consulting, business development
- Much of the success of LRD is due to early and continuous involvement with the industry. This has created a network of contacts, both for collaborative research and financial investment that LRD can leverage when enabling research commercialisation
- Much of LRD's income comes from an overhead on industry contracted research – this has ensured the self-sustainability of LRD operations
- For start-ups, researchers can form virtual companies under the LRD umbrella, de-risking start-up formation
- Researchers are in charge of the commercialisation project but they also receive expert support and close follow-up throughout the commercialisation process. This creates

conditions where researchers benefit from knowledge transfer on business matters while continuing to have the capacity to engage in research

- LRD supports and funds researchers until they become attractive to investors. LRD further aids researchers in finding (specialised) investors and industry partners
- Researcher may receive earnings from commercial activities (as wage supplement, which is capped at twice the annual salary), which is an important incentive according to researchers interviewed (Wang, 2018) but comprises less than 1% of LRD's turnover. The arrangement of a flat 17% fee from contract or collaborative research going back to the university (incl. 8,5% to LRD), is predictable and does not subtract large part of researchers funding from the project at an early stage

6 UK Centre for Mammalian Synthetic Biology (Edinburgh)

6.1 Introduction

The UK Centre for Mammalian Synthetic Biology (CMSB) was established at the University of Edinburgh in 2014 with funding from the UK research councils BBSRC, EPSRC and MRC under the Synthetic Biology for Growth Programme.

The centre focuses on research into mammalian synthetic biology, building multidisciplinary research involving synthetic and systems biology as well as other fields such as cell biology and medicine. The centre's overall vision is to develop "tools and technologies to realise the full potential of engineered biology for human and animal health and wellbeing."⁶⁵

The primary focus of this case study is on responsible research and innovation (RRI) at CMSB, but it also describes the effort to combine different sources of funding to complement the centre grant and expand towards innovation and commercialisation.

6.2 Background

6.2.1 UK policy background

The policy and investments in synthetic biology by UK research and innovation funders⁶⁶ from 2007 onward is described in the 'SYNBIOCHEM' case study. Alongside SYNBIOCHEM, CMSB was one of six multidisciplinary Synthetic Biology Research Centres (SBRCs) funded by the UK research councils as part of a £102m investment to boost research capacity in the field.⁶⁷

6.2.2 The Mammalian Centre

The University of Edinburgh was awarded a £11.4m Synthetic Biology Research Centre (SBRC) grant, running from November 2014 to September 2021. It is a 'virtual centre' with members across the university and forms part of the Centre for Synthetic and Systems Biology (SynthSys).

The initial focus of the centre's research in 2014 was the development of tools to engineer cells, enabling more sophisticated control of cell behaviour.⁶⁸ These tools, in turn allow the building of biological systems to gain a deeper understanding of natural systems, and applying the tools to accelerate biomedical research to improve health and wellbeing.⁶⁹ The centre also works

⁶⁵ <https://www.ed.ac.uk/biology/mammalian-synbio/about-us/our-centre>

⁶⁶ At the time of the awards, the seven UK research councils and Innovate UK were separate organisations are now part of a single organisation, UKRI.

⁶⁷ BBSRC: Synthetic Biology for Growth Programme: <https://bbsrc.ukri.org/research/programmes-networks/synthetic-biology-growth-programme/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.ed.ac.uk/biology/mammalian-synbio/our-research/research-work-packages/tools-for-engineered-biology>

⁶⁹ <https://www.ed.ac.uk/biology/mammalian-synbio/our-research/research-work-packages/insights-for-medicine>

with the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) to define standards for synthetic biology to help enable further growth of the field.⁷⁰

CMSB provides opportunities for industry to access facilities, in-house training, collaborative projects, consultancy services, and licencing opportunities. Industrial engagement is evidenced by visits from 14 industry partners⁷¹ and two start-up companies: Cellinta Ltd (gene therapy for cancer) and OGI Bio Ltd (microbial culturing).⁷²

Like the other SBRC's, CMSB has incorporated responsible research and innovation (RRI) into its activities and builds on the EPSRC's AREA framework (Anticipate, Reflect, Engage, Act) for responsible innovation (see also SYNBIOCHEM case study).⁷³ A dedicated team of social scientists has been part of the centre from the outset and encompasses groups from the field of science and technology studies (STS), as well as innovation studies.

6.3 Domains of relevance for this case

6.3.1 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital

6.3.1.1 Initial conditions

CMSB is based on longstanding multidisciplinary collaboration focused around the Centre for Synthetic and Systems Biology (SynthSys). This centre was founded in 2007 based on another centre-of-excellence grant from the UK research councils.⁷⁴

6.3.1.2 Research community

Grant funding in the UK often forbids the use of funding for purposes other than the core aim for the funding. Funding from the SBRC grants fund early-stage research (TRL 1-3) rather than collaborative R&D. Research funding in general also excludes funding for doctoral research. The research community is therefore required to look for multiple different grants to be able to build the desired set of complementary research and innovation activities.

6.3.1.3 Policy

The SBRCs are intended to 'stimulate innovation' by building research capacity and diverse expertise. At CMSB, the initial aim is to build tools for engineering cells to develop innovations in the biomedical field.

The UK research councils routinely collect information about research impact from grant holders, including policy influence, further funding, intellectual property, and spinout companies.⁷⁵ This reflects the interest from the funder in achieving impacts, including commercial impacts, beyond the immediate scope of the research grants.

⁷⁰ <https://www.ed.ac.uk/biology/mammalian-synbio/our-research/standards>

⁷¹ <https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=BB%2FM018040%2F1#/tabOverview>

⁷² <https://www.ed.ac.uk/biology/mammalian-synbio/for-industry>

⁷³ <https://epsrc.ukri.org/research/framework/area/>

⁷⁴ BBSRC and EPSRC funded six Centres for Integrative Systems Biology

⁷⁵ <https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=BB%2FM018040%2F1#/tabOverview>

6.3.1.4 Examples of success and success factors

CMSB has succeeded in attracting additional funding from multiple sources to connect expertise in the centre with end users, including grants from research councils, innovation agencies and charities, as well as industry co-funding. Recent examples include:

- ESRC Impact Acceleration Grant: Building Capacity for Responsible Innovation in International Biotechnology Policy Organisations (see details in the following section)
- Innovation to commercialisation of university research (ICURe) from Innovate UK
- A £8.7m partnership with Fujifilm Diosynth Biotechnologies UK to develop cost-effective ways to make modern antibody-based medicines.⁷⁶
- Investment by SV Health Investors and Cancer Research UK to establish the spin-out company 'Cellinta'.⁷⁷

6.3.1.5 Lessons

- Long-term collaboration and building multidisciplinary research capacity form the basis for attracting further funding.
- The centre grant can act as a platform for 'leveraging' funding for further activities such as training grants, co-operation, and co-funding from industry.

6.3.2 Domain 7 – RRI

6.3.2.1 Initial conditions

The collaboration between social researchers and synthetic biologists pre-dated CMSB by nearly a decade, building on a smaller networking grant as well as other joint grant bids (both successful and unsuccessful) in the intervening years. This helped to establish a trusted interdisciplinary collaborative relationship by the time the opportunity to bid for the synbio centre emerged.

6.3.2.2 The research community

Groups of social scientists within the centre have approached RRI in different ways. One group, led by Jane Calvert, has a longstanding interest in the emergence of synthetic biology and collaborated with colleagues with different disciplinary backgrounds based on this shared interest. These projects have taken various forms involving the arts as well as policy analysis (see below). Another group, led by Professor Joyce Tait from the Innogen Institute, has focused on innovation, and provided a practical approach to the implementation of RRI in industry engagement.

Formal RRI training has not been a central part of the centre since the grant does not cover doctoral research. However, longstanding collaboration between social scientists and synthetic biologists at the university has enabled them to establish social science/RRI training as a compulsory course for synthetic biology master's students going as far back as 2012.

Within the centre, interaction and collaboration among researchers from different disciplines, as well as the centre leadership, has helped bring about a culture of discussion and reflection,

⁷⁶ <https://www.ed.ac.uk/biology/synthsys/news-and-events/news/ps8-7m-collaboration-seeks-better-route-to-modern>

⁷⁷ <https://www.ed.ac.uk/biology/synthsys/news-and-events/news-2020/new-biotech-for-cancer-treatment-launches>

e.g., on and innovation pathways. It is from this process, rather than from the RRI team alone, that 'responsibility' can emerge.

6.3.2.3 Policy

Funding bodies have roles to play in providing incentives for RRI. Some researchers regard RRI as a marginal activity, but collaboration between social scientists and biologists to bid for grant funding can change the dynamic, develop collaborative relationships, and provide an incentive for everyone to take RRI seriously. The corollary is that funders need explicitly to mandate, support and reward researchers to embed RRI in funding schemes. For culture change to happen, these moves must be sustained over an extended period of time.⁷⁸

6.3.2.4 Examples of success and success factors

Research into the social and political dimensions of synthetic biology, under the banner of RRI, at the centre has led to several strands of work, each considered successful, although in very different ways. Three examples are provided below:

- Professor Tait has led the work on 'Proportionate and adaptive governance of innovative technologies' for the British Standards Institution (BSI) and BEIS, which also included a proposal for a more integrated approach incorporating responsible research and innovation within the approach to governance of innovative technologies (Tait et al. 2016). This work contributed to the development of an emerging RI standard for industry in the UK, most recently expressed in the BSI Responsible Innovation Guide, PAS 440.⁷⁹ As a 'guide', PAS 440 is less prescriptive than other types of BSI standards. It provides practical guidance to companies on how to innovate responsibly, at the organisational level as well as at the level of individual innovations and demonstrate that they are doing so. The PAS 440 guide has thereby facilitated the take-up of tools developed at the centre and elsewhere for new innovations.⁸⁰
- With collaborators external to the centre, Dr Robert Smith and Professor Jane Calvert were commissioned by BBSRC to review practices of RRI within funding organisations for ERA CoBioTech, a European network of funders of biotechnology research.⁸¹ The resulting 'Agenda for Responsible Research and Innovation in ERA CoBioTech' contained a series of recommendations for best practice in RRI to funders, project consortia and grant reviewers. The RRI approach for CoBioTech outlined in the document defined a 'broad arena' for RRI within the programme rather than narrowly defined prescriptions. It focused on four key tasks, including the following practical steps: 1. Trialling a new approach to agenda setting in ERA CoBioTech, 2. Integrating and assessing RRI within funding calls, 3. Programme-wide workshops (capacity building), and 4. piloting a novel form of programme evaluation.⁸²
- A different strand of work at the centre involved collaboration between social scientists, artists and scientists in the 'Crossing Kingdoms' project, an artist-led experiment which involved creating a unique hybrid of yeast and mammalian cells to explore the scientific and cultural implications of synthetic biology.⁸³

⁷⁸ Smith et al. (2019), p. 11.

⁷⁹ BSI (2020a)

⁸⁰ See e.g. Tait et al. (2021)

⁸¹ Smith et al. (2020)

⁸² Smith et al. (2019)

⁸³ Szymanski et al. (2020)

An important success factor for these projects has been the active involvement of the social scientists in the centre on a regular basis. For example, bi-weekly meetings, presentations, and other interactions, have helped bring everyone together as part of the centre, discussing and learning across disciplinary boundaries around the common interest in synthetic biology. This contrasts to a view of social scientists as an external team coming in to deliver RRI and ethics.

6.3.2.5 Lessons

- RRI can play multiple roles within a research centre, serving to open new perspectives and reflections as well as practical guidance and advice for stakeholder engagement and innovation
- An important condition for RRI research to flourish is providing time and space for collaborations to develop. Continued emphasis from funders on the topic, including at multiple funding scales (not just Centre funding), is important in supporting this
- Joint grant applications can provide a context for testing or developing collaborative relationships. The fact that there is money at stake can provide an incentive for all concerned to take the collaboration seriously and not regard RRI as a side activity

6.4 Conclusions

This case study of the UK Centre for Mammalian Synthetic Biology in Edinburgh has focused on the combination of funding sources building on support fundamental research supported by centre grants to build innovation and commercial partnerships, as well as the role of RRI within the centre. The key points are take-away lessons are summarised below:

- Long-term collaboration and building multidisciplinary research capacity can form the basis for attracting further funding. The centre grant can act as a platform for 'leveraging' funding for further activities, whether training grants, cooperation, and co-funding from industry
- RRI can play multiple roles within a research centre, serving to open new perspectives and reflections as well as practical guidance and advice for stakeholder engagement and innovation
- An important condition for RRI research to flourish is providing time and space for collaboration to develop
- Joint grant applications can provide the context for testing or developing collaborative relationships. The fact that there is something 'on the line' can provide the incentive for all concerned to take the collaboration seriously and not regard RRI as a side activity

6.5 List of references

6.5.1 Interviews

- Professor Jane Calvert (<https://www.sps.ed.ac.uk/staff/jane-calvert>)
- Dr Robert Smith (<https://www.sps.ed.ac.uk/staff/robert-smith>)

6.5.2 Policy background:

- BBSRC on Synthetic Biology investments: <https://bbsrc.ukri.org/research/programmes-networks/synthetic-biology-growth-programme/>
- Synthetic Biology Leadership Council: <https://www.gov.uk/government/groups/synthetic-biology-leadership-council> ; <https://ktn-uk.org/programme/synthetic-biology-leadership-council/>

- Most recent publication: “Synthetic Biology UK A Decade of Rapid Progress 2009-2019”
- Clarke and Kitney (2016), “Synthetic biology in the UK – An outline of plans and progress”, *Synthetic and Systems Biotechnology*, 1:4
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405805X16300382>)
- “Synthetic Biology Dialogue”, 2010:
<https://bbsrc.ukri.org/engagement/dialogue/activities/synthetic-biology/findings-recommendations/>
- BSI (2020a), PAS 440:2020 Responsible Innovation – Guide, available at:
https://pages.bsigroup.com/l/35972/2020-03-17/2cgcnc1?utm_source=pardot&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=SM-STAN-LAU-PAS-PAS440-2003
- BSI (2020b), *BSI Education Podcast – Standards in the spotlight: PAS 440 – Responsible Innovation*, [featuring Professor Joyce Tait], available at:
https://www.podomatic.com/podcasts/bsigroup/episodes/2020-12-07T01_09_43-08_00
- EPSRC, “Framework for Responsible Innovation”, available at:
<https://epsrc.ukri.org/research/framework/>
- Marris, C. & Calvert, J. (2020) Science and Technology Studies in Policy: The UK Synthetic Biology Roadmap. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, **45**, 34-61.

6.5.3 SysSynth-Mammalian

- The Synthetic Biology Podcast – Episode 3: Jane Calvert and Rob Smith, available at:
https://media.ed.ac.uk/media/Episode+3A+Jane+Calvert+and+Rob+Smith/1_8n6d5haj
- Smith et al. (2019) An Agenda for Responsible Research and Innovation in ERA CoBioTech. Swindon, UK: Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council and ERA CoFund on Biotechnology
- Smith, Robert (2020): Responsible research and innovation as social learning: Insights from BBSRC and the ERA CoBioTech programme, available at: <http://rri.ed.ac.uk/responsible-research-and-innovation-as-social-learning-insights-from-bbsrc-and-the-era-cobiotech-programme/>
- Smith, R.D.J. et al. (2021) Taking knowledge production seriously in responsible research and innovation, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2021.1935584>
- Szymanski et al. (2020) Crossing Kingdoms: How Can Art Open Up New Ways of Thinking About Science?, *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology | Synthetic Biology*
- Tait et al. (2017), Proportionate and Adaptive Governance of Innovative Technologies (PAGIT): A Framework to Guide Policy and Regulatory Decision Making
- Tait et al. (2021) “Responsible innovation: Its role in an era of technological and regulatory transformation”, *Engineering Biology* 2021; 5; 2-9.

7 Nofima

7.1 Background and context

Nofima is a leading institute for applied research in fisheries, aquaculture and food along the complete value chain. The goal of Nofima is to deliver internationally recognised, applied research and solutions of high quality that create socially and economically beneficial results that can be used and help strengthen the competitiveness, innovation rate and profitability of its customers. The customers of Nofima come from the aquaculture industry, the fishing industry, the land and sea-based food industry, the feed and ingredient industry, the pharmaceutical industry and public administration. The institute has an extensive collaboration with the industry to arrive at the best solutions.

Nofima was established 1 of January 2008 following a political desire to rationalise and strengthen the competitiveness of the Norwegian professional communities in the area of industry-oriented research into fisheries, aquaculture and food production and a subsequent decision to merge the four research institutions Norconserv (previously Norway's canned food laboratory), Akvaforsk, Fiskeriforskning and Matforsk. The merger initiative started in 2003 when the Ministry of Fisheries and Coastal Affairs and Ministry of Agriculture and Food made a review of the research institutes in their sectors. The year after, a newly-established steering group presented a proposal on "The blue-green food alliance – coordinated efforts and new structure," and proposals were forwarded to strengthen cooperation between marine research and agricultural research in two white papers (2004–2005). One of the arguments for combining "blue" and "green" research institutes was that consumers and authorities, both domestically and internationally, have the same demands towards food regardless of whether it is produced on land or at sea. Additionally, there were many of the same disciplinary challenges in agriculturally-based food production and the production of seafood, and a need and desire to achieve disciplinary and market-related synergies to strengthen the international competitive capacity of the two sectors. Therefore, in May 2005, the government proposed the establishment of Nofima, and the parliament supported the proposal. On 1 January 2008 the organisation became operative.

In 2011 Nofima decided to simplify and rationalise its corporate structure further and established the limited company Nofima AS which today is owned by The Norwegian government, under the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries (56.8%), Stiftelsen for landbrukets næringsmiddelforskning (33.2%) and Akvainvest Møre og Romsdal (10.0%). The institute has an annual turnover of approximately NOK675m (2019) and its largest sources of income are The Research Council of Norway, The Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries, The Norwegian Seafood Research Fund (FHF), The Foundation for Research Levy on Agricultural Products (FFL), Industrial sponsors and the EU.

Nofima's head office is in Tromsø, Norway, and it has departments in Alta, Bergen, Stavanger, Sunndalsøra, Tromsø and Ås. The institute has about 400 employees.

Nofima is a relevant case for this study with respect to the health sector and domain 1, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7.

7.1.1 Domain 1 – Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence

Research across disciplines

The research competence of Nofima is broad and covers the entire value chain within aquaculture, and significant parts of the chain within the fisheries and food sector. This means that Nofima has a very special competence profile, which ensures interdisciplinary and applied

research and comprehensive solutions for their clients. Their research is organised in the three divisions – aquaculture, food science and seafood – and focuses on the following areas: breeding and genetics, capture-based aquaculture, fish health, food and health, food safety and quality, industrial economics, innovation, consumer and sensory sciences, marine biotechnology, marketing research, nutrition and feed technology, processing technology, production biology, raw materials and process optimisation and seafood industry.

Nofima always has about 600 research projects going on, on average. Some of them are strategic research programmes, some are prestigious lighthouse projects focussing on basic research on hot topics, or nationally funded research projects, while others are more applied, innovation projects or contract research. Nofima also has a strong focus on EU projects and experience with leading and participating in EU-projects. These are larger and more complex projects and require a higher level of project management and involvement from different functions within Nofima.

The role of data for innovation in Nofima

Nofima has a significant role both in collecting, structuring and processing data used in research projects and other studies. There are also initiatives to use data for innovation and idea generation. One example is the foods department of Nofima where they have created a group working on statistics and data science. The group is doing their own research focusing on digitalisation of the food industry, using big data and sensometrics to analyse consumer data and identify ideas for food production. This is a way of using big data for innovation. The SFI “digifoods” (centre for research-based innovation) has been established in 2020. They also work on how to find ideas in online communities. Expert discussion forums on the internet are found to be very useful to identify innovations – there ideas pop up a lot earlier than in other places. One example is gluten free beer, which was discussed in such a forum several years before such beer came out on the market. Another example, also with beer, was to let consumers give feedback on the product when released and use that feedback to change the recipe accordingly.

7.2 Domains of relevance for this case

7.2.1 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

Collaboration with the universities

Nofima is part of a larger ecosystem consisting of both universities and industry and considers itself as having a role in bridging the gap between industry and academia. There is collaboration with universities in almost every project Nofima runs and the universities they collaborate with more often are the Norwegian University of Life Sciences in Ås, the Norwegian University of Science and Technology in Trondheim, the University of Stavanger, UiT the Arctic University of Norway in Tromsø and the University of South-Eastern Norway. Many of Nofima's staff also teach at universities occasionally and they often use master students and PhD students in the projects as well.

7.2.2 Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use

Industry Collaboration

Nofima collaborates with industry both through contract research, RCN funded centres for research-based innovation (SFI in Norwegian) and other research projects such as IPN (innovation project in the industry), KSP (competency and collaboration project) and EU projects with the goal to deliver research and solutions that help strengthen the

competitiveness, innovation pace and profitability of their customers. Nofima has quite an applied orientation, and the ambition is that all the projects should contribute to solving real problems in society. Nofima therefore includes industrial actors already when designing and launching projects.

The customers of Nofima come from many different sectors such as the aquaculture industry, the fishing industry, the land and sea-based food industry, the feed and ingredient industry, the pharmaceutical industry and public administration. On the question whether the food industry, which is one of their major collaboration partners and customers, is open to new ideas, the answer is that the culture is generally very traditional, in particular among the large companies. They are usually "sitting on the fence", looking at what is happening in Europe before they make changes themselves. The small producers are more agile and adoptive whereas the large companies are less open to disruptive approaches.

Ideas for new projects are generated both ways; sometimes the industry comes to Nofima, and sometimes Nofima goes to the industry. Nofima has strategic agreements with some companies, where they exchange information and ideas about future challenges and how to adapt research and address research towards relevant issues. If Nofima wants new ideas, new ideas are invited from stakeholders from everywhere, different for different projects. Nofima also organises focussed events for specific sectors where certain topics are discussed and knowledge is shared. These events are very popular and attract a lot of participants. And they do ideation workshops. One example project is "matfloken", an open innovation project where Nofima participated as knowledge partner. In this project the participants came up with some 15 commercial concepts together with industry, which were then developed, and some are now being further tested for realisation.

Collaboration through business clusters and networks

Nofima is active in many of the existing business clusters such as the NCE Aqua Tech Cluster, NCE Blue Legasea, NCE Heidner Biocluster, NCE Seafood Innovation, Circular Packaging Cluster, Cod Cluster and Stiiim Aqua Cluster and collaborates with several other business networks such as Biotech North, Food for Life, sustainability food network, Fremtidsmat, etc. The purpose of being part of all these networks is not directly to do research but to have contact with industry. Nofima is responsible for the local food network (kompetansenettverk lokalmat in Norwegian) and ecological food program (økologiprogrammet in Norwegian) which are competency offers (courses, company visits, workshops, problem solving) for smaller producers.

Innovation collaborations through centres for research-based innovation (SFIs)

Nofima has experience from innovation, or user-oriented research and is partner in several SFIs:

- CtrlAQUA, which focuses on the development of closed-containment aquaculture concepts where the salmon is separated from the outside environment. Such systems will improve the control of the production process and thus both reduce problems associated with mortality and sea lice and reduce the production time for farmed salmon. The project is addressing a great market need and both Mowi ASA, Grieg Seafood ASA, Lerøy Seafood Group AS, Cermaq Norway AS, Bremnes Seashore AS and Nekton are industry partners in the consortium.
- DigiFoods, which focuses on developing smart sensor solutions for food quality assessment directly in the processing lines to allow for process optimisation throughout the food value chains and make the food industry more efficient and sustainable. DigiFoods will combine applied and basic research to generate new basic knowledge, evaluate prototype

solutions, and create results for innovation. The centre also aims to increase digital competence in Norway through the education of masters and PhD candidates.

The project is organised as a multi-disciplinary team comprising food companies, technology providers and research institutions. The industrial partners will participate in all research tasks, committing essential in-kind contributions to the project. Industrial partners are Tine, Nortura, Prediktor Instruments AS, Norsk Elektro Optikk AS, Camo Analytics AS, Idletechs AS, International Business Machines AS, Norilia AS, Maritech Systems AS, RobotNorge AS, Lerøy Aurora AS, CGI Norway, Biomega Group AS, Nanoplus Nanosystems and Technologies GmbH, MarqMetrix Inc, HOFF SA, Havfisk AS, Saga Robotics, OptoPrecision GmbH, Lerøy Norway Seafoods AS and Intelec.

- SFI Harvest which aims to develop knowledge and technologies for sustainable harvesting and processing of underexploited species such as mesopelagic fish, krill and Calanus, allowing sustainable growth of Norway's biomarine industries. The project brings together pioneering shipowners, key technology providers, large producers of raw materials and feed for the aquaculture sector, stakeholders, SINTEF Ocean and other strong research groups, including AMOS (the Norwegian Centre of Excellence for Autonomous Marine Operations and Systems).

Knowledge production for a sustainable industry

The fishing industry is one of the major industries in Norway. Still, compared to other Norwegian industry, the profitability is quite low.

Within the focus area "Sustainable value creation in the seafood industry", Nofima is developing the knowledge-base about markets along the entire value chain from catch to market, that the government through Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries can utilise in its long-term strategic administration. Nofima is looking into opportunities and barriers for Norwegian seafood, both in the Norwegian and in international markets. The market research includes both consumer level and industrial customers of the Norwegian seafood industry. Academically, the market research has focused on projects that contribute to academic renewal and excellence, which thus will enable them to deliver knowledge that is needed by the governmental administration at the same time as it is relevant as useful for the industry and sector in large. Nofima therefore holds regular meetings with the Norwegian Seafood Council to discuss cooperation and ensure the relevance of the research.

Another example of research done by Nofima, which is indirectly relevant for the business development of the marine sector, is the operational survey in the fishing industry. The survey aims to analyse and describe developments and trends in the Norwegian fishing industry. The results are disseminated to and used in industry, public administration and financial and business organisations.

7.2.3 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations

Training

According to Nofima, which is an organisation that to a large extent depends on industry collaboration, there is still a lot to do within academia on culture and innovative mindset. The experience is that classical research training does not really train PhDs to collaborate with industry. However, those few PhDs who have a certain business understanding of how industry thinks and what conditions it operates within, are much better at collaborating with them. It is important to have both a skillset, toolset and mindset at hand for how to collaborate. Business and market understanding is key. End-user understanding and empathy are also key to improve innovation, in addition to some communications skills so that industry understands

what the researcher means. Visualisation skills sometimes also appear advantageous. Nofima has done some approaches to enhance the communication. There are examples from one huge EU-project where a lot of methods and perspectives were combined, for instance a session which brought all the terminology to the table and investigated what it meant to the different partners. In the end a sort of dictionary was created, or common language, with a joint understanding of what it meant. The experience was that it had to be simplified quite a bit, in particular the "innovation language", then the understanding increased among the partners of why they at all did some things, like some research. A better team-feeling and increased belonging were also among the outcomes. Nofima observes a higher focus on impact, consumer and industry needs and better collaboration but these are difficult to measure quantitatively (Ref: Gonera, A. and Pabst, R., 2019. The use of design thinking in transdisciplinary research and innovation consortia: challenges, enablers, and benefits. *Journal of Innovation Management*, 7(3), pp.96-122.).

Incentives

Nofima has no specific incentives to make the researchers interested in translational research or to stimulate innovation. In fact, the opinion is that more should be done with respect to this; there are not enough, or not good enough, incentives for innovation. The biggest incentive is to be able to acquire projects and for that purpose, an innovative or translational approach may be required. However, once the project funding is granted, then there occasionally is less interest in what happens afterwards with regards to achieving real impact. There are no salary incentives or such, and it is all about individuals; if someone is interested and likes to work with innovation then it might happen. However, it should be noted that Nofima does not run many pure internal projects, neither basic research or innovation, and the projects done together with industry are by default applied projects in one or the other way with the aim to solve a problem or achieve value creation / innovation.

Industry internship as a tool to increase industry-orientation

As an initiative to improve the general industrial understanding among the researchers working within the institute and to become more industry-oriented Nofima has created an industry internship programme. The programme, which allows researchers to go and stay at a company between one and three months, is very popular and offered to both senior and young scientists.

7.2.4 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

Tech transfer and IP

Innovation in Nofima shall always be founded in the research going on in the institute and contribute in changing businesses towards sustainable value creation. Therefore, the concept of innovation and commercialisation in Nofima encompasses several activities with the purpose to create completely new or improved products, services, business models and way of work. Innovation also includes Nofima's contributions in implementation of new technologies and development of new production and processes, as well as improvement and modernisation of public regulatory framework.

Nofima will collaborate with business and industry based on insight with the goal of developing new, relevant, research-based solutions that are implemented/commercialized and thereby contribute to the renewal in society. Nofima actively seek to protect intellectual property either through confidentiality or patents and strengthen the organisation's innovation capabilities. As a result, Nofima will actively develop ideas with commercial potential through structured processes for evaluation, development and realization. Nofima handles IP and Tech Transfer processes in a mix of in-house competence and resources, together with collaboration with

several Tech Transfer Offices, such as Validé in Stavanger, VIS in Bergen, Norinnova in Tromsø and both Ard Innovation and Kjeller Innovation in the region of Oslo.

Design thinking as a tool for innovation and translation

Nofima is working consciously with developing translation in the research. The institute works internally with strategic issues and try to combine different sciences and disciplines, such as for example innovation science and food technology, to develop collaboration platforms and purposely look for collaboration opportunities and seek transdisciplinary angles.

The food section of Nofima has over the last five years started to actively incorporate design-thinking methods in their research projects. This helps identifying many more ideas to work with, both research ideas and applications. The design-thinking methods are usually applied during the projects together with all the involved stakeholders, but they could ideally be used also in a pre-application process to come up with new ideas for new projects. So far, Nofima has not been trying that very much but would like to in the future.

The process for how Nofima uses design-thinking is different for different projects. The innovation research group in Nofima has a toolkit of methods, but since every project is different, the existing tools and their applications must be adapted to the individual project. There is normally a rough idea of how to do it, but then the team must have a flexible and iterative attitude to the research and reflect on it along the way. Sometimes they even experiment with new tools in the projects. Design-thinking is an iterative and reflective process in a way that is different from what is normally done in research, and according to Nofima, they have learned a lot by experimenting. The process is not “carved in stone” – sometimes they succeed and sometimes they do it less well – but all in all, the perception is that applying design-thinking is a really successful way of running the projects. And the perceived higher success rate is believed to be due to better collaboration and higher chance for implementation of the project in the market or the partner organisation; the work seems to increase the trust between industry and research. However, it is impossible to say anything about causality; the success is difficult to measure and Nofima has no figures to prove it. And Nofima is also very clear about that still, after five years, they find themselves on a learning curve.

Applying these kinds of new methods in a research environment like in Nofima is of course not straightforward. Most researchers wish to stay in the lab and not do so much of outreach and innovation, and they have to be pushed a bit. Nofima believes this is a bit of a new role in the research world – translating information and such – and it is a process to change that mindset. They do sometimes meet resistance, but the experience is that, in general, they manage to turn the researchers around when they start to see that they get better projects through this approach.

However, it requires dedication to succeed. Nofima has a dedicated team, a group of five-six people, facilitating these activities. The team members work as innovation catalysts, or translational developers, helping to translate information into something useful or new concepts. They all have a scientific background, for instance within food chemistry, in addition to industry competence. The combination is important for the credibility. The team also hires external designers and use them in the projects as full project members. That is, as a rule, already in the plan when applying for project funding and included in the project budget, together with all kinds of innovation activities.

Research infrastructure and facilities

Nofima has several laboratories and pilot plants, which they use in their own research. The facilities are also available for industry to carry out experiments and to test production methods.

BioLab

BioLab is Nofima's accredited (ISO17025) contract and research laboratory that offers analytical services in chemistry, microbiology and physical measurements. BioLab has cutting-edge expertise in marine and vegetable raw materials and products for animal and aquaculture feed as well as human use. The lab also has expertise in process and product development, and therefore offers extra support and product-specific knowledge, not normally available from commercial analysis labs.

BioLab carries out approximately 50,000 analyses each year for Norwegian and overseas enterprises. It also runs various projects, such as the development of new methods of analysis, quality documentation in chemistry and microbiology, and help in the interpretation of regulations. BioLab guarantee that all contracts are handled confidentially.

Tromsø Aquaculture Research Station

The Tromsø Aquaculture Research Station (Havbruksstasjonen i Tromsø) is a modern research facility for experimental studies of marine fish, freshwater fish, molluscs, crustaceans and other aquatic organisms. It is run as a private company owned by UiT the Norwegian Arctic University and Nofima AS with equal ownership interests. Property and buildings are owned by Statsbygg and rented by the Ministry of Trade and Industry with the Aquaculture Station as user. The station has three different research facilities: the Fish Health Laboratory, land-based facilities and marine facilities. In addition, the Aquaculture Station operates Nofima's Centre for Marine Aquaculture located at Kvaløya outside Tromsø. The latter part of the operations is financed in its entirety through the Cod Breeding Programme.

The research facilities of the Aquaculture Station are open for both academic and industrial users. Researchers and students from Nofima and UiT make up the majority of the users, but there are also researchers from other research and educational environments. Entrepreneurs are also given access to the facilities, either directly or through collaborations with the universities or research institutes. The Aquaculture Station is an important tool for Nofima's industry-oriented research activities. The research going on at the station contributes to building knowledge and competitiveness in the seafood industry, focusing on areas such new species for farming, production of sterile farmed fish, animal welfare in aquaculture, production of robust fish with good resistance to disease, testing of fish vaccines, catch-based aquaculture (storage, feeding and transport of live fish and shellfish), and improved quality of commercial fish catches.

Research Station for Sustainable Aquaculture

The research station for sustainable aquaculture is a land-based research station located at Sunndalsøra in central Norway, at the heart of Norwegian salmon production. At this station Nofima can carry out biological and technological experiments along the complete aquaculture value chain. The station has research facilities for nutrition, formulated feeds, physiology, breeding, recirculation, radiography and metabolism studies, in addition to its own laboratory. Many tools for particular problems have been developed at the station during the past 40 years and more.

The Nofima Centre for Recirculation in Aquaculture (NCRA) is also located at the research station. This centre was built in 2010 and is suitable for testing technology and studying farmed fish in the aquaculture systems of the future, including closed systems.

Research is currently carried out in six halls with a total floor area of 6,500 m². The centre has 22 biocontainment departments with just over 1,000 tanks, and 600 hatcheries of various sizes. The main areas of research at the station concentrate on salmon, and it is licensed to work also

with trout, halibut, cod, wrasse and lumpfish. The water temperature is controlled with heat pumps, exchangers, coolers and district heating.

The research station was built in 1971 and was the first aquaculture research station in Norway. Today, approximately 50 Nofima employees work there.

Biotep

Biotep is a national facility for marine bioprocessing located close to the laboratories and scale-up hall at the Nofima headquarters in Tromsø. Through Biotep, Nofima can offer extensive experience in the development and scale-up of bioprocessing methods and has all necessary equipment for bioprocessing a large variety of biomass. Biotep is like a flexible mini-factory where high-tech companies can test and optimise their processes to extract all desired components from marine- and plant-based biomass. Each type of biomass requires its own optimised process in order to extract the desired components. Components produced are typically fish-, bone-, shell meal, purified oils, protein concentrate, small molecular components, bioactive peptides and ash. Optimisation is done on a lab scale and scaled up through a step-wise process to yield small industrial scale. Companies can choose to perform test productions based on their own processes and technology or they can collaborate with Nofima to develop the processes and technology they need. The facility also offers companies to test their production on a larger scale without the risk of large investments. From the test production, a cost estimate can be made and a product prototype can be developed and tested in the market. Market and consumer analysis and product evaluation can be offered as well if needed. Smaller companies can rent the facility to perform periodical or regular production. The facility is very important for business development in the field and it is unique in an international context.

In addition to commercial use, the facility is intended for use in research and for educational purposes.

Food Pilot Plant Norway

The Food Pilot Plant Norway offers first-class facilities for research, education and product development of food and raw materials. Nofima, in collaboration with the Norwegian University of Life Sciences, is home to Norway's largest food research centre. Food Pilot Plant Norway has a number of research pilot plants where students, scientists and businesses can test new technologies, packaging solutions and combinations of raw materials, among other things. We welcome both food manufacturers and other clients to use our facilities. The following pilot plants are located at Nofima: Bakery, Meat Pilot Plant, Packing Pilot Plant, Pathogen Pilot Plant, Vegetable Pilot Plant, Fish Pilot Plant. The following pilot plants are located at NMBU: Biorefinery, Brewery, Dairy, Fish slaughtering plant. These pilot plants are a venue for research, innovation, product development, courses, networks and teaching. Along with Nofima's professional advisors, scientists and engineers, they serve as a broad and unique platform that enable Nofima to offer tailor-made solutions to food producers at every stage of the value chain as required.

7.2.5 Domain 7 – RRI

RRI is not a distant term in Nofima; in fact, the institute has several projects that focus on RRI. There is one example of a CRISPR project where citizens are involved with the purpose to understand their attitudes towards the technology, their risk perception, and listen to their concerns and ideas. Another example is a project where they work with laboratory meat and where the consumers view and ideas on that is considered carefully.

However, the perception in Nofima is that RRI is a quite diffuse terminology and some have not really understood what it means. In particular the industrial partners do not have a clear idea of the concept. Nofima has not yet found a systematic approach to RRI itself either, but the use of RRI is more prevalent in projects focusing on new applications. There Nofima has a role both as innovation and consumer scientists and are cocreating with the consumers. And since consumers have different ideas than researchers, RRI can in a way facilitate innovation.

7.3 Conclusions

Nofima works much closer to market than most of DLN's work. Nonetheless, the following lessons emerge, on which DLN could usefully reflect.

- Deliberate focus on digitalisation has demonstrated its importance and usefulness in food, fish and agriculture
- Nofima has a very strong demand-side focus, using networks, ecosystem participation, technical services and contract research to enhance its understanding of needs, at the same time as effectively marketing itself to current and potential clients
- Industry internships for researchers offer learning to the interns which they do not get from the PhD training but which is necessary for successful industry collaboration
- Design thinking tools and methods can be very useful in both applied and fundamental research because it brings the needs and the user side in focus and fosters a collaborative environment.
- Nofima has a special team of 5/6 people, in addition to a number of hired designers, facilitating innovation and design thinking in the research projects. This is not only effective in its own right but helps build a stronger innovation culture into the institute, demonstrating that increased user relevance leads to selling more projects and achieving better results

8 Sustainable Aquaculture Innovation Centre (SAIC)

8.1 Introduction

This case is about the Sustainable Aquaculture Innovation Centre (SAIC)⁸⁴ – a Scottish innovation centre for aquaculture. SAIC operates as an autonomous unit within the University of Stirling and receives public sector funding grants from the Scottish Funding Council (SFC), Scottish Enterprise (SE) and Highlands and Islands Enterprise (HIE), as part of a national Innovation Centre Programme (ICP). SAIC aims to facilitate collaborations between academia and industry to *drive commercial success and economic growth, with long-term success measured in terms of aquaculture's contribution to Scotland's economy and reputation*⁸⁵.

The case covers the following topics (domains) of relevance for Digital Life Norway (DLN). Domain 2) Funding from research to venture capital; domain 3) Operating within innovation ecosystems; domain 4) Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use; domain 5) Innovation culture and practices in the universities; domain 6) University innovation support and commercialization systems; domain 7) Responsible research and innovation (RRI).

In short, SAIC is an example of an R&I organisation that promotes industry and academia collaborations by funding research projects (domains 2 and 4); acts as a hub for aquaculture issues within the wider RD&I context (domain 3), supports education, skills development and skills provision (domains 4 and 5); promotes an innovation culture amongst researchers and the wider sector (domain 4, 5 and 6); provides innovation support and tools to handle Intellectual property (IP) rights in collaborative projects (domain 6); promotes a sustainable aquaculture industry (domain 7).

8.2 Background

SAIC was launched in 2014 as one of eight Scottish innovation centres within the ICP – a programme set up by SFC, SE and HIE to support transformational collaboration between Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and businesses within Scottish key sectors.

The overarching aim of the ICP, which SAIC contributes to, is to increase the pace of innovation and entrepreneurship across Scotland's key economic sectors, create jobs and grow the Scottish economy. The ICP's main objectives are listed underneath.

- To offer **collaborative knowledge exchange and research** activities to help solve industry defined problems and co-create innovative opportunities for growth
- To **enhance two-way knowledge exchange** between universities, industry, and others towards realising tangible benefits for businesses while also stimulating and challenging the Scottish research base
- To **provide an environment that supports the development** of the next generation of business innovators, academics and entrepreneurs in Scotland and a culture change towards greater and more effective university/industry collaboration

⁸⁴ Formerly named the Scottish Aquaculture Innovation Centre (SAIC), the centre changed its name 2021.

⁸⁵ EKOS Limited, 2016, 'Business Engagement and Economic Impact Evaluation of the Innovation Centres Programme', Final Report to the Scottish Funding Council 9th September 2016, http://www.sfc.ac.uk/web/FILES/InnovationCentres/Innovation_Centres_Programme_-_Final_Report_to_SFC_-_9_September_2016.pdf [accessed 2021-03-15].

- To **simplify the innovation landscape** in Scotland through creating conduits to the university knowledge and expertise for all businesses in Scotland and being complementary to and exploit existing initiatives

The programme's initial phase ran between 2014–2019 and the second phase, now in operation, is planned to run between 2019 and 2024. SAIC was awarded the second phase of funding based on reviews on programme level as well as on centre level. The main take away from them was that the centre had become well established as a key networking and funding hub for the aquaculture industry, academia, and relevant stakeholders.⁸⁶

SAIC's focus is the aquaculture sector, its key issues, and ambitions for sustainable growth in terms of production values, capacity, export, revenue, and job creation. SAIC aims to *drive commercial success and economic growth, with long-term success measured in terms of aquaculture's contribution to Scotland's economy and reputation*. With all of this in mind, the centre supports innovation across all aspects of the aquaculture supply chain and covers a wide range of topics. Particular areas of interest for research funding include finfish and shellfish health and welfare; sustainable feed, nutrition, breeding and stock improvement; environmental capacity assessment and modelling; and the application of engineering, automation, sensors and big data solutions. Instead of doing a large number of things 'well enough', the centre focuses on doing a small number of things very well.

During phase one, SAIC was very successful in attracting the bigger aquaculture producers as project partners, whereas SAIC's beneficiaries in phase two also include a stronger focus on SMEs and the wider aquaculture supply chain, whilst also retaining strong customer relationships with existing industrial partners. This shift in focus was primarily made to ensure that the benefit of innovation would be as inclusive as possible – targeting rural areas and stimulating job creation in rural regions. At the same time, SAIC would be able to build on Scottish aquaculture's existing foundations and establish a low-carbon, hi-tech, data-rich, and cutting-edge sector that is led by pioneering research aligned with industry need.⁸⁷

The centre adopts the triple helix model of innovation by connecting the industry with academia and supporting collaboration amongst its 204 member organisations. To instigate and accelerate commercially relevant solutions that address aquaculture's pressing issues, the centre works with a wide variety of researchers and companies. On this behalf, the centre's member consortium comprises 176 company members, ranging from SMEs to multinationals and present at all points along the aquaculture supply chain, from hatcheries to retailers; 23 HEIs, with researchers from different career stages and research environments; five stakeholder organisations (public sector organisations and non-governmental organisations). There are a number of international members of the SAIC consortium too.⁸⁸

At the launch, the SFC invested £11.2m in SAIC for its first phase of operation, the budget for the second phase was £10m. The new budget was provided to SAIC to *drive innovation, nurture*

⁸⁶ Scotland's Innovation Centres, Chaired by Professor Graeme Reid, 2016, 'Independent Review of the Innovation Centres Programme', http://www.sfc.ac.uk/web/FILES/InnovationCentres/Independent_Review_of_Innovation_Centres_Programme_-_29_September_2016.pdf, SFC, 2019a, 'Innovation Centre Programme - Phase 2', SFC/19/43 Agenda item 9, 25 June 2019, http://www.sfc.ac.uk/web/FILES/councilpapers_25062019/SFC19_43_Innovation_Centre_Programme_-_Phase_2.pdf, SFC, 2019b, 'New £10m investment in aquaculture' <http://www.sfc.ac.uk/news/2019/news-77675.aspx> [accessed 2021-03-15].

⁸⁷ SFC, 2019b, 'New £10m investment in aquaculture', SFC, 2019a, 'Innovation Centre Programme - Phase 2'.

⁸⁸ SAIC, SAIC Consortium, <https://www.sustainableaquaculture.com/about-saic/saic-consortium/> [accessed 2021-03-15], Innovation Centres, 'SAIC (Sustainable Aquaculture Innovation Centre)', <https://www.innovationcentres.scot/innovation-centres/saic/> [accessed 2021-03-15].

innovation, and share innovation. Three tasks which became SAIC's three strands of activity under which all activities are aligned.⁸⁹

i) **Drive innovation.** The centre drives innovation primarily by funding solution-oriented research projects, which bring together multiple partners from industry and academia, from across the UK, to collaborate on the sector's key issues; operationalised by three Priority Innovation Actions (PIAs):

- PIA 1) Addressing environmental and health challenges, particularly sea lice and gill disease, and developing feeds that optimise fish health and nutrition⁹⁰
- PIA 2) Unlocking additional capacity in Scottish aquaculture
- PIA 3) Shellfish and other non-fish species

By facilitating and funding research projects on Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) 4–7, the centre is designed to fill a gap in research funding, and activities, between basic research (TRLs 1–3) and company R&D projects (TRLs 8–9).

Additionally, the centre contributes to the attraction of extra funding from UK and the EU into Scottish aquaculture, by the provision of support, guidance, and financial co-contributions.

ii) **Nurture innovation.** SAIC nurtures innovation by developing aquaculture skills and talent across Scotland through focussed skills development initiatives – from apprenticeships to MSc and PhD courses and programmes, where researchers can work on company issues. Many of these programmes offer training to individuals working in the sector, and thus create a sector-wide cohort of people from both a commercial and an academic background trained in e.g., innovation thinking, or management and leadership skills

iii) **Share innovation.** Sharing the insights and knowledge gleaned with the wider sector, highlighting the benefits of aquaculture for the Scottish, UK and world economies are key in terms of sharing innovation. Main activities include organising workshops and conferences, as well as disseminating information in various ways.

Figure 6 The centre's governance.

Source: SAIC's website, 2021-03-11.

Figure 6 illustrates the centre's governance. To carry out activities and to govern the centre, SAIC has a Board, the SAIC Team, and the SAIC Independent Scientific Panel (SISP).

All matters of strategy and operation are under the control of the Board, which consist of members from the industry as well as from academia. In terms of strategy, the Board is, for instance, in charge of the formulation of SAIC's PIAs; the original PIAs were identified during a workshop with about 80 industry representatives at the onset of the centre; those have

⁸⁹ EKOS Limited, 2016, 'Business Engagement and Economic Impact Evaluation of the Innovation Centres Programme', SFC, 2019a, 'Innovation Centre Programme - Phase 2'.

⁹⁰ See for example some case studies here: <https://www.sustainableaquaculture.com/projects/health-and-welfare/details/scaling-up-the-use-of-cleaner-fish/>, [accessed 2021-03-31].

subsequently been reviewed, refined, and updated through extensive consultation with the whole consortium membership, to ensure that SAIC's focus continues to reflect industry needs and expectations.

The SAIC Team⁹¹ takes care of day-to-day business and consortium-related activities. The Team's primary tasks are to assist members with initiating research projects, finding project partners and applying for additional funding (see section 8.3.1); managing collaborations within the member consortium and with other R&I organisations (see sections 8.3.2, 8.3.3, 8.3.5) coordinating skills development programmes (see section 8.3.3).⁹² and disseminating the outputs and results of all of those activities.

The SISP consists of an international panel of people not active in the Scottish research community but with scientific credibility and a good commercial understanding or experience. The panel's primary purpose is to provide independent and informed scientific opinion on SAIC sponsored projects to the SAIC Team as well as the Board (see section 8.3.1). The panel is also expected to engage in offering insights and research intelligence to ensure that SAIC is aware of relevant work in other scientific fields or parts of the world through 'horizon scanning'.

The fact that SAIC's Board includes members from the industry is essential for the success of its core business. This ensures that SAIC's operations are aligned with industry needs and that SAIC, from the outset, has managed to deliver value back to its partners. Ultimately, this way of organising has been a key success factor as it has increased the centre's ability to keep and attract companies in membership of its consortium.

SAIC's academic base is, however, crucial for its operations. Given that the fact the centre is supposed to fill a gap in research funding and activities – the insights and guidance provided by the SISP and the academic Board members become vital in this regard. Academic expertise is essential to underpin high quality, applied research developed jointly with industry and research partners.

8.3 Domains of relevance for this case

8.3.1 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital

The centre funds collaboration projects between TRL 4–7. Such projects must be aligned with SAIC's PIAs, be innovative in their approach or lead to innovative solutions that will help to support the Scottish aquaculture sector and associated supply chains. Hence, the centre also looks for projects with multiple industrial users. SAIC, furthermore, defines innovation as something novel that creates measurable value – commercial, economic, social, or public – for the sector and the Scottish economy.⁹³

During SAIC's first five years, a majority of the funded collaborative projects involved more than one industry partner. In many cases there were multiple industry partners, and in around half of the projects, more than one university or research institution was involved. The involvement of several companies and HEIs has helped SAIC to increase the spread of knowledge and access

⁹¹ The team consists of the Chief Executive Officer, Aquaculture Innovation Managers, the Head of Skills and Talent, Finance Officers and marketing and communications staff.

⁹² SAIC, 2020a, 'Terms of Reference – SAIC Governing Board', https://www.sustainableaquaculture.com/media/1992/saic_governing_board_for_2020.pdf, SAIC, 'SAIC Independent Scientific Panel (SISP)', https://www.sustainableaquaculture.com/media/1773/saic_sisp_termsofreference.pdf.

⁹³ SAIC, 'Funding', <https://www.scottishaquaculture.com/funding/> [accessed 2021-03-15].

to know-how across the aquaculture sector. In light of this, SAIC continues to encourage projects of this kind.

Organisations that may apply for funding are:

- Any company that is active within Scottish aquaculture or a related sector (including those headquartered overseas but have operations in Scotland), and is willing to contribute resources to the project – cash, in-kind or a combination of both
- Any recognised Scottish HEI or research institute if they apply in collaboration with an industry partner

Projects are usually initiated in one of the following ways. Either the academic party has an idea that it presents to a company, after which they apply together – or a company discovers a need for a research project that requires input from an academic party, after which it either reaches out directly to an academic partner or to SAIC. If the company reaches out to SAIC, the SAIC Team helps it to find researchers with the right expertise for the project. In order to encourage project applications that align with SAIC's funding priority innovation areas, the SAIC Team proactively approaches organisations directly and asks them to bring forward ideas for research projects, or to join emerging consortia to work together on joint projects. SAIC also encourages the development of projects that address industry-wide challenges and encourages companies or academics that have research ideas that could bring value for the whole aquaculture sector to develop those in consultation with the SAIC Team.

To trigger collaboration and proposals, the centre has convened 'deep-dive' conferences and workshops within strategic thematic areas and other sectors, such as food, data or IoT. During said 'deep-dive' conferences international and local experts both from academia and the industry are gathered for one day to discuss certain aquaculture topics. For example, after the centre arranged a 'deep-dive' conference on gill disease, which gathered more than 80 people, this triggered 5–6 new proposals within a single theme.

Generally, SAIC offers a funding contribution to the total project cost. The expectation is that the industry contribution will be the largest component of all funded projects. SAIC funds the academic costs of joint projects. Industry partners must demonstrate that they are able to contribute in cash, in-kind or both. HEIs or research institutes must also contribute, although they are expected to input 20 per cent of their costs, with SAIC awarding funding at the rate of 80 per cent of the academic full economic costing.

SAIC has two main types of in-house funding calls, Rapid Response Funding Calls and Timed Funding Calls:

Rapid Response Funding Calls

These calls are live throughout the year for smaller, shorter-duration collaboration projects. The assessment process is divided into two steps. Firstly, the SISPs assess the application primarily based on its scientific merits. Secondly, the Team and the CEO review the project's commercial potential. After this process, a decision will be made on projects costing under £100,000 by the CEO. Any projects seeking more than £50,000 SAIC funding require to be approved by the Board. Projects are judged on scientific excellence, industry need and forecasted economic impact.

The extent of the commercial benefit of projects has become more important over time, and SAIC has evolved its project assessment process to involve a commercial review stage, where forecast economic impacts are required, as is a robust case for the business need for the proposed innovation. This means that all projects meet robust scientific and commercial standards before being funded.

To be eligible for funding, applications must meet the following criteria:

- Have at least one industry partner, with a registered office in Scotland
- Involve at least one Scottish HEI
- Have a maximum grant request of £50,000
- Be completed within 12 months
- Fall within one of SAIC's PIAs

SAIC also aims to secure a target of 1.5:1 of private sector funding to match funded projects

Timed Funding Calls

These calls are launched once or twice a year for bigger industry-led collaborative projects. Previously, the centre only had continuous calls but learned that calls with deadlines make it easier to pick the most competitive cases, because via continuous uptake SAIC has nothing to compare the cases with. Consequently, the Timed Funding Calls were created.

The application process is divided into two steps. Firstly, applicants submit a written Expression of Interest (EoI), using a downloadable form from SAIC's website. SAIC's technical staff and SISP reviews the EoI by checking if the proposal is in line with SAIC's priority funding criteria. If this is the case, they will advise the applicants to submit a full application. If it is not the case, SAIC refers the applicants to other organisations where they might receive funding instead or offer other feedback to enable a stronger proposal to be developed.

Secondly, once the full application has been submitted, the SISP evaluates it, thoroughly, on behalf of its scientific merits. Then, a joint SISP and industry panel evaluates it based on commercial potential and industrial need. Following this procedure, a ranked list of proposed projects is taken to the main Board, where decisions will be made. Once a project is approved for funding, SAIC participates in a 'project kick-off' meeting with all the collaborators and stays in touch throughout the duration of the project, so that the project will have a greater chance to achieve its objectives. There is active monitoring and support of projects to enable successful outcomes for all.

To be eligible, applications must meet the following criteria:

- Contribute towards at least one of SAIC's PIAs
- Have at least one industry partner (one of them must be the lead partner)
- Have at least one Scottish research partner
 - Identify and address a commercial need
- Deliver an economic benefit

Brokerage of external funding

In addition to the funding calls described above, the centre keeps track of funding opportunities UK and EU-wide and advertises other organisation's calls (of relevance to SAIC's members). Further, SAIC supports organisations to leverage funding by providing guidance about how to apply for additional funding from other organisations in the UK or other parts of Europe, and it may offer financial contributions as co-funding of collaborative projects seeking funding from outside Scotland.

Continuous development

SAIC is a learning organisation, constantly reviewing its processes to tweak them, thus making them more fit for purpose. In order to demonstrate the longer term economic and social

benefits of previously funded projects, SAIC is currently reviewing all projects from the first five years, to be able to explain their economic and social value and to learn what to do better in the future. In this exercise, SAIC has brought in consultants who are assessing the economic impact with industry and across the university research base.

8.3.2 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

The Scottish RD&I landscape for aquaculture is diverse and not aligned under a single authority or stakeholder group. It includes the Marine Alliance for Science and Technology for Scotland; academic institutions; producer RD&I – including international knowledge transfer; supplier RD&I and the Scottish Government, as well as SAIC.⁹⁴

SAIC was established to bring everyone with an interest in aquaculture together for the good of the Scottish economy (in line with the ICP's fourth objective, see section 8.2).

The idea was that the centre would utilise the strength of the Scottish research base and draw on those resources to address the industry's key issues and opportunities, by acting as a fulcrum for industry, academia, and the public sector.⁹⁵ In this regard, the centre has made an impact in the sense that it has, indeed, facilitated closer relationships amongst research-performing organisations, the industry, and relevant parts of the state. It does so through the memberships/consortium activities and by acting as a hub for aquaculture issues (collaborating with other R&I organisations; gathering the industry; influencing policymakers; spreading knowledge regarding aquaculture issues to the wider public).⁹⁶

Concerning membership/consortium activities, SAIC acts as an intermediary by connecting industry members with members from academia through funding collaboration projects; arranging workshops and conferences; and, by referring consortium members either to other members (i.e. initiating new collaborations) or to other funding bodies (i.e. supporting innovation by the promotion of other funding opportunities) (see sections 8.3.1 and 8.3.3).

Some of SAIC's activities with other R&I organisations are with the fellow innovation centres within the ICP. From the beginning, the funders encouraged dialogue and collaboration amongst the centre directors through quarterly meetings to review progress and activities to bring about the sharing of learning and good practice amongst them. Now, during the pandemic, the centre directors meet online weekly to share experiences and team up on joint initiatives or projects which are of national importance. Because the centres are working in parallel, they have developed a collaborative environment where people are able to learn from each other and find opportunities for synergies. This is a major strength of the innovation centre model as a whole.

SAIC has teamed up with fellow innovation centres, Centre for Sensor and Imaging Systems (CENSIS), the Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre, and The Data Lab on different projects and other activities, such as workshops. Underneath are two examples.

⁹⁴ Gatward I, Parker A, Billing S, Black K, et al., 2017, 'Scottish Aquaculture: a view towards 2030'. Published 2017 by the Scottish Aquaculture Innovation Centre and Highlands and Islands Enterprise, <https://www.sustainableaquaculture.com/media/1174/scottish-aquaculture-a-view-towards-2030.pdf>.

⁹⁵ SFC, 2019b, 'New £10m investment in aquaculture'.

⁹⁶ SAIC, 2017, 'Innovation and the Ripple Effect: Progress Report 2014–2017', <https://www.scottishaquaculture.com/media/1698/saic-progress-report.pdf>, SAIC, 2016, 'Charting our progress towards 2030: Annual Review 2015/16', <https://www.scottishaquaculture.com/media/1173/saicannual-review1516.pdf>.

- A Scottish consortium – comprising of marine technology provider OTAQ, the Iain Fraser Cytometry Centre at the University of Aberdeen, CENSIS and SAIC – is creating a low-cost sensor system that can automatically sample, identify, and count specific microscopic organisms using imaging analysis. By this, they are taking a significant step towards the development of an early-warning detection system for potentially dangerous plankton and algae, which could help the global aquaculture industry tackle one of the biggest challenges to fish health and wellbeing.⁹⁷
- A Scottish consortium - comprising of marine biotechnology company Ecoclean, the University of St Andrews, IBiolC and SAIC - is investigating the market, and production methods, to replace conventional surfactants produced by synthetic or petrochemical feedstocks (produced by oil, gas and chemical processing) with surfactants produced from fish oil waste. The development of this product will support and promote the process of the circular economy solution, which fits perfectly with Scotland's strategy, creating new opportunities for business growth by reducing waste, and reducing the environmental impact of the production and consumption of finfish in Scotland.
- Together with the Data Lab, SAIC offers a series of interactive sessions for business leaders in the Scottish aquaculture sector called the Data in Aquaculture Programme, which is set up to help researchers and industry representatives identify the right opportunities in terms of data usage for their organisation.⁹⁸

In terms of bringing the industry together, SAIC participates in the Aquaculture Industry Leadership Group – a national group that gathers industry leaders and relevant stakeholders. The group was established to drive the development and delivery of the Aquaculture Growth to 2030 industry strategy⁹⁹ (the industry's plan to sustainably double the sector's economic contribution from £1.8b in 2016 to £3.6b by 2030). SAIC played a key role in the development of the strategy and is currently responsible for implementing some of the strategy's recommendations (mainly recommendations on RD&I support and skills provision).¹⁰⁰

In order to influence policymakers and spread knowledge regarding the aquaculture sector and its issues to the wider public, SAIC communicates its projects, results, and vision, as well as engages in discussions with the government and other policymakers. The centre has made an impact on the national level by doing this. Until very recently, UK funders at the national level did not invest in aquaculture issues, because the majority of the high value aquaculture industry in the UK is devolved to Scotland. However, ever since the centre brought attention to the UK-wide supply chain and export income benefits the aquaculture sector brings about a shift in the policy space has occurred, with the importance of investing in aquaculture as part of precision food production has been recognised at a UK level. For instance, UK research and Innovation (UKRI) and Innovate UK have recently specifically included aquaculture into their funding calls for food, precision farming, and other innovation schemes.

⁹⁷ SAIC, 2019c, 'New Algae Detection System Could Help Aquaculture Industry Bloom' <https://www.sustainableaquaculture.com/news-events/new-algae-detection-system-could-help-aquaculture-industry-bloom/> [accessed 2021-03-15].

⁹⁸ SAIC, 2020b, 'Data in Aquaculture Programme', <https://www.scottishaquaculture.com/news-events/data-in-aquaculture-programme/> [accessed 2021-03-15].

⁹⁹ Scotland Food & Drink, 2017, 'Aquaculture Growth to 2030', https://aquaculture.scot/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/Aquaculture_Growth_2030.pdf.

¹⁰⁰ Aquaculture Industry Leadership Group, 2018, 'Aquaculture Industry Leadership Group – Governance', <https://aquaculture.scot/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Aquaculture-ILG-Governance-Text-May-2018.pdf>.

8.3.3 Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use

Within all three strands of activities: driving innovation; sharing innovation; nurturing innovation, SAIC has initiatives that contribute to forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use.

At the outset, there were only a handful of companies that were used to working closely with universities on joint research; SAIC has played a significant role in making this practice more widespread. A significant part of this was because of the project funding which SAIC offers. SAIC's knowledge exchange and networking function also bring about the conditions under which strong collaborations between companies and universities are created, because they incentivise organisations to a) engage in innovation (since they are granted funding for doing so) and to b) collaborate with the other sector whilst innovating (since this is a requirement for receiving funding). A key behind the centre's success in this area is that it always makes sure that all activities are aligned with industry needs, and thereby delivers commercial benefits and value for the industry, which in turn cements industry participation. Also, companies that are part of SAIC's member consortium may gain a first-mover advantage to the results of research to which they contribute, along with the centre's funding; this further incentivises companies to participate.

Another part of SAIC's role is to encourage researchers to participate in these types of applied research collaborations. SAIC does so by attracting additional funding into aquaculture research, supporting researchers as they bid for earlier stage research funding, and by providing early career researchers with the tools and skills needed to contribute effectively in applied research and industry collaborations. For instance, when organisations are members of SAIC's consortium, they get access to SAIC's expertise and a team of aquaculture innovation managers who support projects from start to finish, acting as coaches and disseminators of project results. Additionally, SAIC has skills development programmes dedicated to providing researchers and staff working in the industry with essential skillsets and tools to adopt an innovation mindset (see further down in this section).

In light of this, SAIC has, furthermore, been successful in the sense that it has helped the industry deal with some of its biggest challenges – which individual businesses, or even groups of companies, may not have had the resources to tackle on their own – through access to additional funding, academic expertise and a strong focus on applied research that delivers results.¹⁰¹

A further benefit of being part SAIC's consortium is that it, as part of the mission to share innovation, provides the industry with the power of knowing. Many companies enter the consortium to keep up to date with what is going on and to learn from other companies as well as academic partners. To that end, SAIC offers key account managers, for both companies and researchers, to further deepen the dialogue with its members, so that it may tailor offers and activities, even further, to fit the members' needs.

Moreover, SAIC encourages the widespread adoption of the latest best practice, for example, by organising events where organisations can learn from each other, such as the International Cleaner Fish Summit in Glasgow. SAIC has also created an arena for cross-fertilisation, the 'deep-dive' conferences on specific topics are part of this.

¹⁰¹ SFC, 2019b, 'New £10m investment in aquaculture'.

8.3.4 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the universities

The Aquaculture Innovation and Industry Engagement Programme

To steer Scotland's excellent research base toward applied research that meets genuine industry demand, SAIC has several actions targeting innovation culture and practices in the universities. SAIC has created a programme, together with Skillfluence¹⁰², specifically focusing on innovations and industry engagements. The Aquaculture Innovation and Industry Engagement Programme is a programme that brings together individuals from industry and academia on a three-month training programme providing them with the knowledge and skills to solve complex challenges of 21st-century aquaculture in close collaboration with the other sector. The programme is for anyone currently working or studying in aquaculture interested in innovation. The goal is to give participants a practical process they can start using to create and implement real solutions to current business challenges. It equips researchers with skills, such as commercial awareness, needed to engage in industry collaborations and to innovate.

Participants are expected to commit to attending six workshops with different themes. Currently, the programme is given on-line due to the Covid-19 pandemic, and this round the workshops are themed as follows:

Table 3 Course content of the Innovation and Industry Engagement Programme 2021.

Module 1: Idea Generation	Module 2: Idea Communication & Selection	Module 3: Making it Real	Module 4: The Power of Numbers	Module 5: Testing Assumptions	Module 6: Make it Happen
Learn tools, techniques and principles to immediately increase their ability to create a large volume of high-quality ideas to solve current societal or business challenges.	Learn a framework for effectively communicating new ideas in a way to gain buy-in. Learn how to pick ideas with a higher likelihood of success.	Learn tools and techniques to quickly accelerate the development of new ideas while reducing overall risk.	Understand how to use numbers in situations with high uncertainty and focus on discovery and development activity.	Learn how to engage with and gain high-quality feedback from potential users, stakeholders, and customers	Explore how to apply the principles in a structured way to get buy-in & generate results. Pitch team ideas.

Source: SAIC's website.

The programme has been successful, and there are several examples of industry-academia collaborations that have initiated post programme participation.

An important aspect that the programme, courses, and support from SAIC's aquaculture innovation managers, is to bridge any gaps in knowledge or understanding, the 'cultural divide' that may occur between those coming from an industry perspective and those coming from an academic background. SAIC therefore supports forging long-term, mutual understanding, and deeper, better links between the two sectors with a view to encouraging more collaborations to occur in future.

SAIC Aquaculture Academy

Besides driving and sharing innovation, SAIC promotes producer-user links in knowledge production and use by nurturing innovation. It does so primarily via the Aquaculture Academy

¹⁰² Skillfluence is a training company that specialises in upskilling participants to work with others outside of academia.

initiative, where SAIC has established institutional relationships with a range of Scottish universities (up from the initial two) and organisations to contribute to the development of aquaculture skills and talent across Scotland.¹⁰³

The programmes provided by SAIC through the Aquaculture Academy include:

- **The summer internship programme.** A programme originally offered by the centre in partnership with Skills Development Scotland and Developing the Young Workforce, which aims to encourage new generations into the sector by giving undergraduates an insight into the range of career opportunities available. Students spend their internship with a Scottish aquaculture business (large or small) or with SAIC.
- **The MSc initiative.** SAIC offers funded places at its partner universities to those interested in studying for an MSc in an aquaculture-related subject. The key to each funded place is that students undertake their MSc applied research project on an industry-identified issue, giving them a heightened awareness of the challenges and opportunities faced by the sector. The initiative aims to create a cohort of master students, a network, which have the practical tools, methods, and mindset to work with the industry and, down the line, commercialise their projects. Initially, SAIC had to work hard to convince the industry that a three-month master's dissertation could make a commercial difference. However, now when there are some good examples of master's projects which have made commercial impacts, the industry recognises the benefits of students gaining commercial exposure during their degrees. For instance, one student project changed the packaging of mussels in a business-to-business supply chain, and thereby cut down the distribution losses.

Within the MSc initiative, SAIC hosts a series of industry perspectives workshops throughout the academic year, where students engage with industry representatives, learn about job opportunities and make valuable connections for the future and forge ties with their peers at other universities.

- **PhD projects.** SAIC funds PhD projects which it brings in via timed calls. The centre funds up to 50 per cent per PhD, to a maximum of £45,000 over three years. Total studentship costs are expected to cover all fees and stipends, as well as associated running costs such as bench fees and consumables. The standard studentship duration is expected to be three years, or up to three and a half years where needed to accommodate industry placement activities. Projects must be conducted with an industry partner, and industry partners are expected to contribute resources to the project.

Project proposals should be set up based on industry need and must align with one of the following areas: 1. Scotland's Green Recovery; 2. The Blue economy; 3. Fish Health & Welfare; 4. Environmental Modelling. Project proposals must also include industry-related training, because participants are expected to spend a significant amount of time in an industry setting, to increase their understanding of the commercial context in which their applied research is being undertaken and, in turn, enhancing their employability.

In 2018, the centre part-funded four PhD scholarships to advance research within the sector. The four PhD positions focused on an area of research with the capacity to progress the sustainable growth of Scottish aquaculture, and the projects were conducted in collaboration with companies and research-performing organisations.

¹⁰³ SAIC, 'Aquaculture Academy', <https://www.scottishaquaculture.com/opportunities/aquaculture-academy/> [accessed 2021-03-15].

8.3.5 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

Because the innovation centre is tasked with facilitating and funding projects on TRLs 4–7, its main priority regarding innovation support and commercialisation systems is to establish conditions under which industry-academia collaborations projects can be carried out. In light of this, SAIC provides an IP Policy¹⁰⁴ to its members to protect their IP rights when participating in collaborative projects. If project partners have not reached an agreement regarding IP rights, the projects are not allowed to start.

The primary function of SAIC's IP Policy is that the IP arrangements between SAIC and its consortium partners should facilitate the achievement of SAIC's objectives. Based on this, a framework, with different arrangements depending on the type of funding, has been developed in which the IP arrangements will:

- Be flexible enough to be tailored to the different circumstances of Consortium members large and small
- Enable the development of new technology and the subsequent protection and/or exploitation of IP for the benefit of the aquaculture sector as a whole
- Not create burdensome costs for small companies and other Consortium members

To avoid doubt, SAIC has a general presumption that IP will be provided on an open-access basis or where otherwise that ownership of IP should be proportionate to the investment of each partner in SAIC collaborative projects.

The centre's innovation managers act as coaches and help researchers with their innovation projects by providing input and advice. The SAIC Team also includes experts in marketing, events and design, who have assisted project collaborators, spin-out companies, and Aquaculture Academy participants in disseminating news about their work widely. This has included support with marketing activities.

8.3.6 Domain – 7 RRI

RRI principles are incorporated in SAIC's core operations. It is established to promote a sustainable industry and fosters challenge-driven innovation. All SAIC's PIAs address environmental and social challenges. To mark the commitment to support sustainability and a green recovery from the Covid-19 pandemic, the centre changed its name to the Sustainable Aquaculture Innovation Centre February 1st, 2021. Additionally, SAIC's activities are now guided by the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

As mentioned before, (see section 8.3.2) the centre works as a hub for the aquaculture sector's issues and needs, therefore it has made sure that an innovation roadmap and sector study has been conducted, please see '**Scottish aquaculture: a view towards 2030**'¹⁰⁵. The roadmap sets out the steps to success and priorities to 2030, and ways to reduce a negative impact on the environment and to promote sustainability are included in the roadmap.

On sharing innovation, the centre has created the virtual network Women in Scottish Aquaculture (WiSA). It exists to introduce more women into aquaculture, and support those already working in the sector. The network is open for all to join and promotes that diverse and rewarding careers that are available in aquaculture. It aims to raise awareness of the opportunities for women to work in the aquaculture industry; provide a network for women to

¹⁰⁴ SAIC, 2016, 'SAIC Intellectual Property (IP) Policy', https://www.scottishaquaculture.com/media/2011/saic_ip_policy.pdf.

¹⁰⁵ Gatward I, Parker A, Billing S, Black K, et al., 2017, 'Scottish Aquaculture: a view towards 2030'.

develop their careers within the industry; and support the industry in developing the potential of women within the workplace at all levels. The network has been successful in that it has raised awareness regarding inequality issues in the workplace, including some companies amending their employment policies to take account of feedback received via this forum. WiSA has gone from strength to strength during the pandemic, and the fact that the network has transitioned to a thriving virtual community has been key in terms of overcoming the geographical isolation of some of its members.

8.4 Conclusions

SAIC's overall success factors

- SAIC focuses on its core activities and topics – it does a small number of things very well rather than attempting to do many things with a risk of poor execution.
- The centre ensures that all activities are aligned with the industry's needs so that the centre can deliver value to, attract and keep industry members. The fact that SAIC has members from the industry present in the Governing Board is a guarantee for this.
- SAIC is a learning organisation, by participating in various forums, and constantly reviewing processes to tweak them and make them more fit for purpose. This has contributed to SAIC being successful at what it does.
- SAIC has found its position within the ecosystem, as a hub for the aquaculture sector, it can thereby deliver value back to Government, its founding funders, and the sector (industry as well as academia).

Lessons and conclusions per domain

Domain 2

- For projects, SAIC requires a minimum of one company and one HEI per project but encourages more participants than one of each. This has resulted in many projects with multiple industry and academic partners. In turn, this has increased the spread of knowledge and access to know-how across the aquaculture sector.
- To trigger collaboration and proposals, SAIC convenes 'deep-dive' conferences where representatives from the industry and academia get together to discuss different aquaculture-related topics. These conferences have generated R&I project applications.
- SAIC's assessment process for the Timed Funding calls is divided into two steps. 1) An EoI, that SAIC's technical staff and SISP reviews to see if the proposal is in line with what SAIC wants to fund. 2) A full application, which the SISP and then the Board reviews on scientific merits and commercial potential. Applicants receive feedback from the reviewers throughout the application process, and support during the project's delivery so that the project will have a greater chance of success in achieving its objectives.
- SAIC has revised its project application processes to make them more fit for purpose in two ways:
 - SAIC changed the project assessment process to ensure a balanced focus on the commercial/industrial need for the project, its scientific quality, and credentials and that it would have measurable outcomes in terms of jobs and increased turnover or efficiency gains.
 - SAIC established calls with deadlines, instead of the continuous uptake it initially had, because it learned that it is easier to pick the most competitive cases when comparisons can be done.

Domain 3

- The Scottish RD&I landscape for aquaculture is diverse and not aligned under a single authority or stakeholder group, however, SAIC has established itself as a fulcrum for industry and academia by its provision of a network, funding, and skills development opportunities. A significant part of SAIC's success is that it is part of the ICP. The programme's overarching aims, and organised learning opportunities helps to guide the centre's operations and facilitates synergies, such as mutual learning, collaborations and the spread of best practices.
- Another interesting aspect is that the centre unites the aquaculture sector and advocates its issues to the public sector. Through results provided by its members, SAIC brings attention to the benefits of aquaculture, and the need for R&I investments in the sector, which, in turn, has resulted in investments in aquaculture at the national level (e.g., UKRI and Innovate UK have recently added aquaculture specifically into their funding programmes).

Domain 4

- Rather than having a few large companies cooperating with universities, SAIC has made cooperation between the industry and academia into a more widespread practice, mainly through the provision of funding. This is because organisations are incentivised to a) engage in innovation (since they are granted funding for doing so) and b) to collaborate with the other sector whilst innovating (since this is a requirement for receiving funding). The key is also to bring value back to the participants and support them during to innovation process. For this reason, SAIC's membership offers scope for first-mover advantage to companies involved in co-funding applied research projects, as the company is actively contributing to the research project.
- Additionally, SAIC's skills development programmes – offered in close collaboration with the industry as well as academia – under the Aquaculture Academy umbrella allows students and researchers to learn to collaborate with the industry early in their careers. This seems to have forged user-producer links in knowledge production.

Domain 5

- SAIC has teamed up with Skillfluence¹⁰⁶ and some other training providers to provide programmes and courses specifically focusing on innovations and industry engagements, such as the Aquaculture Innovation and Industry Engagement Programme. This way of working, i.e., teaming up with companies or universities (as presented in domain 4) is an interesting measure for fostering an innovation culture amongst academics and industry players.

Domain 6

- IP arrangements amongst parties must be agreed on before projects may commence. An interesting aspect of how SAIC handles IP is that the primary function of SAIC's IP policy is that the IP arrangements between SAIC and its consortium partners should facilitate the achievement of SAIC's objectives. Therefore, the centre handles IP on a project-by-project basis and has a general presumption that IP will be provided on an open-access basis or where otherwise that ownership of IP should be proportionate to the investment of each partner in SAIC collaborative projects.

¹⁰⁶ A training company that specialises in upskilling participating researchers to work with others outside of academia.

- To foster innovation, the centre has innovation managers who act as coaches and help researchers with their innovation projects by providing input and advice. The SAIC marketing and communications team also assist project partners in a wide range of marketing and communication activities.

Domain 7

- An interesting feature of SAIC's work to promote RRI is the virtual network WiSA. It gathers women interested in or currently working in the Scottish Aquaculture sector, raises awareness of work opportunities, and supports the industry in developing the potential of women within the workplace at all levels. The fact that the network has succeeded during lockdown by being virtual has been key in terms of overcoming geographical isolation, although the network hopes to return to face-to-face events in future.

9 SynbiCITE

9.1 Background

SynbiCITE is the UK's national centre for the industrial translation and commercialisation of synthetic biology and is an Innovation and Knowledge Centre (IKC). IKCs are a key component of the UK's approach to the commercialisation of emerging technologies through creating early-stage critical mass in an area of disruptive technology and are set up to nucleate new industries, by closing the gap between scientific research and its commercial exploitation.¹⁰⁷

SynbiCITE is based at Imperial College's White City Campus in London and is a collaboration of the UK's leading academic institutions and industrial partners, ranging from MNC's to start-ups, as well as supporting organisations. The environment for synthetic biology at Imperial College is well developed and the innovation focus of SynbiCITE is supplemented by the more academically focused Imperial College Centre for Synthetic Biology (IC-CSynB)¹⁰⁸. The environment was boosted when SynbiCITE received a grant to build the first bio foundry in the public domain, the London DNA Foundry, which provides a state-of-the-art infrastructure for DNA testing, verification, and characterisation of various genetic circuits.¹⁰⁹

The domains which are of relevance in this case study are *Domain 2: Funding from research to venture capital*, *Domain 3: Operating within innovation ecosystems*, *Domain 4: Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use*, *Domain 5: Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations*, and *Domain 7: RRI*.

In Domain 2, the case study describes how SynbiCITE provides smaller amounts of investments for companies at crucial stages for them to develop into an investable state. The case gives insights in Domain 3 because of the developed ecosystem at Imperial College surrounding synthetic biology with actors along the value-chain. Domain 4 explains how SynbiCITE's network connects users and creators of knowledge and their role in establishing standards for the sector. Domain 5 showcases SynbiCITE's two education programmes for helping entrepreneurs and how they leverage the entrepreneurial culture of Imperial College to innovate within the area of synthetic biology. Domain 7 focuses on how SynbiCITE works with responsible research and innovation (RRI).

For this case study we conducted a group interview with Paul Freemont and Richard Kitney, both Co-Directors of SynbiCITE.

9.2 Context

The environment for synthetic biology at Imperial College started with the Centre for Synthetic Biology & Innovation (CSynBi) which was established in 2009 as the first UK National Centre for synthetic biology by a grant from the UK's Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC). CSynBi enabled a core group of researchers at Imperial to develop within the area of synthetic biology which allowed them to produce publications, attract independent research funding, train PhD students and Post-docs and run an inter-faculty undergraduate teaching programme.¹¹⁰

¹⁰⁷ <https://epsrc.ukri.org/innovation/business/opportunities/impactschemes/ikcs/>

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/synthetic-biology/centre/about/>

¹⁰⁹ <http://www.synbicite.com/innovation/londondnafoundry/>

¹¹⁰ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/synthetic-biology/centre/about/>

The UK strategy for synthetic biology, originally launched with the Royal Academy of Engineering's Synthetic Biology Inquiry Report¹¹¹ from 2009 and later the Synthetic Biology Roadmap for the UK in 2012¹¹², was defined by a number of influential reports – placing synthetic biology as a key driver of the UK bioeconomy.¹¹³ The core themes of this Roadmap were Foundational science and engineering; Continuing responsible research and innovation; Developing technology for commercial use; Application and markets; International cooperation.¹¹⁴ As part of this strategy and to further strengthen the synthetic biology landscape in UK, SynbiCITE was established as a synthetic biology industrial translational centre in 2013 with a £28m commitment from EPSRC, Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC), Innovate UK and its industrial and academic partners.

The number of researchers at Imperial College with active research in synthetic biology continued to grow until 2014 when the grant supporting CSynBI ended. This called for further expansion of Imperial's synthetic biology resources and triggered the establishment of the Imperial College Centre for Synthetic Biology (IC-CSynB).¹¹⁵

In 2016 the synthetic biology environment at Imperial was boosted with the opening of the London DNA Foundry, a bio foundry located at SynbiCITE. This was the first UK synthetic biology foundry in the public domain for the industrial automation of construction and validation of biological systems. The Foundry is open to companies, start-ups, and academics and was funded by a separate grant by Research Councils UK.¹¹⁶ In 2018 the initial grant that supported SynbiCITE was renewed for a second phase of the centre.

SynbiCITE provides support in three ways: (i) by providing and channelling scientific and technical expertise; (ii) acting as a conduit for funding - particularly private sector funding; and (iii) providing business education. The practical implementation is via three hubs of activity within SynbiCITE:¹¹⁷

- The BioDesign and Applications Hub - supports design and supports and manages proof of concept and development projects. The hub works closely with industry supporting companies to get involved with synthetic biology at different levels.
- The Business and Outreach Hub - supports and manages an Investor Consortium and an industrial club, as well as providing business education and training through a four-day More Business Acumen (MBA) course, and a business growth accelerator for synthetic biology.
- The Facilities Hub - provides facilities through the London Bio Foundry and expertise for companies, including expertise in data analysis and learning, design automation protocol developments and more general project and company support.

SynbiCITE also has funding available to accelerate and enhance innovation in synthetic biology that meets the selection criteria and can demonstrate significant commercial potential. Because of the Covid-19 pandemic this funding is currently paused but would be approximately £250k annually. The criteria for selection of projects are based on technical

¹¹¹ <https://www.raeng.org.uk/publications/reports/synthetic-biology-report>

¹¹² <https://www.gov.uk/government/groups/synthetic-biology-leadership-council>

¹¹³ UK Synthetic Biology Start-up Survey, SynbiCITE, 2017

¹¹⁴ <http://www.synbicite.com/news-events/SynbiCITE-videos/creating-synthetic-biology-industry/>

¹¹⁵ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/synthetic-biology/centre/about/>

¹¹⁶ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/synthetic-biology/centre/about/>

¹¹⁷ <https://gow.epsrc.ukri.org/NGBOViewGrant.aspx?GrantRef=EP/S001859/1>

feasibility as well as the societal impact.¹¹⁸ SynbiCITE provides two innovation education programmes: Lean Launch Pad and a four-day MBA in Biotechnology. The innovation programmes have been designed to support early-stage entrepreneurial ventures and are tailored to fit the specific challenges of new businesses.¹¹⁹

SynbiCITE has 98 partner organisations: 26 academic, 46 industrial, and 26 supporting members. The supporting members include organisations such as research councils, not-for-profit organisations, consulting firms, design firms, investment companies etc.¹²⁰

SynbiCITE has since the start:¹²¹

- Supported over 50 start-up ventures ranging from speciality chemicals to mobile medical devices
- Helped entrepreneurs develop a minimum viable product and gain initial commercial traction
- De-risked the science and technology by funding fifteen proof of concept (PoC) projects and one development of prototype (DoP) project
- Supported start-ups in attracting over £5m investment from a range of public and private sources

9.3 Domains of relevance for this case

9.3.1 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital

Research and innovation funding at the pre-commercialisation stage

In SynbiCITE's first phase, the organisation provided two types of funding: Proof of Concept (PoC) and Development of Prototype (DoP). PoC-funding is provided up to £50k where further validation of the technical, market or commercial concepts are required to make them attractive for investment by investors or product development by industry. DoP-funding is provided up to £500k and is used for larger collaborative projects in partnership with companies that need to accelerate projects beyond PoC.¹²²

PoC-funding is used to provide:

- Funding for staff to undertake specific activities to accelerate the commercial opportunity
- Support for intellectual property protection, exploitation, or freedom to operate reviews
- Support for legal and professional costs including commercial business plan development and assessment of market size and reach
- Support for prototype development, manufacturing cost assessment and other key aspects required as part of validating a commercial investment decision
- Support to engage with commercial and investment partners that may have the capacity and potential to invest in a new product

¹¹⁸ <https://stip.oecd.org/stip/policy-initiatives/2019%2Fdata%2FpolicyInitiatives%2F26254>

¹¹⁹ <http://www.synbicite.com/collaboration/start-ups/>

¹²⁰ <http://www.synbicite.com/collaboration/Partners/>

¹²¹ <http://www.synbicite.com/collaboration/start-ups/>

¹²² <http://www.synbicite.com/innovation/funding-opportunities/>

If the concept of the project is proved feasible, the PIs are expected to take the project forward and develop them into DoP-projects. SynbiCITE can help those projects find the next stage of funding or recommend the projects for applying to other funding opportunities from SynbiCITE or other funders and investors.¹²³

Since the renewal of the grant supporting SynbiCITE in 2018, the investment strategy of the organisation has been refined. The new investment model is targeted towards companies at the pre-investment stage, before venture capitalists can take over the investment. The investment is usually a small amount, ranging from £5k-10k which typically allows the grantee to do some crucial due diligence or similar. This new strategy has been refined over SynbiCITE's two programme periods and the management has found that more investments of smaller sums have more impact than fewer and larger grants. The rationale behind this is that much research within synthetic biology only needs a small amount of support to de-risk the development for the technology and reach an investable state. In the first phase of SynbiCITE, the centre also organised investor breakfasts. This was an opportunity to introduce interested investors to the technology coming out of SynbiCITE and create networks for both entrepreneurs as well as the investors.¹²⁴ But since 2019 SynbiCITE has instead been running an annual industrial conference in the area of synthetic biology which incorporates sessions for and by investors.

Because of SynbiCITE's role as a national translational centre in an established ecosystem, new ideas normally come from researchers and entrepreneurs approaching SynbiCITE for support to develop their potential technology further. One important channel for ideas is the annual International Genetically Engineered Machine (iGEM) competition.¹²⁵ The participants are student teams from all over the world trying to push the boundaries of synthetic biology by tackling everyday issues facing the world. When a new idea has reached the centre, SynbiCITE sets up a workgroup to look at the idea more closely and see how the Centre can aid the PI in development.¹²⁶

9.3.2 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

Synthetic biology is a rather new interdisciplinary and application-driven field. It has been described as a disruptive technology at the heart of the so-called Bioeconomy, capable of delivering new solutions to global healthcare, agriculture, manufacturing, and environmental challenges.¹²⁷ The ecosystem for synthetic biology in UK has developed rapidly during the last decade and is now made up of seven major research centres.

Although the area has developed rapidly, many companies have not yet the needed knowledge or technical capabilities to setup problems for the researcher base to solve. Therefore, a lot of SynbiCITE's work during the first period has been focused on educating and showing the industry and the government the potential of the area. One of the strategies for this has been to let companies do pilot projects at the centre to showcase the possibilities of synthetic biology. For this to be possible, the pillar of the BioDesign and Applications hub has been crucial in allowing companies to understand how SynbiCITE and the bio foundry can fit

¹²³ <http://www.synbicite.com/innovation/funding-opportunities/investment/>

¹²⁴ Interview

¹²⁵ <https://igem.org/Competition>

¹²⁶ Interview

¹²⁷ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6692427/>

into the companies' own R&D-processes which will eventually lead to a critical mass can be built.¹²⁸

A key component in the strategy of the second phase of SynbiCITE is to work closely, but not exclusively, with three of the seven synthetic biology research centres. These are the research centres in Bristol, Edinburgh, and Manchester which are more focused on entrepreneurship than the others. In addition, SynbiCITE works with a range of smaller research centres throughout the UK. Through these partnerships, SynbiCITE will interact with and impact the industry in general, especially local SMEs as well as other academic institutions throughout UK.¹²⁹

The environment for synthetic biology at Imperial College has also become quite extensive. The more academic IC-CSynB provides strategic thinking and vision for synthetic biology whilst developing an open, inclusive, and collaborative environment for interdisciplinary research and ideas to flourish. To tackle the interdisciplinary nature of the research field, the centre is currently composed of 36 research groups across 6 Departments from the Faculties of Engineering, Life Sciences, and Medicine – the largest critical mass of world-class synthetic biology academics in the UK.¹³⁰ SynbiCITE on the other hand, is focused on translating novel technologies to commercial technologies by supporting companies and researchers in their development.

The academic (IC-CSynB) and industrial (SynbiCITE) activities of Imperial in synthetic biology form the basis for a pipeline for developing new solutions in synthetic biology. The pipeline includes training from undergraduate to post-doctoral researchers combined with world-leading research and a commercialisation and exploitation strategy. This is a unique proposition and environment for research, development, and application of synthetic biology to solve many of the challenges facing society, from healthcare to biomaterials to sustainable energy.

The London Biofoundry provides state-of-the-art automation of end-to-end design, construction and validation of large gene constructs. The foundry is at the core of SynbiCITE's facilities hub and is specifically designed to support the commercialisation of synthetic biology allowing SynbiCITE's partners to prototype new biologically based chemicals, drugs, and materials. The management of SynbiCITE had earlier identified the impact of bio foundries in the private sector of synthetic biology and wanted to incorporate this into the public sector. The foundry was built as the first one in the public sector and was funded by the Research Councils UK.¹³¹

The foundry has a cycle for developing new synthetic biology solutions: Design → Build → Test → Report → Learn. The capabilities of the foundry include:

- Design of DNA components and pathway assemblies to create specific genetic constructs
- Automated Assembly Platform
- Automated Characterisation Platform - designed to perform the automated high-throughput characterisation of parts, chassis or devices

¹²⁸ Interview

¹²⁹ <https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=EP%2FS001859%2F1>

¹³⁰ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/synthetic-biology/centre/about/>

¹³¹ Interview

- A suite of high-throughput analytical equipment for metadata acquisition allowing characterisation and quantification across a range of biological products
- Statistical interpretation, predictive modelling, and pattern matching
- Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS): a web-based application that allows the tracking of the workflow for any assembly

9.3.3 Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use

SynbiCITE has 98 partners: 26 academic, 46 industrial and 26 supporting members. The industrial partners range from SME's to MNC's in sectors ranging from technology to petroleum. Partnering with SynbiCITE gives access to an extensive network of synthetic biology experts, technical knowledge, and business expertise to facilitate growth and success of industry by acting as a conduit for industry, academia, and investors.¹³²

Recently SynbiCITE launched an Industry Club, which is an exclusive community of synthetic biology professionals, both in the UK and internationally. As it evolves it is intended to provide a forum through which innovative SMEs, spinouts and start-ups can connect and form a community. The purpose of the club is to enhance the existing relationships between SynbiCITE and numerous companies in the field, as well as help facilitate relationships with new partners.¹³³

SynbiCITE uses its network to help companies identify suitable partners who can solve problems using synthetic biology as well as help identify innovative solutions that are unique to the field. SynbiCITE has also facilitated and led industry-supported 'sandpits' around specific problems to uncover innovative solutions. Sandpits and problem-solution meetings provide opportunities directly to influence the direction of synthetic biology research and to connect supply and demand for knowledge. The centre is also intended to reduce the barrier to entry into synthetic biology by offering resources and facilities to explore new technologies through the London BioFoundry.¹³⁴

A pivotal part in establishing a new area in industry such as synthetic biology is to establish standards and metrology unique to the area. SynbiCITE engages with its industry partners to understand such challenges, and which of them will be encountered at the scale-up stage. Recognising the importance of common standards to interoperability and the value of shared learning experience, SynbiCITE was a prime mover in the establishment of a Global Biofoundries Alliance (GBA), launched in May 2019. The initial cohort comprised the three prime movers (Imperial, Berkeley and NUS Singapore), plus the four other UK foundries and 15 other foundries from Europe, the US, Asia and Australia. SynbiCITE also has a direct collaboration with UK's national measurement institute, NPL.¹³⁵

When SynbiCITE was setup, a lot of time and effort was spent to create collaboration agreements on IP with different partners and was done through the lawyers of Imperial College. SynbiCITE never retains ownership of IP in any project. Since SynbiCITE is the national industry translational centre with the goal of growing the UK industry for synthetic biology it has been important for the management to let companies freely run projects to generate data and knowledge without worrying about losing their IP. Therefore, SynbiCITE has developed

¹³² <http://www.synbicite.com/collaboration/Partners/>

¹³³ <http://www.synbicite.com/collaboration/industry-club/>

¹³⁴ <http://www.synbicite.com/collaboration/industrial-partners/>

¹³⁵ <http://www.synbicite.com/collaboration/standards-and-metrology/>

comprehensive data management strategies for encrypting, storing, and transferring the data generated at the centre.

9.3.4 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations

SynbiCITE is geographically located at Imperial College. This allows SynbiCITE to leverage the entrepreneurial spirit of the College to innovate in synthetic biology. All undergraduate programmes at the College have an obligatory entrepreneurship course, the students therefore get exposed to entrepreneurship early on.¹³⁶ Through SynbiCITE's Business and Outreach Hub, the 4-day MBA programme and a 12-week Lean Launchpad education programme are also provided. The MBA is a part of SynbiCITE's drive to translate synthetic biology research by taking it from the lab to the development of tools, products, processes, and services for high-value manufacturing industries. The four-day interactive course covers the main strategies required to establish, build, and manage a biotech company built around synthetic biology and aims at developing natural entrepreneurship amongst their partners. Particular focus is given to the early stages of setting up a company, getting funding and understanding the wider reaches of IP.¹³⁷ Lean Launchpad is a course for teams interested in commercialising synthetic biology technology through a hands-on training experience designed to recreate the pressures and demands of the real world in the early-stage start-up. The participating teams are selected based on company's position in the market by analysing attributes like the necessary resources and needs of customers. This is used as a launching point for bringing the teams out in the real world to gather information from real customers and modify their strategy from those interactions. The programme is focused on customer discovery and development as well as market validation as tools to improve the relevance and desirability of the team's product.¹³⁸

SynbiCITE provides long-term support to existing companies and researchers wanting to spin-out their own company. This support distinguishes itself from a normal accelerator by involving long-term mentorship by experts, either from the College or from outside, rather than a short injection of support.¹³⁹

9.3.5 Domain 7 – RRI¹⁴⁰

SynbiCITE aims to ensure that the work of its academic and industrial partners provide innovative solutions to societal challenges in an ethical and legal way with the safety of society and the environment as a priority. The strategy for incorporating RRI-principles is through embedding the principles in education and the development of new technologies.¹⁴¹ The centre fosters dialogue between the public, scientists, engineers, and policy makers and are joined by the various bodies that fund research in the UK and are developing a comprehensive Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework. In association with social scientists at King's College London methods have been developed by which RRI principles can be translated into governance of synthetic biology. The approach maps onto a framework, set out by the EPSRC called AREA:¹⁴²

¹³⁶ Interview

¹³⁷ <http://www.synbicite.com/knowledge/biotechnology-mba/>

¹³⁸ <https://synbiobeta.com/uk-synbio-entrepreneurs-rejoice-programme-waiting/>

¹³⁹ Interview

¹⁴⁰ <http://www.synbicite.com/synthetic-biology/responsible-innovation/>

¹⁴¹ Interview

¹⁴² <http://www.synbicite.com/synthetic-biology/responsible-innovation/>

- Anticipation: SynbiCITE work with a variety of stakeholders to anticipate the economic, environmental, and social implications of research projects, and engage with end users of emerging technologies at an early stage to understand their needs and concerns
- Reflection: SynbiCITE require their partners to reflect on the purpose of and motivations for their work, opening to critical examination their assumptions and framings and analysing the impact that their work may have on society with an appreciation of the uncertainties, areas of ignorance, assumptions, framings, and questions inherent to the innovation process
- Engagement: SynbiCITE engage with the public to discuss synthetic biology, its applications, possibilities, benefits and potential. They encourage their partners to engage in public dialogue and stress the importance of explaining clearly what they are doing, why they are doing it, what the potential public benefits are, what the potential risks are, and how these are being addressed
- Action: SynbiCITE inform their partners on the outcomes of these activities, so that they can direct their innovation towards achieving public benefits and meeting key societal challenges

Furthermore, SynbiCITE work with several regulatory bodies including:

- Nuffield Council on Bioethics
- US National Academy of Sciences' Committee on Science, Technology, and Forum on Synthetic Biology
- Synthetic Biology Leadership Council
- Society of Biology
- BioIndustries Association (BIA)

SynbiCITE promotes engagement through:

- Close links with the Department of Social Science, Health and Medicine at King's College London and their editorship of the PLOS Biology Series on Public Engagement
- Participation in workshops organised by leading scientific and regulatory bodies
- High quality peer reviewed academic publications
- Comments in popular science media outlets.

SynbiCITE has done a lot of outreach to help educate society about the possibilities of synthetic biology. The different parties being informed include public bodies and research councils since both the co-directors were influential in UK's strategy for synthetic biology and later the strategy for bioeconomy.¹⁴³

9.4 Conclusions

SynbiCITE is the UK's national centre for the commercialisation of synthetic biology. The Centre is based at Imperial College's White City Campus in London and is a collaboration involving leading UK academic institutions and industrial partners, ranging from MNC's to start-ups, as well as support organisations. The environment for synthetic biology at Imperial College is well developed and the innovation focus of SynbiCITE is supplemented by the more academically

¹⁴³ Interview

focused Imperial College Centre for Synthetic Biology (IC-CSynB). A central component in the success of the centre is the London Biofoundry, the first in the public domain in the UK.

The conclusions which can be drawn from the case study which can provide valuable insights for DLN is provided in the bullets below:

- Domain 2: Since the renewal of the grant supporting SynbiCITE in 2018, the investment strategy of the organisation has been refined. The new investment model is targeted at companies at pre-investment stage before venture capitalists can take over the investment. These investments are usually smaller amounts, ranging from £5k-10k but can be up to £50k, which typically allows the grantee to do some crucial due diligence or similar. The management have found that more investments at smaller sums have more impact than fewer and larger grants. The rationale behind this is that much of the research within synthetic biology only needs a small amount of funding to de-risk the development enough for the technology to get to an investable state.
- Domain 3: The ecosystem for synthetic biology has become well developed in the UK with seven major research centres in the area. SynbiCITE's earlier work included a lot of educating industry and public actors about the possibilities of synthetic biology. One strategy has been to let companies do pilot projects. For this to be possible, the pillar of the BioDesign and Applications hub has been crucial in allowing companies to understand how SynbiCITE and the bio foundry can fit into the companies' own R&D-processes. The academic (IC-CSynB) and industrial (SynbiCITE) activities of Imperial in synthetic biology form the basis for a pipeline for developing new solutions in synthetic biology. The pipeline includes training from undergraduate to post-doctoral researchers combined with world-leading research and a commercialisation and exploitation strategy.
- Domain 4: SynbiCITE has a large network of synthetic biology experts, technical knowledge, and business expertise to facilitate growth and success of industry by acting as a conduit for industry, academia, and investors. The recently launched Industry Club is an exclusive community of synthetic biology professionals which will provide a forum through which innovative SMEs, spinouts and start-ups can connect and form a sense of community. The purpose of the club is to enhance the existing relationships between SynbiCITE and numerous companies in the field, as well as help facilitate relationships with new partners. Through the partnership and the Industry club, SynbiCITE can act as a broker to help companies identify suitable partners capable of providing synthetic biology solutions to their problems, as well as help uncover innovative solutions that are unique to the field. The centre will also reduce the barrier to entry into synthetic biology by offering resources and facilities to explore new technologies through the London BioFoundry. An important part for growing the industry is to allow companies to run projects at SynbiCITE, generate data and knowledge without worrying about IP or data theft. Therefore, the centre has developed comprehensive data management strategies.
- Domain 5: SynbiCITE is geographically located at Imperial College. This allows SynbiCITE to leverage the entrepreneurial spirit of the College. Furthermore, all undergraduate programmes at the College have an obligatory entrepreneurship course, so the students get exposed to entrepreneurship early on. SynbiCITE provides long-term support to existing companies and researchers and the support distinguish itself from a normal accelerator by being a long-term mentorship by experts, rather than a short injection of support.
- Domain 7: SynbiCITE aims to ensure that the work of its academic and industrial partners provide innovative solutions to societal challenges in an ethical and legal way with the safety of society and the environment as a priority. The strategy for incorporating RRI-principles is through embedding the principles in education and development of new

technologies. The centre fosters dialogue between the public, scientists, engineers, and policy makers and are joined by the various bodies that fund research in the UK and as such are developing a comprehensive Responsible Innovation (RI) framework. Furthermore, methods have been developed by which RRI principles can be translated into governance of synthetic biology.

10 SYN BIOCHEM

10.1 Introduction

SYNBIOCHEM is a Centre of Excellence for the synthetic Biology of fine and speciality chemicals production. It applies synthetic biology approaches to engineer microbes for rapid, predictable fine and speciality chemicals production, focussing on new products and intermediates for drug development, agrochemical and new materials for sustainable bio-manufacturing.

The centre was first established in 2014 with funding from the UK research councils and is located within the Manchester Institute of Biotechnology (MIB) at the University of Manchester. It is part of a wider investment in synthetic biology by the UK research councils and builds on the strategic priority given to Synthetic Biology through a set of government policies over the past decade.

SYNBIOCHEM – as well as the other centres funded under this government investment – have an important focus on responsible research and innovation (RRI). A group of social scientists and economists have been an integral part of the centre from the outset and have developed a framework for incorporating RRI processes and practices within the centre.

10.2 Background and context

10.2.1 UK investment in Synthetic Biology (Synbio)

The UK research councils, BBSRC, EPSRC and ESRC, first started investing in synthetic biology in the period 2007, 2008 and 2009, through responsive-mode funding and network grants. In the following years, the councils also took part in several smaller-scale international collaborative projects with European and American partners.¹⁴⁴

Following a series of broader strategic government initiatives, such as the 2011 Strategy for Life Sciences, an industry-led group of stakeholders developed a 'Synthetic Biology Roadmap for the UK' in 2012. The roadmap contained 5 main recommendations:

- Establishing a SynBio Leadership Council
- Investing in a network of multidisciplinary research centres
- Creating a skilled, energised and well-funded UK-wide SynBio community
- Investing to accelerate technology responsibly to market
- Assuming a leading international role

Following the roadmap's recommendations, the Synthetic Biology for Growth Programme was launched representing a total investment of £102m, including £70.5m in six multidisciplinary Synthetic Biology Research Centres (SBRCs), with the aim to "boost national synthetic biology research capacity" and ensure a "diverse expertise to stimulate innovation" in Synbio.¹⁴⁵

10.2.2 RRI and Synthetic Biology in the UK

RRI-related activities on synthetic biology had started already before the Roadmap and investment in centres of excellence. In 2010, the BBSRC and the ESRC jointly organised a public

¹⁴⁴ Synthetic biology Roadmap for the UK, p. 9

¹⁴⁵ BBSRC: Synthetic Biology for Growth Programme: <https://bbsrc.ukri.org/research/programmes-networks/synthetic-biology-growth-programme/>

dialogue on Synthetic Biology, with a broad consultation of a variety of stakeholders. Among other things, the final report conclusions outlined the 'Leadership and Funding Roles of the Research Councils' as well as capabilities needed by scientists to 'Think through Responsibilities' with respect to emerging Synbio technologies.¹⁴⁶

In the following years, the UK research councils developed a more systematic approach to RRI, through the EPSRC's 'Framework for Responsible Innovation' summarised in Figure 7 under.

Figure 7 EPSRC Framework for Responsible Innovation: AREA¹⁴⁷

- **Anticipate** – describing and analysing the impacts, intended or otherwise, (for example economic, social, environmental) that might arise. This does not seek to predict but rather to support an exploration of possible impacts and implications that may otherwise remain uncovered and little discussed.
- **Reflect** – reflecting on the purposes of, motivations for and potential implications of the research, and the associated uncertainties, areas of ignorance, assumptions, framings, questions, dilemmas and social transformations these may bring.
- **Engage** – opening up such visions, impacts and questioning to broader deliberation, dialogue, engagement and debate in an inclusive way.
- **Act** – using these processes to influence the direction and trajectory of the research and innovation process itself.

As compared to the concept of RRI used in the European Union's R&I framework programmes, the EPSRC's framework had a greater focus on process and practices such as 'anticipatory governance'.¹⁴⁸

10.2.3 The SYNBIOCHEM Centre

SYNBIOCHEM was part of a portfolio of investments from the BBSRC and the EPSRC (UKRI), which funded six multidisciplinary Synthetic Biology Research Centres (SBRC).¹⁴⁹ The centre received a £10.2m grant from the programme and was established for a period from November 2014 to September 2021.

A central part of the SYNBIOCHEM strategy is the development of a series of integrated technology platforms and physical infrastructure for fine and speciality chemicals production. On this basis, a number of science programmes to accelerate the delivery of synthetic biology solutions. An automated Design-Build-Test-Learn (DBTL) pipeline was developed to allow rapid prototyping and optimising of chemicals. The pipeline was first applied to E.coli but the pipeline is 'compound agnostic' and as such has the potential to be applied to the development of any chemical compound.^{150 151}

¹⁴⁶ Synthetic biology dialogue: Findings and recommendations, June 2010:

<https://bbsrc.ukri.org/engagement/dialogue/activities/synthetic-biology/findings-recommendations/>

¹⁴⁷ <https://epsrc.ukri.org/index.cfm/research/framework/>

¹⁴⁸ Shapira and Ribeiro (2018)

¹⁴⁹ UKRI Gateway to Research: <https://gtr.ukri.org/project/D4E3E7ED-05D6-42E8-A95E-385F256918D6>

¹⁵⁰ Carbonell et al. (2018), "An automated Design-Build-Test-Learn pipeline for enhanced microbial production of fine chemicals", *Communications Biology*, 1

¹⁵¹ <http://synbiochem.co.uk/synbiochem-pipeline/>

The centre primarily focusses on fundamental research, at TRLs 1-3, but also includes industry-driven Proof of concept projects at higher TRLs and encourages collaboration with industry in several respects. The table below summarises the centres output to date (as of 2020):

Table 4 Overview of SYNBIOCHEM output

Category	Outputs
People	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 13 senior researchers. Support for more than 130 PhD students
Scientific output	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• > 450 publications• 3 international conferences
Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• £21m new research funding
Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• >20 funded interactions with companies• 2 start up companies• 10 patents (include routes for the microbial biosynthesis of aromatic polyketides, monoterpenoids, propane gas, and ethanol from CO₂)¹⁵²

Source: SYNBIOCHEM Website

Complementing SYNBIOCHEM, the University of Manchester was awarded a new £10m grant in 2019, the 'Future Biomanufacturing Research Hub' (FBRH).¹⁵³ Compared to SYNBIOCHEM, the FBRH is focussed on scaleup and commercial uptake of bio-based processes, and consequently also has a greater focus on collaboration with industry.

From the outset, the centre had embedded a dedicate RRI group of societal scientists (Social sciences & humanities, Science & innovation policy, Sustainability).¹⁵⁴ The collaboration was established already in the preparation of the bid, which was prepared jointly, and continues in the new FBR hub.

10.3 Domains of relevance for this case

10.3.1 Domain 7 – RRI

10.3.1.1 Initial conditions

Favourable initial conditions relate to both the wider environment within the university and the foundations of the centre. The SYNBIOCHEM centre is situated within the Manchester Institute of Biotechnology (MIB),¹⁵⁵ which provides physical space designed for interactive working and an established track record of interdisciplinary collaboration and industry engagement. The core SYNBIOCHEM staff have been able to access expertise in related domains within the MIB, which houses some 50 different research groups and several other research centres.

The ability to establish RRI at the heart of the centre further depended on the presence of social scientists with the relevant experience and background within the wider university environment. Although they had not previously worked together, it was possible to establish

¹⁵² SYNBIOCHEM Brochure 2020.

¹⁵³ <https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=EP%2FS01778X%2F1>

¹⁵⁴ <http://synbiochem.co.uk/responsible-research-and-innovation/>

¹⁵⁵ <https://www.mib.manchester.ac.uk/>

the connection with the (future) RRI-lead when the funding opportunity arose, and they developed the bid for SYNBIOCHEM collaboratively. As a consequence, the RRI team was embedded in the centre from the start. It was a further advantage that the RRI team was able to spend a significant amount of time physically present at the Centre to develop trusted relationships with the scientists.

10.3.1.2 The research community

SYNBIOCHEM has a dedicated RRI team, whose roles include to “initiate early RRI dialogue”, “provide expertise, guidance and training”, and “foster public engagement and training for the research community.”¹⁵⁶ But the responsibility for RRI is not the sole domain of the RRI group:

“We’re like facilitators, we’re agents, but the whole centre is responsible for RRI and that means individual researchers, it means the management, it means the university, it means the sponsors, it means the companies.”

Key themes include early assessment of sustainability, assessment and anticipation of pathways to market, as well as issues around governance and policy as reflected in the RRI framework developed for the centre is shown in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8 SYNBIOCHEM RRI framework

Source: SYNBIOCHEM website.

Awareness and anticipation of RRI issues requires training as well as integration into everyday practices. In concrete terms the RRI team has provided a range of policy briefs and training activities including:

- A workshop for early career researchers in synthetic biology, in which participants were asked to reflect on notions of responsibility and how to apply RRI in their own work.¹⁵⁷

¹⁵⁶ <https://synbiochem.co.uk/responsible-research-and-innovation/ri-group/>

¹⁵⁷ RRI Group Research Brief 20/03, March 2020

- RRI support for teams in the international student competition iGEM.¹⁵⁸
- Pop-up's stalls in public venues to collect data and engage the public on issues related to RRI.¹⁵⁹

Such activities do not, however, cover the breadth of RRI activities undertaken at the Centre. The interaction between the RRI team and the scientific staff is collaborative and, like other parts of the Centre's activities, the work on RRI is research:

[T]his not like checklist, a set of things that you should do. Every situation is a bit unique. You know, we do have a variety of methods and tools. And it's a research process of working with colleagues who are developing the technologies, working with the companies and trying some things and trying some other things and kind of building on that. So we don't see this as a service function. It's a research function.

Although the centre primarily focusses on low TRLs 1–3, the scientists at the centre work across all levels, doing basic research, applied research, as well as setting up spin-out companies and consulting for industry. RRI has to be considered across all these levels.

Finally, the RRI team also fulfils a wider role as a public resource beyond the immediate constituents of the Centre. As such the group has engaged with companies and other external organisations.

10.3.1.3 Policy

Although there were no policies specifying how RRI was to be implemented, the broader policy environment and instructions from the funding bodies played an important enabling role.

As described above, SYNBIOCHEM was funded in the context of a policy agenda on synthetic biology, including strategic processes of development a roadmap and dialogues on the issue. The sustained investment and strategic priority given to synthetic biology was necessary to ensure that high-cost barriers – for equipment and infrastructure – have been overcome in establishing the centre.

The funders were also instrumental in establishing RRI on the agenda for the field. The Synthetic Biology Dialogue, carried out in 2010/09 (see above), had sought out the public's opinion and identified a number of issues – aspirations and concerns – about societal significance of synthetic biology. In the centre grants that would later be offered, the requirement by the research councils to develop RRI as part of the funded centres provided the conditions for “a series of experiments” on ways of implementing RRI in specific disciplinary contexts, and networking between the funded centres to exchange and develop ideas. The long duration of the grants further helped enable the building of relationships between the social scientists and the scientists, engineers and companies engaged in the Centre.

Finally, SYNBIOCHEM was able to draw on RRI frameworks developed by the EPSRC and British Standards Institution, BSI.¹⁶⁰ The EPSRC's AREA framework for Responsible Innovation (see above) was a relevant starting point from which a tailored approach to RRI for the Centre could be developed. Sustainability is widely seen as particularly important rationale for investing in synthetic biology and has consequently been the focus of further RRI work within SYNBIOCHEM. In the new centre, the Future Biomanufacturing Research Hub, the RRI group has

¹⁵⁸ <https://synbiochem.co.uk/igem-Manchester/>

¹⁵⁹ RRI Group Research Brief 17-01, May 2017

¹⁶⁰ BSI (2020), PAS 440:2020 Responsible Innovation – Guide, available at : https://pages.bsigroup.com/l/35972/2020-03-17/2cqcnc1?utm_source=pardot&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=SM-STAN-LAU-PAS-PAS440-2003

sought to give leverage to emerging public guidance, i.e., the BSI's guidelines have been a useful reference to point to, rather than the RRI group attempting to “reinvent the wheel”.

10.3.1.4 Examples of success and success factors

SYNBIOCHEM has been successful in delivering several RRI-related projects, based on collaboration between the RRI-group and other staff at the centre.

Intellectual property is a key concern for both innovation and RRI, including questions around private and public values of innovations in synthetic biology.¹⁶¹ SYNBIOCHEM has taken out ten patents, typically relying on standard processes with support from the tech transfer office. Many researchers are interested in open access and societal challenges, but institutional pressures and reward mechanisms can limit the scope for change in this area. Within SYNBIOCHEM, **patent analysis** has nevertheless proved a fruitful area of collaboration: A joint project was able to develop a method to identify chemical routes which did not have existing IP protection, helping the centres researchers find a way to patent while avoiding IP conflicts. The method is based on chemical formulas, rather than keywords as is conventionally used, and this was only possible by combining the staff's scientific knowledge with expertise in bibliometric patent analysis within the RRI team.

Formally in support of the new Future Biomanufacturing Research Hub, the RRI-group has worked to develop a **tool for early assessment of a project's sustainability**. At a stage when it is too early to undertake a full Life Cycle Analysis (LCA), formal Scenario Analysis or Horizon Scanning, the tool is meant to help researchers articulate ideas already “in their head”, stimulate reflection, and provide input for early decisions about what projects are taken ahead. A collaborative workshop was organised on this topic in October 2020, and the tool will be further refined and shared with the wider community.¹⁶² A key success factor for the project is for researchers to bring these ideas and practices with them when they leave the meetings and workshops they have attended and actually use them in practice in the lab.

Collaboration with industry on RRI is also done routinely and involves its own challenges. Companies have established contractual and legal procedures, as well as commercial interests to look after, and change often involves managerial as well as technical challenges. The RRI team have collaborated successfully with several companies, e.g., around sustainability.¹⁶³ Attempting to impose a defined set of RRI requirements in this context is unlikely to be a fruitful approach, and the team has instead attempted to highlight good practice and leverage existing guidance, e.g., the BSI guidelines on RRI. Successful factors include finding the right individuals to engage with within companies – which often have separate governance on the one hand, and science and technology on the other – the building of trust, and the use of Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) to protect confidentiality while also allowing ways for researchers to publish. Overall, companies appear to have become more open to new perspectives such as RRI over the course of the past several years.

¹⁶¹ Ribeiro & Shapira (2020), “Private and public values of innovation: A patent analysis of synthetic biology”, *Research Policy*, Volume 49, Issue 1, 103875

¹⁶² RRI Group Research Brief 20/11, November 2020

¹⁶³ See e.g., Matthews, Cizauskas, Layton, Stamford & Shapira (2019), “Collaborating constructively for sustainable biotechnology”, *Scientific reports* 9:1, Nature.

10.4 Lessons

This section summarises some of the key lessons drawn from the case study with respect to RRI, as they relate to the specific research questions for the study:

Convergence between disciplines is generally helped by the location of the Centre within an interdisciplinary environment. Physically embedding the RRI team within the centre has further enhanced dialogue and collaboration with the social scientists as well.

Intellectual property rights is a key concern for both innovation and RRI. Many researchers are interested in open access and societal challenges, but institutional pressures and reward mechanisms can limit the scope for change in this area. Even so, RRI can introduce new perspectives and help enhance innovation through interdisciplinary collaboration.

Partnerships with industry builds on trust and relies on arrangements that help protect the interests of both companies (confidentiality) and researchers (ability to publish). Collaboration on joint projects and sharing of good practice – e.g., encouraging the use of national guidelines (BSI) – is more fruitful than attempts to impose rigid requirements.

The incorporation of RRI principles is enhanced by embedding RRI from the start of a new initiative. With a long timeframe and dedicated resources for RRI, the groups have time to work together to find common ground between different perspectives. Training activities are important, but scientists should bring the principles with them when they return to the lab bench. RRI should not be seen as a service function, but a collaborative research process, for which all staff share responsibility, that involves experimentation and joint projects and development of tools.

Finally, networking, nationally and internationally, was found to enhance learning and experimentation. If equipped and resourced appropriately, the RRI team can work with stakeholders and exert influence beyond the centre, at national or even international level. Existing national guidelines and standards, such as those offered by the ESPRC and the BSI in the UK, can be used internally in the development of the RRI approach and externally as a shared reference point.

10.5 Conclusions

This case has focussed primarily on the RRI aspects of the SYNBIOCHEM centre. The centre has been in operation since 2014 and has therefore acquired considerable experience and expertise in the implementation of RRI. In short, the key learning points were:

- Convergence is helped by a multidisciplinary environment and colocation.
- Practices around IPR can be institutionally embedded and hard to change, but RRI can offer new perspectives on IP and support innovation through dialogue and collaborative projects.
- Partnerships with industry build on trust and mutually beneficial collaboration. Companies are becoming more open to considering RRI but are not likely to adopt frameworks imposed from the outside.
- A dedicated RRI team can act as facilitators but RRI is a joint responsibility that involves all staff and stakeholders. RRI is a collaborative process that involves experimentation and joint development of tools and projects; it is research function, not a service function.
- Networking nationally and internationally will enhance learning and experimentation. If equipped and resourced, the RRI team can work with stakeholders and exert influence beyond the Centre, at national or even international level.

- Existing national RRI guidelines and standards can be used internally in the development of the RRI approach and externally as a shared reference point.

10.6 List of references

10.6.1 Interviews

- Professor Phil Shapira, Professor of Innovation Management, RRI lead at SYNBIOCHEM
- Dr Rosalind Le Feuvre, Director of Operations at SYNBIOCHEM

10.6.2 Policy background:

- BBSRC on Synthetic Biology investments: <https://bbsrc.ukri.org/research/programmes-networks/synthetic-biology-growth-programme/>
- Synthetic Biology Leadership Council: <https://www.gov.uk/government/groups/synthetic-biology-leadership-council> ; <https://ktn-uk.org/programme/synthetic-biology-leadership-council/>
 - Most recent publication: “Synthetic Biology UK A Decade of Rapid Progress 2009-2019”
- Clarke and Kitney (2016), “Synthetic biology in the UK – An outline of plans and progress”, Synthetic and Systems Biotechnology, 1:4 (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405805X16300382>)
- “Synthetic Biology Dialogue”, 2010: <https://bbsrc.ukri.org/engagement/dialogue/activities/synthetic-biology/findings-recommendations/>
- BSI (2020), PAS 440:2020 Responsible Innovation – Guide, available at : https://pages.bsigroup.com/l/35972/2020-03-17/2cgcnc1?utm_source=pardot&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=SM-STAN-LAU-PAS-PAS440-2003
- EPSRC, “Framework for Responsible Innovation”, available at: <https://epsrc.ukri.org/research/framework/>

10.6.3 SYNBIOCHEM

- Carbonell et al. (2018), “An automated Design-Build-Test-Learn pipeline for enhanced microbial production of fine chemicals”, Communications Biology (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s42003-018-0076-9>)
- “Early assessment of sustainability for synthetic biology and biomanufacturing projects”, RRI Group Research Brief 20/11 | November 2020 ([20-11-FBRH-Sustainability-Assessment-Workshop.pdf \(manchester.ac.uk\)](https://www.manchester.ac.uk/research/20-11-FBRH-Sustainability-Assessment-Workshop.pdf))
- “Exercises in responsible research and innovation: Experiences from a workshop for early career researchers in synthetic biology”, RRI Group Research Brief 20/03 | March 2020 (<http://synbiochem.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/20-03-RRI-Exercises-FBRH-Away-Day-1.pdf>)
- Le Feuvre et al. (2016), “SYNBIOCHEM Synthetic Biology Research Centre, Manchester: A UK foundry for fine and speciality chemicals production”, Synthetic and Systems Biotechnology, vol 1, 271-275
- “Menthol in Everyday Life: “Pop-Ups” Collect Data, Engage Publics”, SYNBIOCHEM Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) Group Research Brief 17-01. May 2017

- Riberio and Shapira (2019), "Anticipating governance challenges in synthetic biology: Insights from biosynthetic menthol", *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Vol. 139 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162518308564>
- Ribeiro & Shapira (2020), "Private and public values of innovation: A patent analysis of synthetic biology", *Research Policy*, Volume 49, Issue 1, 103875
- Shapira and Ribeiro (2018), "Responsible Research and Innovation – A Manchester Perspective", https://www.research.manchester.ac.uk/portal/files/73658116/An_introduction_to_Responsible_Research_and_Innovation.pdf
- "SYNBIOCHEM Manchester Synthetic Biology Research Centre", Booklet, June 2020 (<http://synbiochem.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/SYNBIOCHEM-Booklet-June-2020-1.pdf>)
- "Synthetic Biology: Reshaping the Future? Manchester Policy Workshop Considers Implications of SynBio", Yanchao Li and Philip Shapira, January 26, 2016, <https://theplosblog.plos.org/2016/01/synthetic-biology-reshaping-the-future-manchester-policy-workshop-considers-implications-of-synbio-by-yanchao-li-and-philip-shapira/>

11 Umeå Biotech Incubator

11.1 Background and context

Umeå Biotech Incubator AB (UBI) is a specialised life science incubator supporting medical innovators who are eager to test and verify their business ideas in the life sciences field. The incubator is open both for research projects with innovative ideas and early-stage start-ups and it provides full-service support through a wide range of professional expertise, facilities, know-how and financing.

UBI is part of the Umeå University Innovation Support System and has been a private company since 2007. It is owned by Umeå University Holding, Umeå Kommunföretag, Region Västerbotten and SLU holding. UBI receives an annual core funding from some of their owners. The remaining funding comes from organisation and programs such as the European Regional Development Fund, Vinnova, the Erling Persson family foundation and Novo Nordisk Foundation. Most of the business ideas that are processed at the incubator originate from research at Umeå University.

The UBI operational management consists of a CEO and a team of employees: four business coaches, one head of PR and communication, one laboratory & community manager, one financial manager. The incubator has an annual turnover of SEK20–24m and the operating cost is about SEK11m, including personnel and facilities. The remaining money is used to finance activities in the Verify 1 and 2 phases of the incubation program.

UBI is a relevant case for this study with respect to the health sector and domains 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6.

11.2 Domains of relevance for this case

11.2.1 Domain 1 – Digital life capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence

UBI has no specific focus on digital convergence but evaluates all life science ideas that come to the incubator. There are lots of activities targeting artificial intelligence in Umeå region, but so far it has focused more on technological development and digitalisation of manual processes than real problem-solving, using the AI technology. However, UBI would like to see a larger in-flow of new ideas based on AI and life sciences to the incubator in the future.

There is little interdisciplinary research done among researchers at Umeå University, in particular between the social sciences and natural sciences but also between the technical and natural sciences. UBI considers this a weakness because life sciences cover all these disciplines and interdisciplinarity is usually needed to succeed in problem-solving and innovation. Jennie Ekbeck, the CEO of UBI, would therefore like to see more interaction between researchers.

“Here in Umeå we have a pond between the natural-medical sciences, and the social sciences and humanities. There is also a mental one. The respective parts of the sciences do not communicate with each other. And the education does not bridge this either. The courses offered at the different faculties are usually very good, but the students should be allowed to more freely to choose between them. We would like to have students who are not trained in a simple discipline, so we try to make them meet each other. The business sector wants this too.”

An education council has been established to change this situation by creating dialogue and synergies among academic disciplines within the university and making the students more

attractive to industry. Programme coordinators at the university usually have no industrial experience, so UBI has therefore seen its role as being to influence and help. Industry needs a broad spectrum of competences, and it cannot be left to academia to train the students and build the competences that the business sector needs – the companies have to be involved as well. The long-term mission for Jennie Ekbeck is to have more industry PhD students within the regional Life science industry, but at the current stage the industry finds the students too inexperienced. One way to rectify this is to let the students do their examination projects within a company. Previously, the large Swedish pharma companies Astra and Pharmacia used to be driving forces in education as well as research. Now, as they have left the region, the challenge is to attract SMEs as industrial partners.

11.2.2 Domain 2 – Funding from research to commercialisation

Pre-seed financing

UBI offers pre-seed financing to projects and start-ups with business ideas which are approved for the incubation process and has entered the verification phase. The money is supposed to bridge the well-known “valley of death” and help the ideas develop until they become attractive enough for private capital. The model for the UBI pre-seed financing is based on a previous funding instrument called VinnVerifiering from the Swedish innovation agency Vinnova which, according to UBI, was very successful but unfortunately no longer exists.

The pre-seed financing is based on milestones. According to UBI, there is a risk in giving too much money early as the projects then have a tendency to become lazy. Instead, the projects need to present a plan that is evaluated by the UBI board, and to receive continued funding they must deliver. Each milestone is usually SEK4–500,000 and the plan in total can be worth about SEK1m. If the project, or company, develops as planned and everything goes as it should, it can apply for a second batch of SEK1m funding as it enters the second verification phase of the incubation process. That money is then matched with other soft funding from external parties such as Vinnova, Swelife or Novo Seed in Denmark. Unfortunately, the money available from Vinnova is very scarce for this stage of development and the needed SEK2–4m is difficult to find.

Ideas that do not show progress or “do not fly” will be stopped right away. And the number of ideas that are stopped are quite high. Only 5 percent of the ideas being evaluated are funded in the first place, and of those only 50 percent make it to the end, all through the incubation process; 50 percent of the ideas are therefore terminated at some point.

The average investment per idea entering the incubator is about SEK1.3m. Ideas which are good enough to pass through the entire incubation process will at the end have received about SEK2.5–3m. The goal is to increase the value of the company 5–6 times, going from SEK20m to SEK40m with less than SEK3m of investment.

The pre-seed funding provided by UBI through the verification phases are grants and UBI does not take any ownership in return. It is imperative for UBI to be independent and not have its own interest in the projects/companies funded. Otherwise, it will be very difficult to terminate if not successful.

Private capital

In the region where Umeå is located, fortunes have traditionally been created and achieved through the forest. Life sciences has never been a large sector in the region. Private capital therefore must be attracted from elsewhere.

UBI is extremely careful about building and maintaining its brand and consider private investors as its customers. UBI listens to them and adapts the processes and way of working according to their interests. When the investors realise that UBI does listen to them, their interest to invest increases. As Jennie Ekbeck explains it: "When we see that an investor comes back and invests again, then we know that we have succeeded."

Building this kind of relationships is a long-term and continuous work. As an incubator, UBI cannot contact the same investor every time but need to have a network of private investors with whom to collaborate. It is important to be very cautious whom to approach and when. The investors with whom UBI collaborates are based in Scandinavia, Germany, the UK and sometimes the US. UBI has had contact with some Norwegian investors but so far none of them has decided to invest. To be of interest the investments must be substantial; UBI is not at all interested in small and thin investments which dilute the ownership of the companies and may drain the motivation of the inventor.

Business Angel Network and Sam-Invest

Sweden has many business angels and for some years there is a national business angel network in addition to several regional ones. Umeå has such a regional business angel network, but that network's competence in life science is quite weak. UBI therefore acts as a bridge between the business angels in the network and the companies in UBI's incubator, helping the business angels understand the business ideas and the market potential in doing life science investments.

Biotech Umeå Investment Day

UBI used to organise a yearly event, Biotech Umeå Investment Day to help companies in the incubator contact private investors, focusing on partnering between life science start-ups from the Västerbotten region and international investors. The event, which has been very popular and successful, usually attracts around 30 investors and 30 entrepreneurs to a physical meeting consisting of partnering sessions ending in a buffet at the end of the day. From next year, the investment day will be organised as a collaborative digital event together with all the other life science incubators in Sweden. The purpose is to present everything that Sweden has to offer in terms of life science start-ups during one, focussed, day.

11.2.3 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

Umeå University Holding AB and the innovation office

Umeå University has its own holding company which is owned by the government but managed by the university. The holding company is the majority owner of the three existing incubators in Umeå working closely with the university: UBI, Uminova Innovation och expression Umeå. The innovation office of Umeå University is run as part of the holding company instead of as part of the university organisation, mainly to avoid conflicts between the need for confidentiality and the principle of public access to official records.

UBI collaborates with several research-based institutions in the Umeå area: Umeå University, Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Norrlands Universitetssjukhus (NUS) and Försvarets forskningsinstitut (FOI). A majority of the business ideas that come to the incubator originates from the research at Umeå University and some of them are funnelled through the innovation office of the university. The Umeå University innovation office has the responsibility to offer support, inspiration and information that aid innovations and utilisation of ideas emerging from the academic research. It operates in the early stages of an innovation process and ideas that are more developed or have a clear commercial potential are therefore funnelled to the incubators, including UBI, or directly to the holding company, Umeå University Holding.

Swedish Incubators and Science Parks (SISP)

UBI is a member of the Swedish trade association for Sweden's incubators and science parks, SISP. SISP has 62 members across Sweden, which together have over 5,000 companies with more than 70,000 employees. The focus is on knowledge-based, growth-oriented companies and the members together run about 80 physical meeting places, offer operational business development, often operate or collaborate with clusters and have Triple Helix anchoring. Several members also run business angel networks and seed capital funds for early-stage investments in the construction of growth companies. SISP functions as a collaboration platform and members' activities contribute to business renewal, growth and more knowledge-intensive jobs.

Incubators need to have specialised competence within life science in order to handle the kind of business ideas and models relevant in that field. Life science ideas cannot be evaluated and incubated in the same way as other business ideas and there are specific things like regulatory affairs and IP that have to be considered carefully to avoid bad investments. Through SISP the incubators and science parks can share experiences and learn from each other to strengthen the competence on life science on a national level.

11.2.4 Domain 4 – Forging producer-user links in knowledge production and use

Industry-academia collaboration

Northern Sweden has a relative lack of industrial competence and experience within life sciences compared to other Swedish regions such as the Uppsala region. In many other regions there are established individual links between researchers at the university and the industry which makes collaboration a natural thing.

The advantage of not having much industry in the region is that no-one ever has to feel a need for local loyalty but always has the freedom to find collaborators and partners both nationally and internationally. Being a small city can also sometimes be an advantage. People from different sectors and different businesses meet at places like the football field and start to talk, and the barrier for them to collaborate becomes quite low.

Medical research in Umeå started with the cloning method, which was developed at Umeå University and spun out as the company Symbicon. This attracted Astra to the region and the life science era started to develop in various directions. Astra had a factory in Umeå and was at that point dependent on collaboration with academic researchers for its development. But Astra came up with a blockbuster and started to hire its own researchers, and then the collaboration with academia declined. Later, Astra closed its facility in Umeå and the region lost one of its two big life science industries. The other industry, Pharmacia Biotech, became GE Healthcare and now, since a year ago Cytiva. They still have some production in Umeå but all research is being done in Uppsala. Therefore, the interest among the researchers in collaborating with industry has decreased and the university has very little focus on industry-academia collaboration. Some small companies have been started in region since then, but it is mainly the hospital and the Swedish Defence Research Agency that collaborates with the university.

According to Jennie Ekbeck, there is need for a change in attitude both within academia and industry to increase collaborative efforts across the sectors. There is sometimes a perception that the knowledge production in academia is “clean”, and in industry, it is “dirty”. In academia, the results are “accurate”, while in industry they “cheat. Jennie is of the opinion that some researchers at university need to change their mind, and start being interested in industrial collaboration. She says that, those researchers in Umeå who used to have such

collaborations and relations some decades ago are now retired and the younger industrial leaders have not the same links towards academia. Therefore, there is a need to re-establish these connections and the culture all over again. One instrument for that purpose is the student examination projects (see Domain 1 and 5).

Also, the mentality among the medical companies need to change a bit, according to Jennie. Before, they valued the researchers at the university, but as soon as they experience commercial success and can employ their own researchers to a larger extent, they drop the links with academia. And the pharma industry needs a supply of new technology. They have their own venture arms and can-do investments, but they do not understand that to get new projects from academia, they need to invest at an early stage.

AstraZeneca mentor programme

UBI has a mentoring programme together with AstraZeneca which is offered to the projects that are in the incubator. The aim of the programme is to give the researchers and start-ups an open door to discuss research and business with industry specialists. The plan is to broaden the programme to include other companies as well.

11.2.5 Domain 5 – Innovation culture and practices in the research-performing organisations

Organisation and management

If academia truly wants to create an innovative culture, then Jennies experience is that it is imperative that the principal and the university board is interested and supportive. She says that ideally, the TTO should have a representation in the university board. Those universities that have so are more successful, and Umeå University is one good example (Innovation som drivkraft – från forskning till nytta. SOU 2020:59). If key opinion leaders and management are not that interested in innovation and utilisation, then it has a very negative impact on the organisation in total. Applied research must not be considered of less value than basic research, according to Jennie.

Examination projects

UBI and Umeå University are supporting master students to do their final thesis in industry. The major challenge is to attract SMEs as they often have limited capacity for supervising students and have to focus on their core businesses. Previously, the large Swedish pharma companies Astra and Pharmacia used to be driving forces in education as well. Now as they have left the region, Jennie expects that the smaller companies have to take over that responsibility.

Industrial PhD programme ("Företagsforskarskolan")

Another good way to bridge academia and industry and build relations is through "Företagsforskarskolan", and kind of industrial PhD programme offered through Umeå University. The programme is organised so that the PhD candidate is employed by Umeå University but the cost and time is shared 50/50 with a company. The companies participating in the program can be both Swedish and international. As part of the PhD program is a 3-months internship where the student is supposed to work on tasks not related to the research project. These three months are fully paid by the university.

Currently only 9 % of the PhD positions are within medicine, and 50 % are within technical and natural sciences. The ambition is to have a more equal spread between the two faculties in the future since they have more or less the same number of students.

Innovation Award

In order to foster awareness and interest in innovation, UBI would like to establish an innovation award. Such an award should ideally be given on department level at the university, and not to an individual. Innovation grows in permissive environments and to create systemic impact and inspiration and not individual impact only, a larger group of people should benefit from it. The award should be used for activities such as competence building or study visits.

11.2.6 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

Deal flow into the incubator

It is important for UBI that the ideas they develop comes from researchers who have a genuine interest in bringing the ideas forward. UBI takes no ownership in any ideas and therefore never goes "hunting". Instead, it is desired that the researchers come by themselves, driven by their own interest, and knock on the door. UBI spends a lot of time informing researchers about innovation and how to create value from academic research, but at the end it should be their own interest that brings them to the incubator. This also means that UBI cannot set the agenda for what kind of ideas that should be developed based industry needs or market trends. It is the funding agencies that have the power to set the research agenda, and the researcher and in-flow to the incubator will follow. The only way to influence what research is being funded is by lobbying through Vinnova or policy makers.

For UBI, not all ideas will be able to make it all the way to commercialisation. UBI is emphasising that the work shall be "the diamond", top-notch. It is not an offer for all. UBI is only interested in those ideas with commercial potential. The other ideas, which have no commercial potential, are sent back to academia as continued interesting research.

The TTO can assist and speed up the initial processes, so that the researchers increase the pace and start moving along the innovation chain. However, The TTO needs to have knowledge and experiences from life science, else there is a substantial risk that the TTO will miss good ideas or misunderstand their potential. There are many failed investments done because of lack of knowledge. In the last few years there has been an increase in the flow of ideas from the university to the innovation office, but the flow from the innovation office to UBI has however decreased. The reason seems to be that the innovativeness of the ideas from the university has declined.

Evaluation and incubation process

UBI has developed and implemented a systematic and transparent evaluation and incubation process for how to select and support projects to ensure that their resources are invested in the ideas with the highest scientific quality and best market potential. What is unique with UBI program is that it is open also for academic projects and not only start-ups. Projects entering the incubator are given competitive services for verification and development of innovations and ideas can be kept organised as projects until the Verify 2 phase. UBI estimates that it needs four coaches/business developers to run 20 projects through the incubator. The coaches should be generalists – all specific expertise is hired externally. The process goes through 7 steps:

iv) Evaluate

The first phase of the programme is the evaluation phase. Every year about 20–30 researchers, academics or clinicians are in contact with UBI to discuss findings or data that may have commercial potential. All ideas are evaluated based on four different areas: the quality of the scientific data, the IPR situation, i.e., if the idea is actually new

and possible to protect, the team, and the growth potential. Ideas can be very interesting but still have no commercial potential. There must be a need, and the idea shall be the solution, otherwise no one will buy the product in the end. UBI is only interested in ideas that can be commercialised. It is therefore important to sort these things out at a very early stage through the initial evaluation.

Quality of scientific data: When considering the data needed it is important to “start from the end” and ask what data an investor will look for. Drug projects will need data that proves activity, preferably from an in-vivo animal study, a so-called lead. Literature studies or hypotheses are not enough. Biomarkers have to show correlation to a disease, but it can still be open what platform to use since platform selection will be done later as part of the Verify 1 phase. Medical devices and biotech tools must be developed into prototypes that can show proof of concept. Animal models must prove that they work.

Intellectual property: The idea does not yet have to be patented but it must have potential to be protected in some clear and identifiable way. Eighty percent of all projects applying to the incubator is never accepted because the idea cannot be protected or lack of understanding of the potential for protection.

Team: There must be a dedicated person with the interest and capacity to work actively with the project.

Growth potential: The goal is to reach a turnover of SEK20m within six years from product launch, or SEK100m after ten years. To reach these numbers the market potential must be large.

The evaluation process usually takes 3–5 weeks. About half of the ideas being evaluated move on to the pre-incubator phase and it usually takes three evaluations until an individual project is approved to continue.

v) Pre-incubator

The focus of the pre-incubator phase is to investigate the market need for the product or service in question and to evaluate the team. This helps educate the team about what it actually means to be a UBI-case and to test whether they are willing and able to do the work needed. UBI staff will dedicate a lot of time and effort to each case and expects the project team to do the same.

The market need is evaluated by talking to real potential customers and asking critical questions about how they foresee using the proposed product or service. The dialogue has to be about the customer need and not the technical product itself. Therefore, the researchers are not allowed to do the talking themselves – that is always done by an external consultant with sales experience – but the team has to be part of the exercise. The researchers must be trained in how to run these kinds of meetings and what to focus on, to be able to identify the needs and requirements of the customers, before they are allowed to do it themselves. UBI recommends using a postdoc for this market need evaluation and not the PI. The experience of UBI is that 50 percent of the ideas that enter the pre-incubator are terminated because they do not meet a real need. But even if they are terminated, the researchers often benefit from talking to potential customers by obtaining new perspectives and new research ideas, based on which they can apply for more research funding. So, from their perspective it is a kind of win in any case.

The pre-incubator phase usually takes 6–12 months and at the end there should be an official application to UBI with a plan containing carefully selected activities and a

detailed budget. About half of these applications are accepted and will proceed to verification activities in the Verify 1 phase.

vi) Verify 1

Ideas reaching the Verify 1 phase are official UBI-cases with budget, financing, and milestones. The main focus of this phase is to produce and document solid data showing that the idea is scalable, and to build a strong project that can attract seed funding from external sources. Together with UBI, the team has to set up a plan to produce the data needed. The activities mostly include experiments and market research. Each case has clear stop and go criteria.

The Verify 1 phase is also about coaching and training the team. The teams are trained and coached gradually to become increasingly independent from UBI, but they will not be allowed to operate freely by themselves until they have received external funding in the Finance phase. UBI therefore offers every case that enters the Verify 1 phase a coach/business developer/project manager, a sales expert and, if needed, a business expert specialised in the area of business on which the case focuses.

The Verify 1 phase usually takes 1–2 years to complete.

vii) Verify 2

Cases reaching the Verify 2 phase have advanced past in-house funding and secured grants from external stakeholders like Vinnova, Swelife, Novo Seeds or similar. The focus of the Verify 2 phase is on investigating future markets, adjusting the product, evaluating financing options, calculating production and scaleup costs and searching for potential partners. Cases which are still run as academic projects should now register a company to protect their IP.

The cases can apply for another round of funding from UBI in the Verify 2 phase. The phase usually takes 1–2 years to complete.

viii) Finance

The Finance phase helps the cases go from being a start-up with seed funding, to obtain the first round of external private investments. UBI helps the companies find its way through the landscape of global partnering events, coaches them in negotiation and provides contacts to help the company find the right investors with the right competence. The finance phase usually takes 6–9 months to complete.

ix) Grow

When entering the Grow phase, the start-up has raised capital and is on its way to become an established start-up company with potential to scale. The company is now run independently by the team but UBI continues to offer support in this vital stage of development, such as assistance with HR issues, sales techniques, public relations, affordable facilities and professional CEO mentoring. The Grow phase usually takes 1–2 years.

x) Alumni

Alumni – Once graduated from the incubator the companies become part of the biotech cluster in northern Sweden. UBI offers networking and PR support.

Team

UBI puts a lot of effort into the teams of the projects that are accepted for the incubator, and has over the years built valuable knowledge and experience to share.

- It is important that the researcher who had the original idea remains in the process, because it is in that brain that the idea rests. UBI always keeps that person in the process, but adds resources and other competences so that commercial success is achieved.
- There must exist a so-called champion who drives the whole thing. According to UBI, that person should not be the PI of the research team for the simple reason that the PIs usually don't have neither the time nor the necessary detailed insight into the research behind the idea to run the innovation project.
- The PI is also very important for the process; the PI is needed to guarantee high quality of the data and the experimental design, but should not focus on building the business.
- For running the business, try to foster a champion among the younger staff. The ideal situation is when there is a PhD candidate or postdoc, who has the trust of the PI and the right entrepreneurial mind-set and skills. One can also consider bringing in an external person to take responsibility for leading the innovation project, but then there must be trust between the researchers and that person. Trust is key. If an external person is hired to be responsible for the business, and that person is an experienced entrepreneur, then it is extremely important that he or she moves slowly. The researchers have to be trained and taught along the way.
- One has to be prepared that there will be conflicts, because there are always conflicts in teams. Even teams that have cooperated for years and years, experience conflicts at some point. The conflicts usually arises either when the start-up is about to take in external capital or when the product is to be launched in the market. Many people are afraid of this, afraid to fail, so there is resistance. They may not even be aware of this psychology themselves, but it is often like that. UBI therefore sometimes brings in psychologists to sort it out.

Company board

The company board is important for the success. The board should be established before external investors are attracted, and the competence and composition of the board should be optimised to secure the development of the company. Ideally the board members should have slightly overlapping competences as that usually guarantees better discussions. Any historical success stories of individual board members must not dominate the dialogue and development process. The members of the board therefore have to be selected carefully.

Business coaching

It is important for UBI to be an objective part when working with the cases in the incubator. The business coaches of UBI are not supposed to give advice even if they have the competence needed and in practice could do it themselves. Instead, UBI uses external consultants and experts to advise the cases and has a competence pool of experts to use. UBI continuously looks for people with board expertise, project management expertise, mentors and advisors and recruitment is done both through open calls for general applications, and through specific positions for individual projects and start-ups in the incubator. The use of external consultants presents the largest running cost of the incubator.

To be able to coach the cases in the best way, the incubator and the experts need to understand what the teams know in terms of developing their idea towards a commercial product or service, but also what they do not know. The teams need to have a real perspective on their own lack of knowledge – and be willing to listen and learn. UBI uses a model that UBI has developed to help the teams understand their range of knowledge. The model consists of three boxes with different colours. The green box represents knowledge that the teams possess. That knowledge consists mainly of research data. The red box represents knowledge the teams

do not have, but which they are aware of that they lack. Often knowledge about IP is found in that red box. The role of UBI is to help the teams understand what they have to do to gain the knowledge they need in order to develop their idea in a commercial direction. Then, the teams have a third, blue box, containing knowledge the teams do not have and are not even aware that they lack or should preferably have. This box is extremely important, and here the incubator plays a vital role in helping and supporting and building this awareness and knowledge. Usually, the blue box contains lots of soft knowledge such as how to approach and talk to potential customers. UBI will show the way and train the teams along the incubation process.

Key success factors

- To be successful in innovation, the projects must be run by researchers with solid research funding to produce the data and results needed to support the business idea. The experience by UBI is that researchers who have money to do both fundamental research and innovation funding are the most successful.
- An idea should try to live on “soft” public funding such as research grants as long as possible. Managing a company takes lots of effort. The only reason to do so is to access external share capital or to have a place to handle IP (patents). Managing a company takes lots of effort, and the idea needs to fly before the company is established, else it suffocates. The right time to set up a company varies among regions and countries. It is therefore important not to copy-paste what is being done elsewhere but to adapt to one's own context.
- It is important that the idea is based on data that is owned by the researcher or the start-up. The data can be owned through a licence from the university but it is usually more attractive to investors if the ownership is within the company.
- As a life science incubator, it is especially important for UBI to understand the legal frameworks and regulations, in particular if the ideas are to be implemented in the public health sector. One has to understand the difference between user and payer and reimbursement rules and develop business models that match the system. The same holds with IP. If you do not protect your ideas the way the market wants you to do, then the idea is useless.
- Life science ideas should not be incubated together with other ideas. The needs, time frames and costs are so different from most other sectors and therefore need to be treated separately.
- The tempo in academia is generally too slow to be relevant in commercialisation. Data are needed quickly and GO/NO GO decisions must be made fast.

Meet Umeå Life Science – networking and match making

The Meet Umeå Life Science is an annual event taking place in Stockholm where start-up companies and experienced experts in life sciences are given the opportunity to mingle and discuss possible collaborations. This is an opportunity for the start-up company to find professionals to join the board of directors, advisory board, CEO, experts in product development and expand its network.

Facebook group to get access to lab equipment

Lab equipment is usually expensive and requires specific expertise to handle and operate. Early phase research projects and start-ups often struggle with having funding to invest in the kind of equipment and competence they need for some specific studies. Sometimes they only need

to use a certain piece of equipment once, and large investments are not motivated or possible. The solution is often to find a collaboration partner for that specific purpose.

At the same time, there are many labs, both within academia and in the industry, that have equipment which is not fully utilised. Also, since lab equipment usually require specific operational expertise and if that expertise leaves the lab the machine may never be used again.

In Umeå, this issue has been solved through a Facebook community where people can share, buy and sell second-hand laboratory equipment and also gain access to laboratory services. This Facebook group allows Umeå-based companies to support each other. In addition to solving the acute problems of the projects and companies, the Facebook group has increased the networking opportunities between members and made it easier to identify synergies and collaboration opportunities.

12 Flemish Institute for Biotechnology VIB (Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie)

12.1 Background and context

VIB (Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie) is a non-profit research institute that is spread across and operates in partnership with five Flemish universities: Ghent University, KU Leuven, University of Antwerp, Vrije Universiteit Brussel and Hasselt University.

VIB demonstrates a strong focus on translating basic research result to commercial application, whether through industrial uptake or entrepreneurial ventures (i.e. start-ups, spin-offs, etc.). Since its inception VIB has become a prominent part of the Flemish life science ecosystem, boasting a comprehensive list of services connected to supporting research commercialisation.

The focus on technology transfer and the importance of VIB to the Flemish innovation ecosystem offers an opportunity for the case study to focus on the domains 1, 2, 3, and 6 as VIB creates a network between five Flemish institutions, providing both support to conduct research as well as support in translating the research into commercial opportunities.

The institution was founded in 1995 by the Flemish government with the objective to support the Flemish capacity for life science research. Established across five Flemish universities, VIB has an infrastructure based on specific units that are responsible for different areas of operations:

- VIB headquarters, located in Zwijnaarde (Ghent), is the general managing body including two Managing Directors and the Management Committee. The Committee is responsible for developing and implementing the institutional strategy
- VIB's Science & Technology team and VIB Innovation & Business team provide different services for researchers. Science & Technology is responsible for supporting research being conducted at VIB including internal grants for researchers, monitoring research progress. Science & Technology team cooperates with Innovation & Business team regarding the core facilities (that provide access to high-tech equipment for VIB's researchers) and Tech Watch (identifies novel, emerging technologies with applicability in VIB's research). Science & Technology and Innovation & Business in many ways represent two sides of the same coin – the first could be regarded as supporting basic and experimental research while the later supports applied research and research commercialisation
- VIB Operations manages the infrastructure support for VIB. This includes both ensuring that the different VIB teams, operations, etc. have adequate working spaces as well as realizing VIB's ambitions in its partnerships in bioincubator spaces in Flanders
- VIB HR team handles the recruitment and retaining of talent to support the different teams of VIB
- VIB Conferences & Outreach team are responsible for communication and dissemination activities
- VIB Finance and Administration team handles the administrative work at VIB
- VIB IT team ensure the running of the institutional ICT systems, including interdepartmental network, the ERP system

By 2020 VIB had achieved the following output indicators¹⁶⁴:

- During the period of 2016–2020 reached €135.6m in industrial income
- A total of 27 start-ups established from VIB research that employ 900 people. VIB Start-ups have attracted €1.3b in capital investment
- 618 total number of patent applications with 240 total number of active patent families

The following chapters present VIB activities initiatives, programmes, etc. related to one of the domains that form the background of this analysis.

12.2 Domains of relevance for this case

12.2.1 Domain 1 – Digital life capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence

Digital convergence in VIB has taken the form of the VIB Core Facilities, which are further described in section 12.2.4. This is evident with VIB Bioinformatics Core which offers the following services:

- Training in bioinformatics tools, programming, statistics, NGS, omics and single cell data analysis
- Distributes scientific software for use across VIB
- Provides bioimage informatics services in collaboration with VIB Bioimaging Core
- Contributes to software development of bioinformatics applications
- Provide bioinformatics services and research data management to VIB researchers. These services include: bioinformatics pipelines, software development, bioimage informatics, statistics consulting, omics data integration and research data management

The above shows how VIB has approached introducing ICT and digitalisation services to life science research. Perhaps the key element that the cores function as service providers – scientists can enlist for training to run their research without the need of external assistance (training is provided by Technology Innovation Lab, see below), but they can also opt to have the core teams conduct the services that will enhance their research. Importantly, the Bioinformatics Core is what could be considered the “general” core that has a broader range of services, while the other cores are more specialised.

Another evidence of utilising IT to drive life science research is seen when in 2019 the Screening Core launched NextGenQBio which combines cutting edge bioimaging analysis software with IT data storage infrastructure. The platform provides: “high-throughput screening (HTS) technologies with high-content imaging (HCI) to enable high-throughput high-content screening (HT-HCS). Added to this, a centralized cell culture platform was established for automated culturing of a broad range of cell types”.¹⁶⁵ The platform was developed in partnership between the Screening Core, VIB Discover Science (a VIB unit enabling promising research to move into commercialisation stages) and members of the Stem Cell Institute Leuven (SCIL) and VIB-KU Leuven Centre for Brain and Disease Research and VIB Discovery Science.

¹⁶⁴ VIB (2019). Annual Report 2019. Available at: https://vib.be/sites/default/files/vib_2019_annual_report_ENG_2020_0422_LR.pdf

¹⁶⁵ VIB (2019). NextGenQBio: A better view on cells. Available at: <https://vib.be/news/nextgenqbio-better-view-cells>

The Core Facilities are enabled through two programmes: the VIB Tech Watch initiative and the Technology Innovation Lab.

Tech Watch & Technology Innovation Lab

Focusing first of Tech Watch, it was established back in 2008, designed to facilitate research by an “early identification system” for facilitating technologies. The Tech Watch team analyses the Tech market for emerging technologies that can have the potential to boost the research output at VIB. By 2019 the Tech Watch initiative had invested €500,000 to support technology uptake at the core facilities at VIB and approved 43 applications for Tech Watch projects.

Tech Watch is composed of a team of eight people who are selected for their knowledge in novel technologies (an example would be technology-driven scientists). The role of the team is screening for new technologies, start-ups, etc. with the goal of identifying promising technologies that could be adopted by VIB researchers, core facilities etc. This process targets both novel new technologies that are fresh on the market as well as technologies still in prototype stages. The team contacts the technology developers looking for opportunities to get early access to the technologies.

VIB researchers can also apply for Tech Watch funding to introduce specific technologies that are necessary for their research. In this case, researchers have a choice of three options:¹⁶⁶

- Early-access fund – funds the acquisition of non-commercialised technologies
- New technologies – funds the acquisition of recently commercialised technologies
- Tech development fund – funds the development of novel technologies in-house

In support to Tech Watch is the Technology Innovation Lab. If the former introduces new technologies to the core facilities, the later supports their uptake. Specifically, the Technology Innovation Lab is composed of a team of scientists who are trained to use technologies located within the Core Facilities. When new technologies are introduced through Tech Watch, these scientists undertake training by the technology developers to be able to utilise the equipment. The team then performs the dual role of running the technologies in the Core Facilities and training other researchers in their use.

The Tech Watch initiative demonstrates how industry can be included in the convergence. The uptake of novel technologies at VIB facilities has created a working and research environment driven by both access and increasing need for cutting-edge technologies. An example of this is evident with the establishment of the Single Cell Accelerator. VIB was among the early adopters of single-cell technologies. While this allowed for novel research to be conducted it also necessitated higher uptake of such technologies as they grew in their necessity for cancer, inflammatory neurodegenerative illness research.

The answer to this demand was the Single Cell Accelerator which enables researchers to apply for funding for the introduction of single-cell technologies for their research. The Accelerator collaborates with technology companies, such as Mission Bio, Sphere Fluidics, Refeyn, GALT, Nanoview Biosciences and Janssen Pharmaceutica that supply the relevant technologies to conduct single-cell driven research.¹⁶⁷

Thus, successful collaborations with industry partners can become drivers for increased introduction of novel technologies. The approach of Tech Watch in forging these partnerships,

¹⁶⁶ VIB (2021). Tech Watch program. Available at: https://vib.be/science-meets-technology#tech_watch

¹⁶⁷ VIB (2019). Annual Report 2019. Available at: https://vib.be/sites/default/files/vib_2019_annual_report_ENG_2020_0422_LR.pdf

providing avenues for early commercialisations provides added value to industry while benefitting researchers through early adoption of novel applications. This is, however, applied under a screening process to ensure the applicability of technologies at VIB.

12.2.2 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital

Research and innovation funding at the pre-commercialisation stage

The Innovation & Business team is the major organisational unit in VIB that is concerned with business development, research commercialisation, etc. Innovation & Business is composed of smaller sub-teams/units handling different aspects of commercialisation. The VIB's New Ventures team plays the primary role regarding emergence of start-ups and spin-offs.

New Ventures team is specifically interested in the opportunities for new businesses operating within the field biotech and acts as an incubator for promising research. The team itself cooperates closely with the Business Development and IP Management teams. The involvement of smaller units enables VIB New Ventures to operate as a comprehensive package.¹⁶⁸

Figure 9 Pathway of VIB's support for emerging start-ups

Source: VIB

In collaboration with Discovery Science (for more information about Discovery Science, see section 12.2.4), New Ventures gains insight into promising research conducted at VIB that is nearing commercialisation stage. The identification process typically happens when there is enough research data available to start evaluating IP potential. However, it is possible for New Ventures to begin working on commercialisation from the idea stage if they can be convinced

¹⁶⁸ VIB (2021). New Ventures. Available at: <https://vib.be/science-meets-business/new-ventures>

that the research idea will have commercialisation potential. Typically, the research targeted by New Ventures falls into either of two categories:

- Either the research has already started with enough scientific data for New Ventures to work on IP validation. When this process starts the researchers have up to 1 year to move the research towards a stage where New Ventures can engage in Proof of Concept (POC) support
- Or the research is referred to as strategic projects, which have a longer run time (several years). Here New Ventures funds the researchers while also looking for grant opportunities

Working with members of the IP Management team (for more information about IP management see section 12.2.4) helps researchers with PoC, freedom to operate (FTO) analysis and an IP strategy.

PoC Funding

Importantly, the POC stage includes opportunities to receive VIB investment from the POC Fund – internal funding available from Innovation & Business. The POC Fund enables the team to provide early-stage equity capital for start-ups that are considered interesting and have commercial opportunities. In fact, it has been suggested that the POC Fund allows to target research that might not demonstrate significant scientific impacts but could have good commercial potential.

Business plan preparation and “Entrepreneurs in residence”

New Ventures together with VIB Business Development team facilitate the process of preparing a business plan. Crucially, New Ventures features “Entrepreneurs in residence” – business professionals looking for a new entrepreneurial venture. These entrepreneurs are involved in the business plan development with the option that they can become part of the emerging start-up’s man management. In other words, New Ventures supplies researchers with business-minded individuals that can help the company take off and alleviate the need for researchers to be involved in business development.

Attracting investment opportunities through collaboration with V-Bio Ventures

Regarding capital investment into research and start-ups/spin-offs, VIB benefits from a close relationship with the V-BIO Ventures fund which VIB launched back in 2015 as an early-stage life sciences investment fund. With the business plan in place, New Ventures starts looking to attract investment opportunities. This is done in cooperation with VIB Business Development and the V-Bio Ventures fund. V-Bio Ventures is an independent venture capital fund that invests throughout Europe in start-up and early-stage life science companies with high growth potential. The fund focuses on investments in (bio)pharmaceuticals, diagnostics and agricultural improvements. Crucially for VIB, the fund indicates to have a “preferred relationship with them. This is not to say that V-Bio does not fund projects outside of VIB but it does demonstrate that as an institution VIB has a strong relationship to a venture capital fund that beyond providing investment into start-ups, spin-offs, is also involved in giving feedback regarding whether businesses emerging from VIB New Ventures are at a stage where private investment would be interested in their commercialisation. It is estimated that around 60%-70% of V-BIO deals are made with VIB start-ups and/or spin-offs. Investment from V-Bio Ventures also attracts other investments as the involvement of a venture capital fund is seen as an endorsement to the commercial potential of the start-up.

As part of the investment criteria, V-BIO indicates interest in investing in companies whose research, operations, etc. are linked to societal needs, societal impact and are in line with the U.N. Sustainable Development Goals. This is comparable to VIB Discovery Science which

similarly requires research to include societal benefits to receive support (for more see 0). This translates into V-Bio Venture investment acting as an indicator that the new business is working to achieve societal goals and impacts – meaning that VIB spin-offs, spin-outs are recognised for their societal value as well as research and commercial value.

VIB International Grants Office

VIB researchers also benefit from VIB International Grants Office which provides support for researchers looking to gain international funding for their research. In particular, the Office conducts and manages actions that include:¹⁶⁹

- Identifying grant opportunities – the International Grant Office conducts screening to identify funding opportunities. These are presented in an online platform (see below)
- Manages the online grant platform.¹⁷⁰ The platform is designed to be a central tool for VIB researchers (one needs to be affiliated to VIB in order to access the platform functionalities). In addition to hosting the list of funding opportunities, the platform also provides information on completing each part of a grant application
- Supports researchers in preparing grant applications and managing administration processes for funded projects

12.2.3 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

When considering the wider ecosystem that VIB operates in, the discussion turns to the Flemish life science cluster where VIB maintains a pivotal role.

The life science ecosystem is noted for its strong international performance in biotech, medtech, pharmaceuticals and healthcare, including¹⁷¹:

- Number 1 for clinical trial procedure speed
- Number 1 for biotech market capitalisation
- Number 2 for clinical trial applications per capita
- Number 3 for pharma and biotech patent applications per capita
- Number 3 for number of (bio)pharma researchers per capita

The Flemish ecosystem was able to achieve this through a combination of supportive legislative system and a comprehensive number of different stakeholders that effectively established an entire value chain from research to commercialisation within the region.

Regarding the legislative support, companies can benefit from several tax benefits available to companies operating in research intensive sectors. These benefits include: “up to 85% of a company’s net innovation income can be exempt from corporate tax”; “R&D investment deduction of either 13.5% of the investment value (at once) or 20.5% of the annual depreciation (staggered)”; “R&D payroll tax exemption of 80% of the withholding tax on professional income for researchers and academic personnel”.¹⁷²

¹⁶⁹ VIB (2021) International grants office. Available at: <https://vib.be/science-meets-science/international-grants-office>

¹⁷⁰ VIN (2021). Grants. Available at: <https://grants.vib.be/>

¹⁷¹ Invest Flanders (2021). Flanders' life sciences industry: the perfect combo of biotech, medtech, pharma and healthcare. Available at: <https://www.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/invest/en/sectors/life-sciences-health>

¹⁷² Invest Flanders (2021). Flanders' life sciences industry: the perfect combo of biotech, medtech, pharma and healthcare. Available at: <https://www.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/invest/en/sectors/life-sciences-health>

Beyond the various tax schemes that make R&D in life science more profitable, Flanders has, over the years, established a comprehensive network of actors that support transition of research from basic to commercialised. The following presents an overview of the ecosystem's composition – institutions that are engaged in life science education, research, research commercialisation.

- Five universities that provide life science education and contribute to emergence of the next generation of scientists, entrepreneurs, technicians, etc. that work within the life science ecosystem. These universities include: Ghent University; KU Leuven; University of Antwerp; Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Hasselt University
- Three research centres: VIB – focuses on biotech; imec – focuses on nanotech and digital technology; VITO – focuses on cleantech and sustainable development
- Two cluster organisations. Flanders.bio is the association of actors operating in life sciences sector in Flanders while Flanders.health is the cluster encompassing actors developing novel healthcare solutions
- Eleven accelerators and incubators of which the majority are either associated with universities, research centres or clusters listed here
- Six sciences parks: Tech Lane Ghent focuses on life sciences, material science, digital technology development; Science Park University of Antwerp focuses on health, environment, IT and logistics industries; BlueGate Antwerp focuses on growth companies; Arenberg Science Park, Haasrode Research Park and Leuven Noord Science are centred around Leuven with a focus on innovative high-tech enterprises and promoting international interest in Leuven
- Over 20 contract research organisations (CROs) in Flanders offering services for contracted research in life sciences (Belgium has roughly 244 CROs across all research fields)¹⁷³

Within the life science ecosystem VIB has played an active part in strengthening life sciences in Flanders, particularly the biotech sector which has experienced a boom over the past 25 years, growing from less than 10 life science companies to over 300 by 2021.¹⁷⁴

The core facilities discussed in the previous chapter enable VIB to be an active part of both regional and European level research activities. Within Flanders, the core facilities co-invested in state-of-the-art screening and proteomics infrastructure together with its partner universities. Furthermore, they were designed to be accessible to external researchers from their inception, allowing for non-VIB affiliated researchers to benefit from the same opportunities for high-tech equipment that is operating in the cores. On the European level, VIB core facilities are part of the Core for Life (C4L) and EU-LIFE initiatives where VIB is a founding member. The experience of developing the core facilities were carried over to the C4L and EU-LIFE, with VIB active in setting up the organisational structures and development roadmaps for the initiatives.¹⁷⁵

Beyond the cores, VIB runs both an accelerator and an incubator open to stakeholders from the ecosystem. Both are situated within the Tech Lane Ghent Science Park in Zwijnaarde which sees a concentration of biotech and life science companies and other actors. VIB Bio-

¹⁷³ Contract Research Map (2021). Belgium. Available at: <https://www.contractresearchmap.com/places/belgium>

¹⁷⁴ VIB (2021). Ecosystem. Available at: <https://vib.be/science-meets-business/ecosystem>

¹⁷⁵ VIB (2016). Annual Report 2016. Available at: <https://vib.be/sites/default/files/2016.pdf>

Incubator focuses on supporting technological development¹⁷⁶ while VIB Bio-Accelerator focuses on business services.¹⁷⁷

Furthermore, in 2004 VIB was one of the founding members of Flanders.bio an association of different actors operating in the life science sector. Since its inception Flander.bio has grown from around 60 members in 2004 to around 340 members in 2021.¹⁷⁸ As an organisation, Flanders.bio aims at facilitating access to research services, facilities and training and encourage research commercialisation, public-private partnerships and engagement between higher education and industry in life science development. Interestingly, the operations of Flanders.bio are similar to the approach discussed on how VIB enables translating research into entrepreneurial opportunities and provides access to novel technologies and promotes interdisciplinarity, particularly between life science and IT. Within the following figure, which visualises the activities of Flanders.bio parallels those of VIB except Flanders.bio includes the dimensions of education.

Figure 10 The strategy of Flamnders.bio

Source: Flanders.bio

This presents an argument of both VIB transferring best practices to the development of Flanders.bio and indicates how VIB, through its infrastructure comes to resemble the value chain from basic and experimental research to commercialised research. However, it must be stressed that Flanders.bio is a network organisation, connecting different actors in the ecosystem and enabling the ecosystem to function. But it does not perform research while VIB is a research organisation - an important differentiating factor.

¹⁷⁶ Bio-incubator (2021). Bio-incubator in the knowledge region Leuven. Available at: <https://vib.be/science-meets-business/ecosystem>

¹⁷⁷ Bio-Accelerator (2021). Business center. Available at: <http://www.bio-accelerator.com/en/business-centre>

¹⁷⁸ Flanders.bio (2021). History. Available at: <https://flanders.bio/en/history>

12.2.4 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

VIB handles support for innovation and commercialisation through a dedicated team embedded within the organisational infrastructure. The Innovation & Business team handles technology transfer matters in VIB, including: commercial exploitation of the results of this research through submission of patents, collaboration with the industry and the creation of innovative companies. Income from these activities exceeds 15% of the annual VIB budget and all profits are immediately ploughed back into research. As with most teams operating under the VIB headquarters, the Innovation & Business team runs specific units, projects, programmes, etc. that deal with activities within its area of interest.

Innovation & Business is divided into 4 smaller teams, each handling a different aspect of technology transfer. These teams are:

- VIB Discovery Science focuses on identifying promising fundamental research at VIB and facilitates its transition towards commercially viable product
- IP Management work with patent application and development of IP strategy. The team actively scouts for research that will require IP-related activities (i.e. filling applications)
- VIB Business Development manages business outreach and collaboration
- VIB New Ventures foster the development of start-ups from VIB research

Of these, VIB Business Development and VIB New Ventures were discussed previously in their role of attracting funding for research.

Before moving on to a deeper analysis of Discovery Science and IP Management it is important to recognise how VIB's internal policies shape technology transfer. Particularly, researchers join VIB on a five-year rolling tenure with performance KPIs that include technology transfer. This means that after the tenure is up the scientists' future in VIB also depends on their engagement in technology transfer as well as academic research.

Beyond that, the success of technology transfer depends on how well embedded it is in the organisational culture. Making technology transfer part of the organisational narrative is one method but also basing the support infrastructure around people that not only have a scientific background but are also knowledgeable in industry allows meeting both scientists and industry stakeholders on equal terms.

VIB Discovery Science

To discuss how the Innovation & Business supports researchers nearing early stages of research commercialisation we examine the function of VIB Discovery Sciences. A team composed of 20 people, it was established in 2015 VIB by the initiative of Innovation & Business manager, Discovery Sciences proactively analyses the academic research (biology) looking to identify promising drug discovery targets. This is based on the observation that VIB scientists often conduct fundamental research; however, even if this research leads to high quality scientific publications and breakthroughs there is a gap between drug discovery and drug discovery projects.

Discovery Sciences was established to bridge the gap between early research results and the interest of investors. Particularly, investor behaviour trends demonstrate interest to fund early-stage products while unwilling to consider early-stage research concepts.¹⁷⁹ Explaining these

¹⁷⁹ VIB (2019). Introducing VIB Discovery Sciences: an interview with Jérôme Van Biervliet. Available at: <https://vib.be/news/introducing-vib-discovery-sciences-interview-jerome-van-biervliet>

trends is the “valley of death” concept that compares the investment of academia and industry to research as it moves from fundamental research to commercialisation stages.¹⁸⁰

Figure 11 Research project commercialisation valley of death

Source: Global Engage

The Discovery Science team analyses the research being conducted in VIB to identify research projects that are approaching the “valley of death”. The team working at Discovery Science perform screening of research projects being engaged in VIB labs, looking for promising pharmaceutical innovations (VIB PI). Research identified as suitable is evaluated for commercialisation particularly paying attention to whether it is realistic to develop the target into medical products. Selected research is incubated to the stage where investors would be willing to consider the project for funding. At the same time, Discovery Science takes up the requirement for research to have socioeconomic impact. In this way, Discovery Science continues with the legacy of research being aligned to benefit society through the introduction to the market.

Crucially, the researchers themselves do not have to inform the Discover Science team about their interest. Researchers behind promising projects are contacted and, if interested, their work is discussed for valorisation analysis that is organised and performed by VIB Innovation & Business team. Discovery Science then works to attract interest from other academic can business stakeholders, building a foundation for the new company.

This can be examined with the case of Augustine Therapeutics – a spin-off company that achieved a seed-funding round (led by V-Bio Ventures, see below) worth €4.2m. An article on the company's experience notes how VIB Discovery Science team took upon themselves the roles that of CSO and COO while the team of V-Bio fulfilled the roles of CEO and CFO.¹⁸¹ For

¹⁸⁰ Global Engage (2020). Augustine Therapeutics: Bridging the Valley of Death with VIB Discovery Sciences. Available at: <http://www.global-engage.com/life-science/augustine-therapeutics-bridging-the-valley-of-death-with-vib-discovery-sciences/>

¹⁸¹ Global Engage (2020). Augustine Therapeutics: Bridging the Valley of Death with VIB Discovery Sciences. Available at: <http://www.global-engage.com/life-science/augustine-therapeutics-bridging-the-valley-of-death-with-vib-discovery-sciences/>

the researchers this meant that early on they were benefitting from business expertise that were not available to them with the chance to take up the business skills from the Discovery Science and V-Bio as their research was moving closer to an early-stage start-up ready for venture funding.

Figure 12 Incubation process

Discovery Science closely cooperation with V-Bio Ventures – an external early-stage venture capital for innovative companies in the life sciences area that develop solutions for high-demand unmet needs. While V-Bio Ventures work with start-ups from across Europe, they have a preferential link with VIB and it was estimated that 60%-70% of their deal flow comes from VIB.

The success of Discovery Science is attributed to the team, particularly the understanding of industry and investor needs. The 20 strong team is composed of people that have a scientific background but also developed industry experience, legal experience, financial experience, etc. before joining Discovery Science. This is regarded as a key success factor by the leadership of Innovation & Business who consider that it is better (and easier) to have scientists who develop industrial, legal, knowhow rather than trying to teach a lawyer about science.

IP Management

On the subject of IP rights, the Innovation & Business team has signed a framework agreement with VIB to hold exclusive rights to handle the IP-related activities and decisions resulting from VIB's research. This includes right to file IP, administer IP, commercialise IP. The commercial benefits from IP is shared equally between VIB and Innovation & Business team. By managing and marketing the portfolio of VIB patents and patent applications to businesses, the Innovation & Business team has achieved around 1500 agreements with local and international companies from biopharmaceutical, and agricultural industry.¹⁸²

The question of IP is handled by VIB's IP Management team (composed of members that include composed of European patent attorneys or patent attorneys in training). In their operation, the IP Management team work similarly to Discover Science – the IP Management team is proactive in identifying research, technologies, etc. developed in VIB that enter a stage

¹⁸² VIB (2021). Business Development. Available at: <https://vib.be/science-meets-business/business-development>

of instigating IP protection. However, researchers can also report on their inventions to the IP Management team through a standardised form.¹⁸³ The responsibilities of the IP Management team include: patentability assessment, patent landscaping, patent filing, patent defence and freedom to operate (FTO) analysis.¹⁸⁴ They are also involved in the development of IP strategies for VIB start-ups.

VIB core facilities

VIB has a total of 11 “cores” which have been established since 2014. The aim of the Core Facilities is to provide researchers access to novel technologies machinery required for scientific breakthroughs. The Core Facilities were conceived to solve the issue of maintaining scientific technologies required for research, including technical upkeep, infrastructure investment, the technical knowhow required to operate the technologies, etc. It was evident that the maintenance of the scientific technologies was beyond the scope of any one scientific group, university.

The core facilities were introduced to provide VIB researchers (and the partner universities) with access to focused technology aimed at specific life science research (i.e. VIB Genomics Core focuses on high-quality, affordable sequencing services).

- Bioinformatics Core provides high-resolution, high-quality bioimaging services. One is located in Ghent University and a second in KU Leuven
- Bioimaging Core, one is located in Ghent University and a second in KU Leuven. Offers services and training related to bioinformatics research
- Flow Core offers access to high-quality flow cytometry and fluorescence-activated cell sorting
- Metabolomics Core, one is located in Ghent University and a second in KU Leuven. Access to mass spectrometry-based metabolomic services
- Nanobody Core allows the development of Nanobodies and facilitates research related to therapeutics in human and animal health
- Nucleomics Core offers expert services for: expression analysis; miRNA analysis; RNA and DNA sequencing
- NMR core provides access to resonance spectrometers
- Protein Core works with in producing research-grade proteins
- Proteomics Core provides the services of mass spectrometry-driven proteome analyses
- Screening Core enables the development of miniaturised test systems and assays targeting the discovery of biologically active substances

Importantly, these cores are regarded as service providers to VIB researchers (and external customers). In other words, these are not dedicated labs; rather, these are akin to technology platforms that offer specific services related to life sciences. While external parties can have access to the core facilities for commercial rates, the primary intended user group are researchers from VIB and partner universities to drive novel research. In this way, the Core

¹⁸³ VIB (2021). VIB Record of Invention Form. Available at: new.vib.be/sites/default/files/VIB%20Record%20of%20Invention%20Form.docx

¹⁸⁴ VIB (2021). Intellectual Property at VIB. Available at: <https://vib.be/science-meets-business/intellectual-property-vib>

Facilities could be viewed as an enabling factor for further technology transfer but not for direct industry engagement.

The justification for establishing the specific core facilities was related to the trends in life science research, with VIB in particular noting that molecular biology and whole genome studies necessitated new research infrastructure to embed VIB as an institution on the cutting-edge of life sciences.¹⁸⁵ In order to achieve convergence, it was decided that the core facilities should combine life sciences, nanotechnologies and IT. IT in particular plays a role in connecting both the facilities and allowing access to them both for researchers from the VIB network and external parties interested in the services.

This process first began with the investment in supplying the cores to establish them as high-tech platforms capable of carrying out research in their areas of expertise. The technologies in question allowed for "servicing in transcript-, gen-, and proteomics, protein and antibody engineering, advanced light and electron microscopy, and in assay design and proof-of-concept compound screening".¹⁸⁶ In 2015 the technology development in the core facilities shifted towards increased networking between the cores and other VIB facilities. In other words, the cores were first created as autonomous technology platforms that were then interconnected.

The design of the core facilities is based on providing researchers, researcher groups with state-of-art technical equipment for research being conducted in life sciences. As such, the core facilities enable researchers to conduct projects that are technology-demanding. The staff of the core facilities focuses on utilisation of the technologies for on-demand work. In essence, the core facilities act as enablers and intermediaries between researchers and technologies.

12.3 Conclusions

Domain 1. Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence

The approach taken by VIB in establishing core facilities is one of providing accessibility to novel technologies. This accessibility is two-fold. First, the core facilities enable a wide range of researchers to benefit from the technologies by making them available for VIB's researchers (and those from the outside) through dedicated teams that are only responsible for running the relevant tech. This removes the need for researchers to understand novel technologies while making it easier for them to benefit from their research capacity. Secondly, through the Tech Watch programme, VIB ensures that researchers have access to the latest technologies, identifying them sometimes at piloting stages and involving researchers in understanding their applicability potential.

Domain 2. Funding from research to commercialisation

VIB New Ventures represents a comprehensive approach towards research commercialisation, with various teams, units, etc. at VIB involved from identifying potential research to attracting venture funding for start-ups (with V-BIO Ventures favouring VIB research). The approach VIB takes is only possible because of the wide infrastructure that it has built up over a long period (i.e. the aforementioned V-Bio fund was only established in 2015). The benefits of this is that VIB enables complete institutional support for their researchers looking for commercial opportunities, effectively eliminating the need for

¹⁸⁵ VIB (2014). Annual Report 2014. Available at: <https://vib.be/sites/default/files/2014.pdf>

¹⁸⁶ VIB (2015). Annual Report 2015. Available at: <https://vib.be/sites/default/files/2015.pdf>

external involvement in start-up establishment until the stage of venture capital funding (which is also at least partially covered by VIB).

Domain 3. Operating within innovation ecosystems

How VIB operates within the ecosystem reflects how it supports its researchers in that it enables access to services and networking between different actors to achieve research results. The Flemish life science ecosystem can operate as a closed value chain due to the number of different actors operating across research and commercialisation.

Domain 6. University innovation support and commercialisation systems

One of the key takeaways from how VIB approaches technology transfer is evident in the work of Discovery Science. A proactive approach in identifying research suitable for commercialisation shows how VIB tries to remove business consideration from the researchers, or rather, it eliminates the necessity for researchers to be heavily involved in business, administrative matters. However, this is made possible by a dedicated team that understand the industrial side of life science research and the needs of industrial partners.

13 Wageningen University and Research

13.1 Background and context

Wageningen University and Research represents an interesting look at the collaboration between Wageningen University and Wageningen Research – a joint infrastructure of two previously separated organisations that now make up WUR.

With a tradition in education and research that dates back over 100 years, WUR is regarded as one of the top education and research institutions for plant, animal, environmental and agricultural sciences.

Importantly, WUR presents a look at both the introduction of centralised data management principles to a large organisation as well as facilitating technology transfer through both traditional and novel approaches. Furthermore, WUR is an active participant in what is referred to in the Netherlands as the “golden triangle” scheme – a concept used to describe the traditional productive relationships between businesses (firms and farmers), the government and knowledge institutes to stimulate innovation. Thus, WUR presents an opportunity to focus on the domains 1, 3, and 6.

Wageningen University and Research is a joint partnership between Wageningen University and Wageningen Research. The history of WUR as a combination of university and research centre began in 1997 when the Wageningen University was merged with the Agricultural Research Service (*Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek – DLO*) and Institutes for Applied Research. However, under the laws in the Netherlands the Wageningen University and Wageningen Research have to remain separate legal entities.

This has resulted in an interesting organisational structure where Wageningen University and Wageningen Research share common operational management (Executive board), common strategic goals and some joint infrastructures (i.e. service facilities). However, the two sides are not allowed to share resources between themselves in the performance of their activities. Furthermore, the collaboration between University and Research is not strictly mandated by policies; rather, any collaboration results from the interest of the two parts to work together.

Support for this collaboration hinges on five science groups – Agrotechnology and Food Sciences Group; Animal Sciences Group; Environmental Sciences Group; Plant Sciences Group and Social Sciences Group - that connect the work done at the university and research halves at WUR. A science group consists of a Wageningen University department that is integrated into the organisational structure of appropriate Wageningen Research institute(s).¹⁸⁷

¹⁸⁷ WUR (2019). Annual report Wageningen University & Research 2019. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/show/Annual-report-WUR-2019.htm>

Figure 13 WUR organisational structure

Source: WUR

At the top of the WUR organisation structure is the Supervisory Board which links the institution directly to the Dutch Government. Particularly, members of the Supervisory Board are appointed by the Minister of Economic Affairs and in their role are direct representatives of the Minister. The role of the Board is to supervise governance and management of WUR and advise the Executive Board which is responsible for the operational management of WUR activities.

When considering commercial research outputs, since 1995 Wageningen University and Wageningen Research have contributed to the launch of 36 spin-off companies.

Figure 14 WUR spin-off timeline

Source: WUR

The division between University and Research spin-off stems from the aforementioned separation of resources between the two sides. This is also evident in the funding of WUR which separates the funding streams for the University and Research side.

Figure 15 WUR funding streams in 2019

Source: WUR

The following sections present WUR activities initiatives and programmes related to one of the domains that form the background of this analysis.

13.2 Domains of relevance for this case

13.2.1 Domain 1 – Digital life capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence

The way science groups combine the University and Research parts of WUR demonstrate the interconnection between the education and research parts of the organisation (especially since the science groups function through the integration of University department into corresponding Research institute). This interaction also helps explain the emergence of the Wageningen Data Competence Centre (WDCC) in 2018 and its role in facilitating research.

In essence the WDCC combines aspects of an intermediary support infrastructure and research infrastructure, supporting education provision, conducting research and technology transfer (which is referred to as value creation). As for the types of services the WDCC provides to WUR¹⁸⁸:

- In the field of data, the WDCC consults WUR members on the questions of data protection, ownership, quality, acquisition, identification, and data management.
- In the field of technology the WDCC advises regarding the infrastructure of hardware and software with which data is stored and processed.
- In the field of analytics, the WDCC keeps the overview of developments covering methodologies, applications, and algorithms in use for the interpretation of data and connects them when relevant.

WDCC was established as a centralised support unit that focuses on the developments in the field of Big Data, IoT, and data science. The WDCC is a small team that has been embedded into the infrastructure of WUR, chiefly collaborating with the different science groups and units.

Figure 16 Organisation of Wageningen Data Competence Centre

Source: WUR

The project teams work in one of five programmes (see below). The programme development is handled by a steering group (that holds roughly quarterly meetings) which establishes research topics for each programme. The steering group is composed of representative of WUR units and departments together with the Deans and the Value Creation Coordinator. The role of Value Creation Coordinator is divided into two parts and performed by two people:

¹⁸⁸ WUR (2018). Plan van aanpak voor het Wageningen Data Competence Center 2018. Available at: <https://edepot.wur.nl/443105>

- One is responsible for working with alliances, networks and coalitions. Their role is to ensure that WUR is represented in the infrastructures that are involved in digital data.
- The other is responsible for cooperation and outreach with industry. Their role is to facilitate public-private partnerships for the development and commercial application of research.

Department representatives are not just offering input on the direction of WDCC programmes. Back in their respective departments these representatives are known as Data Stewards – acting as a direct point of contact regarding (big) data policy and developments. It is regarded that the role of data stewards is much more important in terms of implementation rather than steering. Particularly, data stewards facilitate the implementation of the WDCC strategy by aligning the practices of their units towards the guidelines of the WDCC (for example that researchers follow data management practices as outlined by the WDC). This allows the WDCC to have a direct link to WUR education and research units, departments facilitating access and use of the WDCC services.¹⁸⁹

The project teams of the WDCC are organised along five programmes: research, education, value, data management and infrastructure. In collaboration with WUR units, the WDCC teams conduct case studies along each of those programmes analysing the potential impact of applying novel technologies. During the WDCC inception, several objectives were established for each programme. These included¹⁹⁰:

- For research: stimulate (digital) knowledge sharing within WUR, develop platforms and methodologies for making various types of data accessible within WUR, develop new concepts and services based on the collected data from WUR units.
- For education: organise data science education programme that could be applied in WUR bachelor, master, and PhD degree programmes, organise data science courses for WUR staff members.
- For value creation: organise a process that takes into account the opportunities for value creation from the outset in the development of new concepts and services based on big data, provides industry with opportunities for data science courses. Furthermore, WDCC is involved in advising science groups and units on licence related questions (for example how to model software, licencing software).
- For infrastructure: determine the infrastructure needs for research and education both inside and outside WUR. Furthermore, the WDCC provides infrastructure for data storage and machine learning. This ensures that scientists have access to infrastructure to store research data as well as expertise in how to utilise the information through data science (for example use of high-performance computing clusters).
- For data management: support policy development regarding research data management, help develop data infrastructure aimed at efficient use, exchange and integration of internal and external data. Here the role of data stewards comes in as they facilitate uptake of the WDCC guidelines for data management at WUR.

However, the WDCC faces challenges in its operations, specifically linked to the small team size with eight core team members, especially when compared to the roughly 6,500 employees of WUR. This means that the team is limited to the number of services it can provide to researchers at any given time. Because of this each of the 5 programmes involve activities that

¹⁸⁹ WUR (2021). FAQ Wageningen Data Competence Center. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Value-Creation-Cooperation/WDCC/FAQ-Wageningen-Data-Competence-Center.htm>

¹⁹⁰ WUR (2018). Plan van aanpak voor het Wageningen Data Competence Center 2018. Available at: <https://edepot.wur.nl/443105>

contribute towards raising the knowledge at WUR about the WDCC strategy for data management and data management and data science practices and benefits to research. Furthermore, the Data Stewards also help with knowledge transfer from the WDCC to the different science groups of WUR. This approach is also part of how the WDCC sees its operations going forward – as a facilitator of applying data science rather than a data science research unit.

By working on the individual programmes, the WDCC centralises and establishes common research data infrastructure at WUR. Similarly, to how WUR Science Groups connect the education and research part of WUR, the WDCC connects different science groups through the centralisation of Big Data in WUR. This makes it possible to work on a shared basis of data across the entire WUR. Here the importance of communication is highlighted to ensure that researchers are aware of opportunities to work with the WDCC. Researchers can contact the Centre through phone or e-mail to start the conversation about their needs and how the WDCC can support their work.

The development of the WDCC was at least in part inspired by the trends regarding data management. In particular, attention was paid to the growing interest at European level for the development of an international research infrastructure (i.e. European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI); European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)) while observing how private corporations (i.e. Google, Amazon) continue to invest in the development of data management infrastructures and Big Data analytics.¹⁹¹ It was regarded that a common research data infrastructure will enable WUR to be better positioned to respond to the emerging trends in data management and data analytics. Beyond identifying data management trends, it was also recognised that data management and data science activities within WUR were fragmented, as each science group could have different approaches. Thus, the establishment of WDCC presented an opportunity to achieve better institutional coordination towards data management, data storage and data science. This is considered the biggest added value by the WDCC – aligning approaches to data management and data science that leads to stronger connectivity between the different science groups, researchers at WUR.

In this regard, the WDCC represents the optimisation of research and education process, at least regarding the use of data. Through the Data Stewards and centralised data management and analysis services, the WDCC also creates further linkages between WUR units and departments. In a way, WUR found how to respond to evolving trends for research data management while also facilitating further collaboration opportunities between its various units and departments.

13.2.2 Domain 2 – Funding from research to venture capital

StartLife accelerator funding instruments

WUR hosts the StartLife accelerator which is regarded as one of Europe's leading accelerators for innovative Food and Agtech start-ups. StartLife offers training, mentoring, funding, and access to community of start-ups, investors, corporates and field experts.

¹⁹¹ WUR (2018). Plan van aanpak voor het Wageningen Data Competence Center 2018. Available at: <https://edepot.wur.nl/443105>

On the subject of funding, StartLife runs two funding programmes for start-ups:¹⁹²

- StartLife Pre-Seed Funding is available to start-ups admitted to the StartLife Accelerate programme (must also be registered in the Netherlands). The funding is a pre-seed loan of up to €75,000 that is divided into two payments: 1) a payment of €25,000 after successful completion of the StartLife Accelerate programme and 2) €50,000 after reaching milestones agreed with the StartLife team. There is also an optional additional one-time investment of €175,000 for start-ups that the accelerator views as with high potential. For each part of the payment the start-up presents their pitch to the StartLife's Review Board which is composed of agrifood investors and serial-entrepreneurs.
- StartLife Student Start-up Loan is aimed at WUR graduates looking to fund their start-up. The Loan is up to €8,000 and provided to recent graduates (up two years since graduating from WUR) and they haven't registered a start-up at the Dutch chamber of commerce for over five years.

Since its foundation in 2010 StartLife has supported and funded 300+ start-ups.¹⁹³ By 2018, the accelerator had invested around €68m as pre-seed capital in its start-ups.¹⁹⁴

13.2.3 Domain 3 – Operating within innovation ecosystems

The Food Valley

The Food Valley was established in 2004 as a private-public cluster network organisation of food companies and research companies. Since then, it has quickly become the leading actor in the agri-food innovation and development both in the Netherlands and internationally.

Both WUR and the Food Valley are active in what is referred to in the Netherlands as the “golden triangle” scheme¹⁹⁵ a concept used in the Netherlands to describe the traditional productive relationships between businesses (firms and farmers), the government and knowledge institutes to stimulate innovation.¹⁹⁶ The Dutch agricultural innovation system is characterised by its complexity and many institutions actively taking part in the golden triangle model. Recently, this metaphor has been broadened to the “Dutch Diamond”, which advocates for the collaboration of NGOs/civil society, private sector, government, and knowledge institutions when tackling challenges.¹⁹⁷ In essence the Dutch Diamond recognises that on an ecosystem level, challenges require multi stakeholder involvement to account for different perspectives and achieve fruitful public-private partnerships.

¹⁹² StartLife (2020). StartLife funding opportunities for startups. Available at: <http://start-life.nl/startups/funding-opportunities-for-startups/>

¹⁹³ EIT Food (2021). StartLife. Available at: <https://www.eitfood.eu/partners/partner/startlife>

¹⁹⁴ Kalaitzandonakes N. et al. (2018). From Agriscience to Agribusiness– Theories, Policies and Practices in Technology Transfer and Commercialization

¹⁹⁵ OECD (2015). Innovation, Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability in the Netherlands. Available at: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/agriculture-and-food/innovation-agricultural-productivity-and-sustainability-in-the-netherlands_9789264238473-en

¹⁹⁶ Finfacts (2020). Dutch food innovation lessons for Ireland. Available at: <https://www.finfacts-blog.com/2020/05/dutch-food-innovation-lessons-for.html>

¹⁹⁷ knowledge4food (2015). Scaling up Dutch Efforts for Global Nutrition. Available at: https://knowledge4food.net/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/150310_GNRevent_report_final.pdf

Figure 17 Dutch Diamond

Source: How the Netherlands Became Leading in Seed Sector Innovation: the Dutch Diamond Approach

The Dutch agri-food sector is also considered one of the “top sectors”, which is part of a policy to channel targeted investment to key sectors. The agrifood sector is considered of strategic importance to the Dutch economy, with around 5,300 agrifood companies operating in the country and resulting in the Netherlands being the 2nd largest exporter of agrifood products globally.¹⁹⁸

By 2020 the Food Valley encompassed 15,000 food scientists and engineers in a radius of 50km from WUR, yet companies throughout the Netherlands participate and/or benefit. The hub has about 200 companies within a 10km radius of Wageningen, which include both start-ups and large companies (i.e. Royal FrieslandCampina, Kraft Heinz, Unilever).¹⁹⁹ The Food Valley greatly contributes to the Netherlands agrifood sector.

Entrepreneurship and cooperation in the Food Valley

As part of the support and development infrastructure that is designed to enhance the performance of Food Valley members (as well as attract or help establish new ones). The process of accelerating innovations is supported by accelerator and scale-up programmes in the Food Valley.²⁰⁰

- A scale-up programme – ScaleUpFood – is run to support the scaling food and agriculture businesses. Envisioned as a transfer of global practices in business scaling, the programme runs as 2 parts. First, research is conducted to develop a comprehensive look at the success factors of international food and agri scale-up companies. Following the research phase, businesses in the Food Valley are targeted based on their potential for scale-up. These

¹⁹⁸ Invest in Holland (2018). Financial Times Highlights Holland’s Innovative Food Valley. Available at: <https://investinholland.com/news/financial-times-highlights-hollands-innovative-food-valley/>

¹⁹⁹ Finfacts (2020). Dutch food innovation lessons for Ireland. Available at: <https://www.finfacts-blog.com/2020/05/dutch-food-innovation-lessons-for.html>

²⁰⁰ Food Valley (2021). Startup and scaleup support. Available at: <https://www.foodvalley.nl/grow-your-business/start-a-company/>

businesses are invited to participate in a programme that includes best practice transfer, partnering with corporates and innovative mid-caps in the Netherlands.

- Oost NL (part of the Dutch regional development agencies) runs entrepreneurial development programme that are designed to enhance entrepreneurial skills of participants. Businesses can register for the programme and receive an e-scan (entrepreneurial scan) that gages their business skills. Participants then undergo training sessions (webinars, coaching) that end with a follow-up e-scan to demonstrate the improvement in entrepreneurial practise. Participants can request reimbursement vouchers (up to 80%) to cover the costs of training and coaching.²⁰¹

The focus on facilitating entrepreneurship and availability of infrastructure has been noted as an important contributor to the successful functioning of the agrifood ecosystem in the Netherlands. This has been reflected in the long-term programme Foodvalley 2030 (formerly AgriFood 2030) that was developed at the request of the Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate, Ede and of Wageningen Municipalities, Agri & Food Topsector, Wageningen University & Research, Unilever (multinational consumer goods company), FrieslandCampina (dairy cooperative in the Netherlands) with the authorities from the Province of Gelderland in a coordinating role. The purpose of the programme is to provide a long-term vision, goals and funding for continued development of the agrifood sector in the Netherlands.

The Foodvalley 2030 programme notes the importance of cooperation between members of the ecosystem. An interview with the managing director of Food Valley, Roger van Hoesel, notes that the share of knowledge and resources has been a contributing factor to the success of Food Valley.²⁰² Greater access to information and development opportunities, ability to engage in knowledge transfer with other Food Valley actors allows for an ecosystem to emerge. As part of the programme, long-term funding is planned to facilitate continued partnerships in the Valley as it was viewed that at the time partnerships were more short-term developments that focused on producing specific outcomes and moving towards new partnerships. With the 2030 programme Food Valley hopes to achieve long-term cooperation that would facilitate more ambitious research that can react to disruptions in the agrifood sector.

Shared Facility Finder

As part of the efforts to increase access to research, innovation, technology, Food Valley runs the Shared Facility Finder. The service, managed by WUR and the Food Valley (organisation), the Finder is set up to enable quick access for members to available infrastructure for:

- Scale up & production – maps the current Valley businesses interested in partnering to support scale-up of other businesses
- Development & demonstration – maps the available spaces for product development and testing in the Valley
- Advanced research equipment – the Valley maps over 300 different research equipment that are available to members

²⁰¹ De Startversneller (2021). Het Startversneller traject. Available at: <https://www.destartversneller.nl/de-startversneller/>

²⁰² Food Valley (2019). AgriFood 2030: the foundation for a long-term strategy. Available at: <https://www.foodvalley.nl/news/agrifood-2030-lays-the-foundation-for-a-long-term-strategy/#en>

- Investment & funding – supports investment into facilities that are not yet available in the Valley. The primary conditions are that if the Valley invests in the development of new infrastructure, it has to be made available to other members as part of the Shared Facility Finder

Members of the Food Valley can register for the Shared Facility Finder can register freely as an entirely voluntary service. Especially the last Investment & Funding category showcases how the Shared Facility initiative enables the emergence of new technologies, development spaces that are then made available to other members. In this way the Valley ensures easier access to development infrastructure.²⁰³

Shared Facilities are embedded in WUR's infrastructure with a dedicated team responsible for managing operations and support and governed by a steering group. The development of the Shared Facilities at WUR is the responsibility of the Scientific Advisory Board Shared Research Facilities that provides recommendations for which WUR technologies, equipment laboratories should become part of Shared Facilities (these are generally larger infrastructures that would benefit industrial partners) and expanding the service (i.e. investing in new equipment). Some of the technologies, equipment offered through Shared Facilities is acquired jointly with industrial partners. Users can either run the research equipment themselves or work with technicians at WUR (however certain equipment can only be run by WUR staff). Users are charged only for the time spent using the equipment and they own the research results.²⁰⁴

By 2019 the Shared Research Facilities accounted for 559 different pieces of equipment of which 305 pieces were available for external party use and two pieces of equipment belong to an external party (Unilever) that are hosted by WUR. Of the 559 pieces of research equipment 86 were acquired because of Shared Research Facilities identifying their need. In 2019 the average occupancy of the research equipment available through Shared Research Facilities was 60%.²⁰⁵

For WUR, the added value of shared facilities (beyond the fact that the system facilitates access to research equipment to their own researchers) is in enabling partnerships and cooperation. Attracting external parties to WUR to conduct their work is seen as a gateway for further cooperation. In this way the low cost for use of Shared Facilities is made up by outcomes of potential joint research in the future.

13.2.4 Domain 6 – University innovation support and commercialisation systems

Corporate Value Creation department

The approach to technology and/or knowledge transfer in WUR is a combination of historic decentralisation with recent efforts to introduce more centralised approaches. WUR has historically shown to be preferable at WUR. In 2004 WUR launched the Wageningen Business Generator (WBG) that was designed to help commercialise research being conducted at WUR, provide support on legal, IP and commercial matters and increase interest in commercialisation among WUR researchers. While WBG was supposed to be cash-flow neutral (with an annual revenue at €3m) it only managed to achieve a third of that (with the actual

²⁰³ Food Valley (2021). Shared Facilities. Available at: <https://www.foodvalley.nl/grow-your-business/shared-facilities/>

²⁰⁴ WUR (2021). Using the facilities of Shared Research Facilities. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Value-Creation-Cooperation/Collaboration-with-WUR/Facilities-Tools/Wageningen-Shared-Research-Facilities/Using-our-facilities.htm>

²⁰⁵ WUR (2019). Annual report Wageningen University & Research 2019. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/show/Annual-report-WUR-2019.htm>

annual revenue reportedly at €1m). The failure of WBG was attributed to a lack of interest among the business partners of WUR as well as WUR researchers – both of which preferred a decentralised approach where different research institutes would continue to deal with the question of IP, commercial opportunities, business engagement, through direct contact rather than through a specialised TTO. More recently similar opinions on decentralisation were evident before the launch of the WDCC where it was recognised that different science groups had different approaches to data management and data science. This shows that historically WUR has been trying to introduce more centralised approaches; however, at least in the case of WBG the efforts would be unsuccessful and WBG would be shut down in 2008.²⁰⁶

Emerging from the economic crisis of the early-to-mid 2010s, WUR made a second attempt to introduce a more centralised approach to value creation. This resulted in the establishment of the Corporate Value Creation department (CVC) in 2017 that was given the responsibility of supporting technology transfer, public-private partnerships, entrepreneurship at WUR (including spin-offs and start-ups).²⁰⁷ Note that the launch happened around the time where the WDCC was also being introduced (2018) showing that after a decade WUR was more open to infrastructure that established more linkages, common approaches between the science groups. CVC has several sub-units responsible for different activities.

- CVC Entrepreneurship works with potential spin-off, supporting the establishment process and ensuring the spin-offs meet WUR guidelines
- CVC Knowledge Transfer supports the five WUR Science Groups in determining pathways for value creation (both in the public and private sectors)

The function of spin-offs and start-ups in the context of WUR is governed through a set of guidelines dealing with the process of establishing spin-offs/start-ups as well as intellectual property questions. This also reflects one of the ways in which WUR handles technology transfer (though other approaches will be discussed as well).

Spin-offs can be launched in one of two ways: either as part of knowledge transfer or CVC receives a direct request from a company to create a spin-off based on WUR research. Furthermore, a set of criteria are established that a potential UR spin-off must meet. These include:²⁰⁸

- The spin-off being established deals with the commercialisation of WUR Knowledge. WUR Knowledge is defined as either intellectual property rights or research assets
- While not mandatory, it is preferable that a representative of WUR (i.e. student, current/former WUR employee) is involved in at least: “incorporation, equity participation and/or fulfilment of a central operational/strategic role within the company, with which he/she makes an important contribution to its development.”
- The spin-off is being established in relation to WUR's mission
- If the spin-off is success in its operations, it should result in economic benefits to the Netherlands

²⁰⁶ Kalaitzandonakes N. et al. (2018). From Agriscience to Agribusiness– Theories, Policies and Practices in Technology Transfer and Commercialization

²⁰⁷ WUR (2018). Annual report 2018. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/show/Annual-report-2018.htm>

²⁰⁸ WUR (2020). Regulations for establishing WUR spin-off companies (spin-off regulations). Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/show/WUR-spin-off-regulations-ENG-310820-DEF.htm>

Notably the last point shows established a connection between WUR spin-offs and benefits to the Dutch economy, indicating a degree of corporate responsibility is built into the design of a WUR spin-off. As for WUR start-ups, the following criteria are used for their definition:

- A WUR start-up is established by a member of WUR staff, alumni and/or students
- A WUR start-up is established for the purpose of utilising and further developing non-protected and public knowledge
- The founders of WUR start-ups can utilise the general knowledge and experience acquired from WUR

The process of establishing a spin-off involves several different parts, people at WUR with the CVC being heavily involved in the preparation and support of the spin-off launch. When a member of WUR wishes to launch a spin-off, they must contact the director of their respective Science Group and inform CVC of their intention via a draft proposal. If the directors of the Science Group and CVC approve of the plans, a Value Creation Assessment Team (VCAT) is appointed, consisting of: CVC Knowledge Transfer staff, a business developer, the legal staff from the Sciences Group and/or Corporate Staff unit, external advisor(s) if requested.

The VCAT represents WUR's interests and ensures the process of launching the spin-off is in line with WUR's requirements and expectations. The team is responsible for preparing the spin-off proposal and evaluating the business plan for the spin-off (developed by the employee). The spin-off proposal outlines the use of UR knowledge and future (if any) role of WUR in the spin-off's activities. If the spin-off does not ask/require exclusive access to WUR knowledge its establishment is approved by the directors of CV and the Science Group. In the event that the spin-off asks/requires exclusive use of WUR knowledge, the approval process goes to the Executive Board. In particular, the Executive Board becomes involved if the spin-off in questions requires an equity position from WUR. In general, WUR's policy is to sign licensing agreements with spin-offs over equity participation. Equity interest is only really considered if WUR's knowledge is still being developed and the spin-offs would benefit from reduced payments to WUR or the spin-off is regarded as being strategically important to WUR.²⁰⁹

WUR spin-off label

Beyond the process of launching spin-offs and start-ups, WUR has recently introduced a new support scheme for entrepreneurial endeavours. In December 2020 WUR launched the WUR spin-off label for companies that successfully underwent the accreditation process to launch the spin-off. Such companies are permitted to use the WUR spin-off as part of general communication but not for marketing purposes.

One of the goals that drove the launch of the label was to have a more visible way of demonstrating how WUR contributes to emergence of new companies. For businesses this provides evidence of a solid background in agriculture innovation, as noted in the following interview with developers of the Peek educational app: "The acknowledgement of our business as a WUR spin-off is very important to us. Being permitted to carry the WUR spin-off label is a valuable gesture of recognition. With WUR as our development partner, we can show the market that we are a serious business. Although we are commercially independent, our collaboration with WUR remains of great value to us."²¹⁰ This offers an example of utilising the

²⁰⁹ WUR (2020). Regulations for establishing WUR spin-off companies (spin-off regulations). Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/show/WUR-spin-off-regulations-ENG-310820-DEF.htm>

²¹⁰ WUR (2020). WUR launches label for spin-offs with WUR expertise. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/newsarticle/WUR-launches-label-for-spin-offs-with-WUR-expertise.htm>

positive image of academia to enhance business development and use the brand of an institution. However, as the spin-off is still new and few spin-offs were awarded (by March 2021) it remains unknown how much will the label contribute towards collaboration with industry.

StartLife mentoring programme

The StartLife accelerator mentioned in Domain 2 also has a mentoring programme. The programme runs for 3-4 months with a minimum of 8 hours per month spent with the mentor (though there is no set number of monthly meetings/interactions). The list of StartLife mentors includes business executives, entrepreneurs with several successful ventures in their portfolio, investors, and professionals. The mentors provide insights on the subjects of: "business development, management, communications, legal and accounting, retail, and e-commerce."²¹¹

The matching of the mentors and the mentees is more the responsibility of the applying mentee. They must apply for the programme and the application process includes selecting up to three mentors from the mentor list with StartLife representatives then checking for mentor availability. StartLife organises meetings with mentors after which a mentorship agreement is signed if the mentor and mentee want to proceed with the mentorship programme.

WDCC informing on commercialisation opportunities

The WDCC also plays a role in enabling commercialisation. As the WDCC works with the science groups, members of the WDCC have noticed a trend where members of Wageningen Research interact with WDCC more often than those of Wageningen University. This in turn presents an environment where members of Wageningen Research are more aware of opportunities to utilise data science and be involved in technology transfer. To increase interest within Wageningen University the WDCC team has found that workshops and awareness raising activities about opportunities to utilise data science for research commercialisation. Furthermore, the WDCC advises researchers on the steps they could take to make their research more appealing for industry.

Knowledge transfer in WUR's research centres

Regarding knowledge transfer practices that are outside start-up/spin-off launches, it can be argued that these reflect the history of decentralised knowledge and technology practices (discussed in the opening of this chapter). Specifically, WUR's research centres have different approaches used to engage public and private stakeholders, ranging from contract work, operating specialised TTOs and other types of programmes. Interestingly, these approaches can include requirements that connect private interest with societal impacts. The following presents the knowledge transfer infrastructure of WUR's research centres:

- Knowledge Transfer Centre De Marke (KTC De Marke) supports knowledge transfer from the Wageningen Livestock Research and Wageningen Plant Research institutes. KTC De Marke is focused on research related to farm management, particularly in the areas of reducing different emissions (nitrogen, phosphorus and carbon) and minimise the usage of concentrates and inorganic fertilisers in farming practice. The research results of KTC De Marke are shared with farm advisors and dairy farmers. The Centre also offers practical demonstrations in the form of expert meetings (events organised on specific topics); excursions for farm advisors, farmers and policy makers (KTC De Marke operates as a

²¹¹ StartLife (2020). Startup Mentor Program. Available at: <https://start-life.nl/startup-mentor-program/>

research farm so farmers can see practical implementation of new farming practices, technologies); workshops; training sessions; lectures.²¹²

- Wageningen Centre for Development Innovation engages in a broad range of capacity upgrading activities that are connected to furthering sustainable development goals. The Centre offers partners the following products and services: programme design and implementation, process facilitation, training and advisory services and action research, online courses.²¹³
- Wageningen Bioveterinary Research acts as a contract research organisation (CRO) that specialises in health and veterinary studies. Private parties can gain access to: clinical, pre-clinical and pre-competitive studies; animal disease research including drug, vaccine development.²¹⁴ Bioveterinary Research has sophisticated animal and laboratory facilities (including operating room) with security protocols (up to biosafety level 3) for testing animal diseases. An ethics committee is in place to ensure that the unit operates under the Dutch laws on animal experiments.²¹⁵
- Wageningen Economic Research is an institute that conducts research related to developing a sustainable food system. As part of this, the Economic Research institute supports businesses through market and consumer behaviour analysis.²¹⁶
- Wageningen Environmental Research provides access to several databases related to the agriculture sector. Specifically, it manages the Land Use Database of the Netherlands (LGN database) that provides mapping (using satellite imaging) of land distribution between agricultural crops, forests, water, nature, and urbanisation. Users pay per square kilometre, though, the database can be made accessible for education purposes.²¹⁷ Environmental Research also manages the Dutch Soil Information System (SIS) database that offers interested parties with information on soil data including presenting information on sustainable soil and groundwater use.²¹⁸

The knowledge and/or technology transfer services available from WUR research centres shows how, even in enabling commercialisation and partnership with the private sector, WUR also looks to facilitate societal benefits. For example, the Economic Research centre provide businesses with market research, business development services that are at the same time linked to enabling a more sustainable food system to emerge. In other words, the centre's work

²¹² WUR (2012). What is the importance of KTC De Marke for the Dutch dairy sector? Available at: https://www.wur.nl/upload_mm/4/a/4/5a4ed7aa-01d8-4123-8403-21842e0c07dd_De%20Marke%201.pdf

²¹³ WUR (2021). Managing for Sustainable Development Impact: Making informed decisions. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Research-Results/Research-Institutes/centre-for-development-innovation/Our-Value-Propositions/Managing-for-Sustainable-Development.htm>

²¹⁴ WUR (2021). Bioveterinary Research. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/show/General-information-Wageningen-Bioveterinary-Research.htm>

²¹⁵ WUR (2021). Combined Animal and Laboratory Services. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/show/Animal-and-Laboratory-Services.htm>

²¹⁶ WUR (2021). Market Intelligence: a comprehensive view of the future. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Research-Results/Research-Institutes/Economic-Research/Research-topics-WEcR/Market-Intelligence-a-comprehensive-view-of-the-future.htm>

²¹⁷ WUR (2021). The Land Use Database of the Netherlands (LGN database). Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Research-Results/Research-Institutes/Environmental-Research/Facilities-Tools/Kaarten-en-GIS-bestanden/Land-use-database-of-the-Netherlands.htm>

²¹⁸ WUR (2021). Dutch Soil Information System (SIS). Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Research-Results/Research-Institutes/Environmental-Research/Facilities-Tools/Dutch-Soil-Information-System-SIS.htm>

aims to maintain commercial opportunities for businesses but having them aligned with positive societal impact.

Akkerweb platform

Lastly, to discuss how societal impacts are generated through knowledge transfer and application of data science, we look at the Akkerweb platform. Launched in 2016 as a joint development between WUR and Agrifim (though since 2020 WUR is the sole manager), Akkerweb is a geo-based platform compiling and offering access to farming data.²¹⁹

As part of its function, Akkerweb compiles geo and farming data from different sources into a single centralised platform that not only stores said data but also allows users to see how different data connects to make informed decisions. This is possible because the use of the platform is free for farmers, researchers to make use of.²²⁰ Farmers can also upload their own data to the apply the data analysis models available on the platform to perform analysis for them (for example chemicals they might need to use, how to optimise crop-rotation).

An important consideration is that the platform cannot be used for commercial research and this aspect is supported by the WDCC. As part of their communication and outreach activities, the WDCC highlights the potential of Akkerweb as a research toll while noting that the research itself cannot be connected to commercialisation.

13.3 Conclusions

Domain 1. Digital life research capacity, transdisciplinarity and convergence

The approach WUR took in the development of Data Competence Centre is inspired by the organisation structure where the University and Research sides must remain separate legal entities but internally efforts are made to establish cooperation pathways between University and Research. Particularly, the role of Data Stewards should be highlighted as a way of embedding data analytics and management into the organisational structure. The Stewards represent different WUR departments. The data stewards help embed WDCC advice and guidelines. At the same time, the Stewards are also the first point of contact between their respective departments and the Data Competence Centre. This enables the different departments of WUR to have a say in how the Data Competence Centre supports work at WUR while the Centre is represented at the department level by people who have a good understanding of both the Centre and the department.

Domain 3. Operating within innovation ecosystems

One interesting aspect of how WUR operates in the ecosystem can be noted through the Shared Facilities. Making research equipment and spaces available for only small cost (payment is made for the time spend only) can be considered a gateway approach. The use of Shared Research facilities is unlikely to generate significant profit for WUR. However, opening their research space to external stakeholders raises the potential for partnerships to emerge as external parties become more interested in further partnership with WUR (or WUR sees potential in the novel research being conducted).

Domain 6. University innovation support and commercialisation systems

²¹⁹ WUR (2019). New strategic focus for Akkerweb. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/newsarticle/New-strategic-focus-for-Akkerweb.htm>

²²⁰ WUR (2020). Akkerweb A Platform for Precision Farming Data, Science and Practice. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Value-Creation-Cooperation/Collaborating-with-WUR-1/WDCC/data-portal/Former-Spotlight-datasets/dataset-akkerweb.htm>

As aspect that should be highlighted regarding WUR's spin-offs is the built-in requirement for spin-offs to achieve economic benefit for the Netherlands (provided that the spin-off is profitable). This immediately showcases the position WUR takes to research commercialisation in that it should have benefits not only to the company but enhance the research and innovation of the Netherlands. This showcases how research commercialisation rules can be developed to achieve benefits beyond commercial gain, with potential for social benefits to be included as part of regulations to launch spin-offs.

The WUR spin-off label is an interesting approach to enhance the position, performance of the spin-offs but it hinges on the fact that WUR has an international reputation for excellence in agrifood research and education. As it stands, the strength of WUR as a brand is sufficient to make spin-offs interested in the label, seeing the benefits of other businesses recognising their innovation potential based on the WUR branding. The transferability of such idea would hinge on the position of the parent institution nationally and/or internationally – depending on the target markets.

technopolis
group

www.technopolis-group.com